

Impact of Internet on the Printing Industry in Saudi Arabia

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DECLARATION

I declare that the thesis is my own personal effort. I took reasonable care to ensure that the work is original, and, to the best of my knowledge, does not breach copyright law, and has not been taken from other sources except where such work has been cited and acknowledged within the text. The thesis has been carried out in accordance with the regulations of the University of the West of Scotland. This thesis has not been submitted to any other institution in any part of the world for any other academic award.

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ABSTRACT

Printing and Publishing Industry are faced with a decline in the developed markets of the western world. This decline has been attributed to the rise of internet enabled technology which has shifted the landscape in the favour of Digital Print in Comparison to Traditional Print. Similar trends have been witnessed in the developing markets of the Saudi Arabia where majority of the industry is comprised of small-to-medium sized printing firms. This study explores the challenges faced by these firms due to technological disruption in a bid to help these business transform. The study also will provide recommendation to the current product mix strategy and substitution by the internet there by creating a sustainable product mix. The study follows a mixed research design approach with 250 participants who are active users of the printing products and services in Saudi Arabia. Qualitative data is collected from 5 semi structured interviews with industry experts from a local printing house in Saudi Arabia – Al Fakhoor. The key findings of this research point out to the need for product diversification by Saudi printing firms; need to develop skills and capacity to transition into the digital print media; shifting customer needs with customer now expecting add on services such as digital advertising/marketing or lead generations; In adept marketing capabilities; and so forth. The most impact of this study is linked with guiding SMEs printing firms towards diversification of their existing product mix to make it make it more aligned with future needs of the client. The thesis argues in favour of market building for new services and products as printing firms are urged to rethink what it means to be a printer in the digital age?

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1 CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 RESEARCH BACKGROUND

In the current dynamic environment, technological advances and innovations affect almost every area and industry in both positive and negative ways. In this context, the invention of the internet and computers aided technologies enabled industries to enhance their operational and management processes as well as return on investments to satisfy needs and preferences in significant ways (Dillman, 2011). The potential of the internet has catalysed novel ways of doing business, incubated new and emerging ideas of its application such as e-commerce and digital business (Apăvăloaie, 2019).

It has been observed in research such as Ellonen (2006); Gilaninia (2011), and Jadoon, et al. (2011) that the internet has transformed business processes and working styles of individuals to a great extent. The internet has made it possible for people to connect with each other beyond national boundaries and enabled businesses to strengthen their technical infrastructure. Some major benefits of the internet to the customer are more robust business service deliverability options as companies are able to offer high performance connectivity solutions to their customers, decreased costs, increased quality and speed of service and ramping up functionality of business communication with the external as well as internal world (Alotaibi, 2013). The internet supports business growth and prosperity in terms of reduced costs, decreased manual labour, promote automation, transmission of digital information, secure huge data, protect important documents and reduce stress in the workplace (Meersman, 2004). Similarly, in marketing, social media and digital communication allow businesses to promote and support efforts to create a strong brand image, create and propagate awareness about product and service offerings among consumers within a few seconds and aid in the development of long-term relationships with consumers and stakeholders (Batra, 2013).

However, many scholars and researchers such as Brokaw and Reed (2010), and Qasem (2015) analysed that the internet also has a negative impact on various industries. Printing and paper publication are one such industry, which has felt the adverse impact of the growth of the internet. The proliferation of the internet has made it easy for people to read news online, use digital messaging applications to share with friends, colleagues, families, find information about a multitude of products, rather than read brochures and pamphlets and send personal and invitation messages over social media have become more preferable to traditional cards and invitation formats (Gilaninia, 2011).

Printing and paper publishing industry has been affected as the volume of printing newspapers, invitation cards, magazines, brochures, and pamphlets, visiting cards, etc. around the world has gone through noticeable reductions. Research has also pointed out that the internet has morphed into a competitive medium for the printing industry which has perpetuated the need to significantly change the ways of doing business to ensure its survival (Li, 2013). However, the positives are that the internet also helps to reduce end pricing and printing time, maintain a lower cost of production as well as enhance the profitability by inserting advertisements on internet sites (Frey and Sayad, 2015).

Before the mid-1990s, communication was split into three categories namely print, broadcast and telephony. Print was one of the oldest mediums and created a globally higher demand for paper. The advent of digital technology has changed that paradox with the transition from analogue to digital. To remain competitive, the printing companies and industry must adopt different strategies of digital communication to significantly ensure both survival and profitability (Lamb, 2012).

The printing industry is one of the dynamic industries of the world, which has always embraced new and innovative tools and techniques to provide the best experience to readers and

customers. Printing companies typically offer three types of business solutions such as advertising and marketing, publishing, and stationery. The adoption of internet technologies helps the industry to accomplish novel variations in printing processes and products (Diehl and Karmasin, 2013). Utilisation of the internet and application of digital technologies enable copy centres, business centres and related print products manufacturers to produce, print and distribute large volumes of printing copies and other printable materials in significant ways.

One prominent effect of the internet is that it has reduced the demand of newsprint by as much as 62 per cent between the years 1999 to 2012 in the USA (Burton, 2016). Not only in the USA, but also in other global markets in Asia, the Middle East such as the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, the demand and growth of the printing industry has witnessed a slowdown. The internet and its associated technologies, in effect has become a substitution of the printing industry in the global market and has created a crisis, mainly for small and medium-sized enterprises (SME), which produces printed invitation card, business cards, and local and fashion magazines, among others. Moreover, in the same timeframe, advertising revenues also fell by 60% as marketers switched to digital media (FESPA, 2014). The trend today demonstrates that people prefer to communicate more on Social Networking Sites (SNS) and digital messaging applications such as WhatsApp as well as prefer to find information, procure, and read newspapers and magazines online rather than purchase traditional print versions.

Saudi Arabia's printing industry, with an annual expansion rate of 8 per cent, prints 5.2 million copies of daily newsprint and an estimated 2 million copies of monthly magazines, making it the third largest producer in MENA behind Lebanon and Egypt (Saudi Print & Pack, 2016). Therefore, Saudi Arabia's printing industry continues to benefit from such a robust demand and enhance its profitability significantly.

The Saudi printing industry is traditional as it is based on the way of life and values of the country. However, the printing industry of Saudi Arabia is only now adopting modernization, albeit slowly, by encouraging the use of latest technology such as the internet and 3D printing. Many printing companies such as Canon, Agfa, Kodak, Fujifilm, HP, as well as other newspaper and magazine companies are increasingly focused on adopting latest technologies in digital printing in the country in order to provide the best experience to customers (Arab News, 2014).

In the context of these discussions, this research finds significance in evaluating the impact of the internet and digital technology on the traditional printing industry of Saudi Arabia. While most printing companies are beginning to adopt digital channels such as social media, smart phones, and online sites to communicate with the customers and provide information, the adverse effects of the internet have impacted the small and medium-sized printing companies as they are unable to scale up and deliver up-to-the-minute news or information to consumers (Zhao, Ouyang and Xu, 2017). Further, the internet has also negatively affected newspaper circulation figures as both daily and weekly papers cannot provide interactive features, which has led to a loss of revenue generation and profitability (Diehl and Karmasin, 2013).

1.2 AIMS AND OBJECTIVES OF THE RESEARCH

1.2.1 Research Aim

The aim of this research is to analyse the current market scenario of the printing industry of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia and the risks and challenges posed by the internet on the product mix of printing organizations, mainly because of the internet as a substitute. Furthermore, the study will also provide recommendations to improvise the current product mix strategies and the internet's lens of substitution, thereby creating a sustainable and viable product mix.

1.2.2 Research Objectives

- To evaluate the risks and challenges posed by internet and technology in printing organization
- To assess the current market situation and challenges faced by mid-sized printing companies in Saudi Arabia.
- To identify the current product mix used by organizations and assess the impact of internet substitution on the product mix
- To recommend a product marketing mix strategy for small-to-mid sized organizations to benefit from internet technologies and mitigate financial and consumer base losses.

1.2.3 Research Questions

According to the aims and objectives discussed above, the main research questions in this study are as follows:

1. How has the use of the internet impacted the printing industry in Saudi Arabia?
2. What recommendations can be made to small-to-medium sized printing company to help re-position its product mix to minimize the risks caused by internet substitution whilst leveraging on the opportunities it provides?

1.3 JUSTIFICATION FOR THE RESEARCH

1.3.1 Research Perspective and Intended Audiences

Due to the growth of the internet and changes in the technological paradigm, it has become difficult for the printing and paper publication industry to survive in the market (Dillman, 2011). According to AlSaadi (2012), the internet has impacted the daily lives of consumers to a great extent and their dependability on the internet has also increased in terms of searching

for information, reading newspapers, procuring online published material and so on. It has eventually reduced the performance of the traditional printing industry because consumers do not prefer printed newspapers, books, magazines, and other reading material (Meersman, 2004). Studies such as Gilaninia (2011) and Jadoon, et al. (2011) observed that in the fast pace of life, consumers do not have enough time to check published material, post invitation cards and messages to their friends and relatives. High costs and more time are other reasons to shift to digital media. Online published material is beneficial as it saves time and cost of consumers as they can use digital tools for their reading on the go their comfort and convenience (Batra, 2013). So, it is vital for small and medium sized printing firms to identify definite substitutes to resolve the problem. Thus, the intended audiences of this study are current academia and both SMEs and large multinational business organizations in the printing and paper publication industry.

1.3.2 Educational Significance of the Study

From an academic perspective, the main rationale of choosing the selected research problem is to contribute to the extensive range of available literature and disseminate a highly reliable and credible research on the printing industry and its correlation to the internet. It is also important to analyse the issue of sustainability for SMEs in the printing and paper publication industry and develop a set of potential substitutes for these firms to increase sales and profitability. While there is an extensive range of literature available on the internet's benefits and advantages for society and business, literature related to negative impacts on SMEs in the printing industry is limited. This study will help to fill this gap and provide a comprehensive discussion about the challenges and issues faced by the printing industry due to the internet and innovation of digital technology. Further, from existing research, it was also noted that there is no significant discussion about the substitution of the internet, which can provide relief to the

printing and publishing industry to deal with environmental challenges and difficulties posed by the internet. Here, the focus of this study is on SMEs. At the same time, this study also focuses on introducing a class of substitutions to be incorporated in the product mix of the printing industry, which has not been introduced in earlier studies and literature.

1.3.3 Practical Benefits in the Business Area

Without the deployment and utilisation of the internet and digital tools, it is not possible for businesses to sustain long-term growth and expansion in the international market. The world has transformed into a virtual world and consumers are highly interested to use internet technologies for reading, writing, send virtual invitations, create online documentations, etc. Due to this, SMEs are feeling the pinch as it has become challenging to make an adequate profit or ensure long-term survival, as technology eventually affected the product line of the firms and influences the buying behaviour of customers to switch from paper to digital media. It is also noteworthy that internet and digital information tools are significant for SMEs to reduce costs related to production, marketing, advertising, and developing long term relationship with the customers.

The Al-Fakhoor Printing Company is one of the SMEs in Saudi Arabia, which also faces the same issues and it has become imperative for the firm to identify the causes in a detailed manner and create a new product mix strategy. This will enable Al-Fakhoor to minimize the impact of the internet and maintain its profitability. In this regard, Al-Fakhoor serves as a case study for this research. Its background and significance to this study is discussed in the methodology chapter. Thus, the practical benefits of this study are to improve the product mix and develop substitutions of the internet to deal with the available difficulties due to the internet. This model will, therefore, be helpful for all SMEs in Saudi Arabia as well as in the overall global printing industry to identify substitutes of the internet to bolster the growth of the printing industry and

create a new marketing mix. Further, all the small and medium sized business firms will get practical benefits from this study to modify their current product mix, introduce a new substitution strategy based on the internet and ensure that the internet will not impact their profitability and revenue negatively.

1.3.4 Use of the Research to Improve Current Business Practices in the Printing and Publishing Industry

One significant rationale of this study to improve the current industry status quo and provide real life benefits of the internet to the SMEs in the printing and paper publication industry. The SMEs like Al-Fakhoor Printing Company and similarly, others can use this study to analyse the environmental changes and the impact of political and technological changes in the growth of the digital era. Further, the impact of technology on social preferences, lifestyle and digital cultural demographic environment and its effects on the growth of business, the proliferation of the internet and digital lifestyles are also analysed in this study. SMEs will be able to identify areas of improvement to survive in this competitive and innovative era and use the outcomes of this study to implement new strategic alternatives to maintain growth and diversify their business portfolios.

1.3.5 Interest in the Research Area

Innovative technological developments have changed the perspective of human life and provided new benefits to the individual to made life comfortable. Evolution of the internet is regarded as one of the biggest innovations of human society and has ushered in the era of globalisation. The internet has not only transformed the way of doing business, but also connected international markets, societies and communities around the world and influenced the living styles of individuals in a drastic manner. The internet has provided growth

opportunities to several business organizations and opened the doors to operate in the international market (Carr, 2010). Due to the internet, social networking, digital marketing, and online business models have influenced the buying behaviours of consumers and provided the opportunity of receiving global news and updates within a few seconds (Coyle, 2002). However, it is also interesting to identify the disadvantages that the internet has brought along with it for both society and businesses. The internet undoubtedly has caused significant disruptions to traditional business. The printing and paper publication industry is one such example, which has been severely impacted by the internet. As the internet and digital technology has changed the way of communication, it has reduced the popularity and consumption of newspapers, magazines, and at the same time, promoted virtual invitation cards, digital information, changed documentation processes in companies and increased the efficiency of businesses as a result of the switch from hard to soft copies (Dulis, 2012). So, employees and owners of SMEs face a critical situation to survive and compete with the internet. Consequently, this research problem is a means to make an effort to help SMEs to deal with the impact of the internet for the long-term survival of the printing industry.

1.4 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In order to identify the impact of the internet and to establish an effective outcome of the research, a suitable research process needs to be ascertained for the evaluation of the problem, its causalities and generate credible findings. An interpretivism research philosophy along with an inductive approach is has been used in this study for the selection of adequate research methods. The research strategy is a single case-study strategy, based on the Al-Fakhoor Printing Company, an SME in Saudi Arabia. Further, both qualitative and quantitative data collected methods were employed to collect views and ideas of scholars as well as perceptions

of those who have been affected from the printing industry due to the popularity of the internet. Qualitative research approaches are beneficial to find out the actual impact of the internet on the printing industry.

At the same time, semi-structured surveys and interviews with company personnel and consumers was also helpful to understand the way the internet has changed daily lives and the reasons for preferring the internet rather than print. These are primary data collection methods. The probability sampling strategy was used to select the sample size for the survey and interviews.

1.5 OUTLINE OF THE THESIS

Research structure refers to the sketch of the entire research, or the way in which the entire research shall be carried out. Research structure usually unfolds the phases that are to be included by the researcher in executing the research in an effective manner. In the case of this research, the researcher shall conduct the entire research based on the following framework.

Chapter 1 Introduction: This is one of the significant chapters of the study. Here the researcher presented his thoughts and the initial process of the research. This section provides comprehensive details about the complete research process, which will be followed to accomplish the study. It provides the introduction to the research topic by discussing the research background, justification of the research issue, significance of the research issue from the point of view of readers and businesses and the research problem. It is an important chapter to discuss the research aims and objectives along with the research questions and hypotheses. The main purpose of developing this introduction chapter is to develop the understanding of readers about needs of conducting this study on an issue or research problems and to develop their interest in the study.

Furthermore, this chapter is important to present the scope and significance of the study. A comprehensive discussion about the significance of the study in the current area, its related future trends, and information about the users of the study is given in this chapter. Further, relevant impacts of this study for business practices and regulations are also described.

Chapter 2 Literature Review: This chapter involves a systematic review of the existing literary discourse to develop a thorough understanding about the research issue. The researcher follows a critical approach to examine the available information in the context of the research issue. Various secondary sources, including journal articles, books, newspaper, websites, and other authentic online sources are used to make this section effective. In this chapter, a comprehensive overview about the impact of the internet on the printing industry of Saudi Arabia and its positive and negative impacts are provided. In addition, the current product mix of the selected case study company is discussed to identify the substitute of the internet for the future and essential growth of the printing industry. This chapter is also vital as it will elaborate a new product marketing mix strategy for the case study organisation to avoid the negative impact of the internet on the printing business and ensure its long-term success. The main purpose of developing this chapter is to provide a theoretical framework to the readers, to improve their understanding about the existing literature and gain an in-depth knowledge of the research issue from the views of different experts and scholars.

Chapter 3 Research Methodology: The third chapter is the methodology, which discusses a set of research methods and strategies to draw and collect valid and reliable data. It discusses the selection of a method over others with adequate justification. Conducting a study to solve a research problem requires comprehensive knowledge and information about the ways of choosing a research philosophy, approaches, and strategy. It also depends on the nature of the research problem, so that the researcher can select adequate methods to collect credible and

authentic data and information to answer the research questions. So, this chapter is developed with the goals to provide the rationale behind the selection of specific approaches, design, and methods of data collection over others, so that the authenticity of the data collection process can be established.

Chapter 4 Data Analysis and Findings: After the chapter on Research Methodology, the next one is significant to present the statistical results of the data collected through the survey and interview processes. In this chapter, results from the data analysis process are explained. The data is analysed by using statistical techniques such as SPSS analysis and the presentation of analysis of quantitative data is given in tabular forms.

Chapter 5 Discussion of Key Findings: This chapter discusses the analysis and interpretation of the collected data in a systematic manner to present the valid research outcomes. This is the main chapter of the study, where the discussion and findings of the study are presented in detail. This chapter informs the readers about the answers to the research questions and to what extent the research problem is valid and accepted as a major issue of social and behavioural science.

Chapter 6 Conclusion, Recommendations, Contribution and Summary: This is the last section of the study which will describe the conclusion, a set of recommendations and limitations that can affect the scope and reliability of the research outcomes. Further, the limitations discussed in this chapter are also important to understand the factors, which are uncontrollable and may affect the result to some extent. It also indicates that there is a future scope for further research on the same issue or research problems.

1.6 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS

Internet: It is defined as a global computer network, which offers a wide range of communication protocol and facilities. It uses dedicated routers and servers to connect different computers worldwide (Wilson III, 2005).

Printing: It can be defined as the method of producing, books, and magazines. Printing is to put different impressions such as words, images, and signs on paper or any material and create books, cards, and pamphlets (Li, 2013).

Printing industry: A global industry in which all the companies whether large, medium, or small works to print and publish books, magazines, newspaper, articles, documentation and so on (Beck, 2017).

Business Regulations: It can be explained as the laws and policies, which are created to manage the business process and control its activities. Business regulations are the laws that direct the business firm to operate its policies and processes in the global and local markets (Vogel, 2008).

Political Environment: The external environment, which integrates state and government policies and legal regulations as well as public and private stakeholders, which affect the business policies to a great extent and cannot be controlled by companies (Lamb, 2012).

Technology: Technology can be described as the application of scientific knowledge, which is used in real terms for innovations, mainly in different industries (Bello, Zeadally and Badra, 2017).

Digital Technology: The concept of digital technology is the digitalisation of the available scientific and engineering knowledge, which is used to generate and store data in digital form so that another user can employ it through signals (Henderson, Finger and Selwyn, 2017).

1.7 SCOPE OF THE RESEARCH

1.7.1 Current Area of the Research

As this study mainly focuses on the negative impacts of the growth of the internet and digital technologies on the printing and publication industry, it seeks to explore the substitutions of the internet for the industry, mainly for small and medium-sized enterprises (SME). In this era of globalization, the emergence of digital technology has reduced the printing and publishing industry's market share and relevance to some extent. The internet has made it feasible for consumers to communicate with each other within a few seconds beyond boundaries, which was earlier not possible through the medium of print. Thus, the scope and significance of this study are associated with the analysis of the internet as a major substitution of the printing industry. This study also provides the scope for SMEs to identify avenues and strategies to adopt, so that the internet can be used as an innovation to strengthen the product mix rather than a challenge for printing products.

1.7.2 Future Trends

The evolution of digital technology and the internet has drastically changed the eco-system of the printing industry. In the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, SMEs have been affected to a great extent due to the rapid advancement of digital information and communication tools. In the year of 2016, the printing industry of Saudi Arabia declared losses due to decrease in demand for printing and publishing material. The trend is regularly changing, and consumer attention is increasingly towards internet-enabled products and services, which has created a threat for the long-term survival of printing companies. It is really a crucial situation for the SMEs to survive in the printing industry for products such as printed invitation cards, as more and more

people prefer to send easily available digital cards at the click of a button; to the consumer it is both economical and time-saving (Broich, 2015).

Moreover, an uncertainty in the growth of the industry can be seen clearly. The large-scale business firms can survive the competition; however, SMEs have found it difficult to sustain without business from local consumers. This has also been compounded by a radical shift in consumer buying behaviour where the preference is to 'go online' rather than traditional means of shopping. The outlook of the printing industry of Saudi Arabia spells out struggle for SMEs. The market conditions are tough and challenging to cope along with the social, cultural, economic as well as technological changes.

Thus, the significance and scope of this study to understand the future trends is associated with the evaluation of the challenges and opportunities available for marketers to survive in the printing industry. In addition, the types of substitutes available in the printing industry to compete with digital technology and the internet and different alterations that need to be innovated for the future growth of the printing industry are also a part of this study. Therefore, this research has much significance for the printing and publishing industry to boost sales and rejuvenate the growth of printed material such as personal and business cards, magazines, and shore up the falling demand for newsprint.

1.8 USERS OF THE STUDY

This study is beneficial from both an academic as well as business points of view. As the research aim is to identify a substitution of the internet and manage its impact positively for the long-term and sustainable growth of the industry, mainly for SMEs, it is useful for students as a scholarly resource in their further research studies and projects related to the printing industry and its sustainable growth. Simultaneously, businesses are also another group of main users of this study, as it will be beneficial for them to effectively strategize to build and maintain

growth. The scope of this study is not only limited to identify the negative impact of the internet for SMEs in printing industry but also to create a new marketing mix solution as well as develop new substitutions for the internet and digital technologies.

So, all SMEs of Saudi Arabia, as well as in the global market, in the printing industry are the users of this study. Simultaneously, this study also provides reliable and credible information to future researchers and scholars to develop their literature review with the secondary data contained herein. Moreover, the readers of the study, who wish to make their career in the printing industry and produce innovations in paper printing methods can use this study as a guide to evaluate challenges and strategies.

1.9 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE RESEARCH

1.9.1 Benefits of Research in the Context of Globalization/ De-globalization

As the business and social world has become global due to evolution of the internet and digital technologies, it has created a high level of competition for businesses. Due to globalization, access to international markets have opened to multinational business organizations, and at the same time, has also created immense pressure on the local and small business firms to survive (Joseph, 2015). In the era of globalization, printing and publication companies are in a downslide. According to the data presented in news blog of graphic display world, 40 per cent of publishers reported that rather than promoting advertising and promotions in traditional print media such as newspapers and magazines, web advertising and e-mail promotion has taken precedence, which shows that globalization has had an adverse impact on the growth of printing industry (Gilman, 2016).

This research is beneficial within the globalization context to propose different ways and substitutes of digital technology for the printing and publication industry, so that SMEs can deal with the negative impacts of the internet and instead utilize its benefits for their long-term

and sustainable growth. Further, the internet as a tool of promotion, advertisement, communication and attracting the global consumer will be used as an opportunity for the business rather than reducing sales and profits.

Globalization has also introduced external environmental factors such as political, technological, social, and economic factors which affect growth. For example, this study is significant to understand the economical and societal changes and its impact on the industry growth. Nowadays, the social standard of consumers is increasing due to increases in income levels. Consumers organize different parties and events online on social networking sites which renders it effective as virtual invitation. The norm of elaborate printed cards and invitations are passé now and does not suit most status-conscious consumers. At the same time, from an economic perspective, using virtual cards are highly cost effective and a quick means of informing groups or networks. It saves times as well. So, this study is beneficial for readers to understand these issues and identify the substitute which will maintain low printing costs making it more viable for consumers by developing a new marketing mix to sustain profitability.

On the other hand, from the political and environmental points of view, this study also has scope for readers to learn how to save paper and protect the environment, how to use recyclable material and products for printing and minimize the harmful impact on the environment. Similarly, a major switch in organizations and society from hard to soft copy has been evaluated in this study, so that suitable suggestions can be presented to the readers and users.

1.9.2 Current Challenges in the Research Context

According Bello, Zeadally and Badra (2017), evolution of the internet has opened the doors of success for companies in the areas of personalization as well as managing competition in the global market. The internet and the evolution of digital technology has brought about

significant changes in the demographics and cultural environments in Saudi Arabia as well as globally, which have created challenges for the printing and publishing industry. At the time of conducting this research, several challenges and issues were faced by the researcher. For instance, it was difficult to get secondary data about SMEs over the internet. As these companies are very small and with very small or no budgets to operate on e-commerce platforms, the researcher had to collect data on a personal level by contacting the personnel of these companies. It proved to be a challenging and time-consuming task. Further, it was also challenging for the researcher to get basic data about the printing industry. The digital age has radically altered consumer behaviour and buying perceptions and has influenced consumers to opt for virtual and digital options over traditional print products, and therefore, this study is beneficial to influence the printing industry to urgently respond to the changing media landscape by using the different strategies proposed in this study.

1.9.3 Impact of Research on Business Practices, Decision-making and Regulations

This research also has an impact on the business practices and decision-making abilities of SMEs in terms of adopting new business practices and tactics. The pattern of declining revenues of printing companies is evaluated in this study, so that different business practices can be proposed to identify loopholes and understand the various improvement areas which can be leveraged so that companies can become more successful and expand their printing business. Moreover, this study affects the decision-making abilities of marketers and helps them to deal in the digital era and sell a traditional product successfully with innovative features. By using this study, printing companies can find a new approach of decision-making in which the focus will be on innovation and increased concern for environmental and social responsibility rather than increasing profits. Small to medium (SME) sized printing business

could drive their profitability by transitioning their business towards a digital transformation. The conceptual framework provided at the end of the literature review gives a way of doing so.

1.10 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

This study is conducted by following all the precautions to maintain the reliability and creditability, but there are several human errors and complexities, which created certain limitations. The main points described in this study are related to the internet and its impact on printing industry and a direct relationship has been established in both positive and negative ways. It has become challenging to explore the issues that the internet has raised for the printing industry, mainly for small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs). However, in this study, analysing the substitution of internet for printing products and proposing different recommendations to improve the proposed product mix has become difficult. A subjective parameter has been followed at several places so that the aims and objectives can be achieved.

Further, the generalisation of explaining this relationship and collecting data and information without any bias is a major limitation of this study. As the study is based on survey and interview methods, all the participants have different views and perceptions on the same issue and their concerns about the printing industry and the internet are also different. Thus, generalisation in the presentation of findings may affect the credibility of the study. Along with this, producing a large study with minimal errors is a challenge and managing the timeline and budget is also a limitation for the collection of data and its subsequent analysis.

1.11 KEY ASSUMPTIONS

To broadly define a problem, it is imperative to follow some assumptions, so that the relevant data and information can be collected without any restrictions. It is observed from the studies of Simsim (2011) and Smithers Pira (2014) and the data from Saudi Print & Pack (2017) that due to the internet, the demand for printing products like, books, newspaper, business cards, etc. is reducing. So, the key assumptions of the study are that the internet has negative impacts on the growth of SMEs with respect to communication. Further, consumers in the Middle East countries such as the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia prefer to read online content and connect on social media and share virtual information (Stokes, Wilson and Wilson, 2010). The internet has ubiquitously increased the trend of using virtual information and programs rather than printed material, which has created obstacles and challenges for the printing and publishing industry. In practical social and business life, people are interested to share information quickly such as introductions or opinions of products or services over the internet, contact with each other on the internet, communicate via digital media, and share invitations through messaging platforms such as WhatsApp saves time as well as cost of people (Simsim, 2011).

So, it is also assumed in the study that SMEs can benefit from a substitution of the internet by creating a new marketing mix and focusing on new ways of printing rather than following a traditional trend. One other assumption is that the printing and paper publishing industry should expand their product line from paper to 3D printing to use the advantages of the internet to enhance their abilities to deal with challenges. Further, it is also assumed that printing for the packaging industry is high in demand, irrespective of traditional or e-commerce businesses, as product delivery requires printed information and labelling on the packaging material (Gilaninia, 2011). The final assumption is that use of both qualitative and quantitative research design helps the researcher to gather maximum data and help to explore the views of

participants, who are knowledgeable about the internet and its impact on different business areas and industries. The instruments used for the data collection process is valid and reliable and represents all the desired variables to get relevant and useful information.

1.12 CONCLUSION

This chapter of the research study is highly important to understand the research background, the research problem, and its importance to the current business scenario. The objectives presented in the chapter provide a detailed explanation about the research problem to readers, with respect to the risks and challenge caused in such organisations, to assess the current market situation and challenges faced by the mid-sized printing industry in Saudi Arabia, to identify the current product mix used by organisations and the impact of internet substitution on the product mix, to recommend a product marketing mix strategy for the mid-sized organisations so as to minimize the risks caused by the internet substitution. This chapter is also important to explore the problem and define the hypotheses to evaluate the impact of the internet and identify some substitute to reduce its impact and promote the growth of the industry. The internet has changed the way of doing business and strategies and enabled businesses to compete in the global market, however, it has also created challenges for the small and medium-sized firms to compete with large multinational companies. The internet has facilitated consumers to read news online, send messages through social networking sites and reduced the use of paper. Due to the internet, the SMEs in the printing and publishing industries are facing the challenges of attracting and retaining customers to use printing products. A comprehensive discussion about the research background, justification and outline of the chapters are important to develop the interest of readers in further chapters.

2 CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

Internet has proved to be a disruptive agent in almost every industry in today's highly advanced age of information and communication. From a historical perspective, "printing press" in itself could be regarded as the first technological advancement of the industrial revolution which modernised mass communication in the industrial age. Other technological advancements included television and radio broadcasting which reached masses. It can be argued that the "internet" has yet again revolutionised how people interact and communicate. Whilst the impact of the internet has largely been positive in most industries. Industries such as banking, finance, healthcare, education, etc. have successfully managed to leverage the speed and easy accessibility afforded by the internet into their business models. However, like any disruptive agent, the internet has also adversely impacted several other industries. The printing and publishing industry are amongst one of the most adversely affected industries by the rise of the internet. Traditionally profitable product lines in the printing and publishing industry such as printed newspaper, magazines and printed marketing material have been rendered near obsolete due to internet (Burglund et al., 2002). At the same time, internet does offer an opportunity for the printing and publishing industry to diversify its product offerings and re-design business models. The main aim of this research is to investigate the impact of the internet in the particular context of the Saudi printing and publishing industry.

This section of the research comprises of an assessment of the literary discourse concerned with technological advancements in the printing and publishing industry. The review of the literature is done from a global perspective to gain a wider understanding of technologically fuelled phenomenon in the printing industry. Several theoretical frameworks are examined to understand how disruption alters the existing landscape in any industry. This is particularly

relevant as internet has effectively disrupted the printing industry globally. While larger players are able to withstand disruptions to some extent, it is the small and medium sized enterprises which are most severely impacted (Bolkesjo et al., 2003). Therefore, an understanding of disruption management is a pivotal part of this section.

Technological advancements fuelled by the internet has also opened a host of opportunities for printing firms. These opportunities include greater accessibility to geographically distant markets; potential to add on services centred on mass customization; potential to innovate by rethinking the business model; better and effective management of internal processes; and so forth. The internet also presents challenges for the printing industry which relates to being substituted by online based platforms of digital print.

In this context, this section of the research project deals with the theoretical and conceptual framework related to the assessment of the impact of internet on printing industry in the case of Saudi Arabia. This chapter aims to provide in-depth conceptualize information concerned with the research aim.

As a part of this, the first section of the chapter provides information about the global printing industry, printing industry in the Middle East and specifically in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. Further. In the next section, technology, its growth, internet evolution and disruptive internet along with the impact of internet on the printing industry is elaborated. The impact of the use of internet on printing industry, its challenges and key benefits are significant to explore the research aim and objectives. In the next section of the chapter current product mix of the industry is identified which are substituted by the internet for the industry. Apart from this, the chapter includes the discussion related to the development of product mix strategies for Al-Fakhoor Printing Company to minimize the risk of internet substitution and ensuring long term sustainability in the industry.

In the final segment of this chapter, a conceptual framework is proposed based on the synthesis of the existing literature. The conceptual framework is derived by identifying the most significant variables which can aid Saudi small-to-mid sized printing industries to transform their business. This transformation is in response to challenges and opportunities presented by the internet. Thereby, offering viable solutions to survive in the rapidly evolving printing and publishing industry.

2.2 THEME 1: INTERNET SUBSTITUTION

In the recent years there has been a trend of declining use of paper-based print products such as Newspapers, Magazines, and Books, etc. Empirical studies have found this trend to be fuelled by the rise in the adoption of the electronic based media which are powered by the internet (Hetemaki 2008). In this section we will discuss the empirical evidence and discussions from previous studies which attempted to model the future usage of paper-based products in the new age of information and communication technologies powered by the internet. The motive behind doing so is to gain an understanding of the degree of substitution of paper based printed products with digital media. The internet in combination with information and communication technologies have provided the masses with an electronic substitute of paper based printed materials. This aberration from the printed material to the electronic platforms can be explained through the theory of product substitution. Essentially, whenever a new product or service is introduced into the market, its impact on the existing product or service in the market can only manifest in two ways: the new product could either drive down the demand of the existing product if it provides superior utility to the users. Or, the new product could enhance the demand for the existing product if it's complimentary in nature to the existing product and requires the use of existing product alongside its own use (Li et al. 2006). To illustrate, in the context of the paper based printed products experts

anticipated that a rise in the demand with the adoption of personal printers at the turn of the previous century (Cody, 1999). Whilst, at the same time it was predicted with the increased integration of electronic media into business the demand for newspapers (Cody, 1999).

2.2.1 Impact of the Internet on Printing

The adoption of the internet in the western world and OECD gained pace throughout the 1990s. It is interesting to note that during this period the demand for newspaper began to level off. Throughout the following decade the demand for newspapers witnessed a steady decline across the United States (McCarthy 2010). The trends observed in the OECD countries somewhat followed a similar trajectory. The demand for newspaper started to stagnate in the early 2000s in the OECD countries with the sharp decline in the later 2000s. Studies estimate this decline to over 20 per cent in the OECD countries from 2007 to 2011 (McCarthy 2010). From the above figures and timelines, a stark finding emerges. During the 1990s and 2000s internet adoption witnessed its largest every growth across the globe. Empirical evidence suggests internet adoption within the populations of the developed world rose to nearly 75 per cent of the total population (McCarthy 2010). The figure below demonstrates this phenomenon of rising internet adoption and declining demands for paper based printed material from 1970s to 2013 (Latta et al, 2016).

Figure 1: “Regional trends in newsprint consumption, P&W paper consumption, and Internet adoption per hundred people from 1970 through 2013 (Latta et al, 2016)”.

It is interesting to note that the decline in paper based printed products declined throughout the United States and OECD countries throughout 1990s and 2000s. Yet, this trend is not seen to a similar extent in other parts of the world. For instance, Asian countries, African and Middle Eastern regions witnessed an increase in the consumption of paper based printed products throughout the 2000s (Latta et al, 2016). It is also reported than only in later part of the 2010s a fall in demand for paper based printed products began to show (Latta et al, 2016). Other regions including Eastern Europe witnessed a decline in newspaper consumption to over 10 per cent from 2007 to 2011. However, the demand of other paper based printed products seemed constant (Latta et al, 2016). It can be argued that the above-mentioned regions witnessed a somewhat stunted effect in terms of decline in demand for newspaper and other paper based printed products primarily due to later adoption of internet. Empirical

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evidence lends support the above argument, since internet adoption rates in non-OECD countries was close to only a quarter of their populations (Latta et al, 2016).

2.2.1.1 Prior Studies to Model Paper Based Products Demand

Since the industrial revolution, economists have endeavored to forecast the demand for paper based printed products using statistical techniques. Arguably, the work of Buongionara (1978) could be deemed as the first to do so on a global scale. However, Zhang & Buongionara (1997) is widely regarded as one of the first attempts to investigate the impact of electronic media on the demand for paper-based products. In their study, Zhang & Buongionara examined whether the mass adoption of electronic media such as broadcasting (TV & Radio) has adversely impacted demanded for paper-based products of print, primarily newspapers and magazines. The findings revealed broadcast media did not have any statistically significant impact on the demand for paper-based print products during the period 1960-1991 (Latta et al, 2016). Later researchers attempted to explain the structural breaks in consumption for paper based printed products witnessed during 1990s and 2000s, by attributing it to the adoption of information technologies (Hetemäki and Obersteiner 2001; , Hetemäki 2005, 2008, Soirinsuo and Hetemäki 2008, Szabó et al. 2009). However, it should be noted that neither of these studies attempted to examine explicit measures of internet adoption. Study by Huiala (2011) presented a statistical model of paper based printed product' demand including newspaper, magazines and stationary paper. The study benefitted from using nationwide data from 1990-2007. However, a significant drawback of the study relates to the exclusion of “price” as an independent variable whilst estimating demand for paper based printed products. Price is arguable one of the most significant factors in any kind of demand-based forecasting. Nevertheless, Huiala (2011) included variables such as “adoption rate for information & communication technologies” in her study. The findings of

her study revealed newspaper consumption to be strongly negatively correlated with adoption of internet. Furthermore, she revealed mobile phones & computers to be positively correlated with paper-based magazine consumption.

Latta et al (2016) in their study found internet adoption has drastically contributed to decline in newspaper consumption throughout the world. The study revealed geographical patterns of decline in newspaper and other paper based printed products. According to the findings the largest decline in newspaper consumption was seen in the United States. It was predicted, in the absence of internet the consumption of newspaper would have grown by a factor of four instead of declining (Latta et al, 2016). In other regions such as Asia and OECD region newspaper consumption would have increased by 50 per cent and 100 per cent respectively (Latta et al, 2016). The study also revealed consumption of other paper based printed products in the absence of internet would have increased around 100 per cent and 40 per cent in the United States and OECD regions, respectively (Latta et al, 2016).

Latta et al (2016) is a pivotal study in the context of understanding how global demand for the newspaper and other paper printed products were affected by the rise of the internet. The study concluded internet adoption has resulted into a “substitution affect” for the paper printed products. In a nutshell, greater internet adoption has led to a global decline in the demand for paper based printed products. This decline is seen to be more pronounced in some regions of the world as compared to others. For instance, United States and OECD countries have seen the sharpest internet fueled decline in the demand for paper-based print products (Latta et al, 2016). It can be argued that stronger demand decline trends for paper based printed products in certain regions of the world in comparison to others could be attributed to better internet connectivity in developed regions of the world such as United States and OECD nations. Better internet connectivity would facilitate increased adoption of digital

media, thereby effectively substituting printed media. However, it is also interesting to note that demand for other paper based printed products is only seen to be severely affected in the United States and not as much in other regions such as Asia (Latta et al, 2016). The author also highlights that experts believed at the turn of the previous century that internet adoption would lead to a greater demand for paper printed products such as Magazines, journals, and books. However, there is little to no empirical evidence to support this notion (Latta et al, 2016).

The effect of income on demand for paper-based print products is shown to differ with internet with internet adoption (Latta et al, 2016). To illustrate, as internet use increases the demand for paper based printed products become less and less responsive to the individual's level of income. In the absence of internet use, level of income is seemed to be a strong indicator of demand for paper based printed products. This is a stark finding which lends support to the idea of the prevalence of an internet fueled substitution effect in the global printing industry.

Historically, there have been numerous outlook studies which have attempted to forecast the demand for paper based printed products (Hurmekoski & Hetemäki 2013). In the age of the internet, Haynes et al (1995) were the first to note the decline in paper-based mediums of advertising as a direct result of advertising being done online. Other studies such as Zhu et al, (1998) predicted a steady increase in the consumption of newspapers and other paper based printed products. Later, empirical evidence proved the results of these studies to be incorrect. Perhaps, a major flaw of the study related to not considering the impact of the internet in the printing industry. The report by Haynes (2003) predicted a declining trend in newspaper consumption but an upward trend in consumption of other paper based printed products. Haynes (2003) attributed the declining trend in newspaper consumption to continued gradual

substitution by gradual substitution by digital media for news broadcasting and advertising purposes.

Figure 2: “Forecasts of US newsprint and P&W paper consumption compared with actual and fitted estimates (Latta et al. 2016)”.

Zhang (1995) in his study found the demand for print based products to be complementary to digital media. Essentially, the study based on an econometric model asserted falling prices of computers would signal for an increase in the demand for print based products. Future studies disproved this finding. For instance, Latta et al (2016) showed that lowering cost of technology is actually directly related to the falling demand for print based products. Other sources such as the 2010 Global Robotics Process Automation report by Buongiorno et al. (2012) lend support to Letta et al’s (2016) findings.

From the synthesis of the literature it becomes evident that previous attempts to forecast the demand for paper based printed products did not consider all influencing factors. While, later

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studies did include some control to various degrees to factor in the influence from digital media, there were only few studies which explicitly tried to study the impact of the internet on demand for paper based printed products (Latta et al, 2016). Latta et al (2016) recommended the use of per capita internet use and interaction of internet use with the GDP to be a critical variable for forecasting printed products demand. Further insights relates to the significance of smaller and more domestic studies to better understand the specific intricacies of how internet has influenced the demand for print based products. Study by Goldfarb and Prince (2008) presents a good example of a smaller study which *examined “how Internet adoption affects substitution among goods, including paper products, and identify the important determinants of these choices.”* (Latta et al, 2016).

2.2.2 Theory of Disruptive Innovation & Implications for the Printing Industry

Disruption as a phenomenon is used to describe scenarios where a new entrant or a smaller market player can give significant competition to an already established, usually larger market player (Batra, 2013). The phenomenon manifests in stages. Initially, the established player will be predisposed to focus on innovation targeted towards their most demanding and profitable segment. This creates a gap where the needs of other not as profitable segments of customers are overlooked by the established player. Usually, the product offering of the established player exceeds the needs and expectations of the sub-standard profitable segments. New entrants or smaller players begin the disruption phenomenon by targeting these overlooked segments. They deliver products and services specially targeted to the needs and expectations of these overlooked segments. Usually, the pricing of disrupter’s products and services are significantly lower as compared to established players. In this the prospective disrupter gains foot holding in the industry. At this stage the established player tends not to respond to vigorously, as they are chasing higher profitability. Eventually, the

disrupter starts moving up market, providing the established player's highly profitable segment of customers with competitive products and services. The disrupter must ensure they preserve their capabilities which drove their initial success with lower profitable segments of customers. Disruption as a phenomenon manifests when the established player's highly profitable segment starts churning in favour of the disrupter. The disruptive innovation model given below provides a graphical representation of the disruption phenomenon.

Figure 3: The Disruptive Innovation Model (Source: Christensen et al 2015)

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2.2.2.1 Origins of disruption in the market

Disruption begins usually in the low foothills of an established market where the needs of certain segments are overlooked. Or, it occurs in a new-market foothold (Christensen et al, 2015). To put it simply, the disrupter can create a market where none existed. In the specific context of the printing industry, disruption happened in the early days of the photocopying technology (Christensen et al, 2015). The established player in the market used to be Xerox Inc., providing high priced photocopying solutions to large corporates. However, segments overlooked by Xerox Inc., included small to mid-sized businesses. Disruption occurred after the arrival of low priced personal printers by several new entrants to the small and mid-sized businesses. Hence, a whole new market was created for low priced personal printers.

Eventually, these new entrants were able to cater to the large corporates which used to be the domain of Xerox Inc.

2.2.2.2 Innovation & Disruption

Innovation refers to “creation” in response to a demand or a challenge. There is a clear distinction offered by disruption theory between two types of innovation, i.e. – disruptive vs. sustaining innovation. Sustaining innovation refers to improvement of a product or service to altering consumer demand, i.e. – demand centric. It entails adding of new features to the product/service which enable to business to drive sales. Apple Inc. with latest features added to every successive generation of iPhones is a classic example of sustaining innovation.

Disruptive innovation usually occurs in response to a challenge. Typically, the good and services resulting from disruptive innovation are of primitive or inferior quality but offered at low prices. There is tremendous scope of improvement through experience. Disruptive innovation is generally applied for low segment markets with a poorly defined consumer base. Typically, the mainstream consumers start adopting the good/service after the quality

has crossed a certain threshold. Disruptive innovation has tremendous potential to driving down market prices.

2.2.2.3 Useful Insights Surrounding Disruption

Christensen et al (2015) valuable lessons on disruptive innovation which could be relevant for the Saudi printing industry. These insights are given below:

- **Disruption is a process:** Christensen et al (2015) argue that almost every innovation started out as a small-scale experiment. The characteristics which enable disruption is the agility of the business model which fosters that small-scale experiment into innovation. Disrupters often focus on building the right business model which is conducive to innovation. The process of disruption could take a significant amount of time and during this time the established player may apply several forms of creative defence tactics. Nevertheless, it is the agility of the disrupter's business model which dictates their ultimate success.
- **Disruptive business models are often different from established players:** Disrupters tend to build business models which is designed to exploit the gaps in the market which established player overlook. This requires building unique business models.
- **Disruptive innovations don't guarantee success:** Simply put, success isn't an indicator of disruptive innovation and vice versa. Disruption within industry varies and there isn't a one size fit all model for a specific industry. The disruptive innovation path chosen by the disruptor should complement their existing capabilities

and the opportunities they are trying to exploit. Theory of disruptive innovation dictates the path to disruption should be tactfully chosen which avoids direct competition with the established player. Often the established player will have larger resources and better capabilities (Othman & Shoib 2016).

2.2.2.4 Key Insights from a Disruptive Innovation Perspective

Any new product is usually not inherently sustaining or disruptive. During innovation, the disruption theory offers the choice to the business whether to follow a sustainable or a disruptive approach to innovation.

Theory of disruption argues that when a new or smaller player will attempt to compete with the established player directly by offering similar level of services to the established player's core consumer segment one of two possibilities are most likely to occur. Either the established player will beat the new or smaller player through accelerating their innovation or through a combination of tactics such as price war (Philippe, 2017). If the new/smaller player is successful in withholding then, it may get acquired by any other larger established player. Historical trends lend support this argument (Latif 2016). Numerous cases of stand-alone players which have either succumbed or were absorbed by a larger player exist (Rostom 2015).

Theory of disruption also reveals that established player are more involved in sustaining innovation instead of disruptive innovation. This is due to the reason, it makes more sense for larger businesses with a developed consumer base to try and anticipate the needs of their consumers (Ali, 2009). However, empirical evidence also points out that there is a real danger for these larger businesses to become institutionalized in their innovation process (El-Erin 2017). This relates to forming an organizational culture of only following sustainable

innovation. This puts the established player at a disadvantage where they overlook the benefits of disruptive innovation.

The above insights help in illustrating why established players tend to ignore new/small entrants following the path of disruptive innovation. Or perhaps, why their initial responses to the disrupter are ineffective.

So far, it has become evident that there is plenty scope for growth which the new/small player could enjoy as a disrupter within the foothills of the market. This begs the question - why new/small players would want to move upwards in the market and challenge the disrupter head on? The answer to this is to chase higher profitability which the established players reap (Nalband et al 2016). To illustrate, the foothills of any market is usually populated by a considerable number of new entrants offering similar products/services at similar prices to the segments overlooked by the established player. The established players provide de facto price for the good/service in the industry. The growth of the new smaller entrants in the foothills of the market is driven by the difference between their price and de facto price set by the established player (Burton 2016). This phenomenon does not always last. As the established player cede the foothills of the market, they take away the de-facto price with them. This leads to a situation of intense competition between the numerous new entrants still located in the foothills. Since now the price is dictated by market forces the new entrants are pitted against each other for driving their profitability. Competing with other new entrants becomes challenging if the quality of products is similar, which usually is the case. Therefore, to avoid this challenging environment, the only option for new entrants is to move upwards in the market. Hence, true disrupters will always strive to better their service and move up market where they can once again drive their growth via higher profitability.

2.2.2.5 Transformational changes

Incorporation of technology into business has had a tremendous impact on the printing industry. Brokaw & Reed (2010) note with the rise of technology printing process was integrated as an in-house function for most businesses. Examples of this could include Libraries, offices, data processing centres and so on. These transformational changes on how printing jobs are carried out in the wake of the technological revolution has impact printing industry. Strokes et al (2010) state changes in trends and customers' personal schedule also become the reason of customer's movement from print magazines or books to online books and magazines. It affected printing industry by posing pressure to provide quick, accurate and reliable information to customers.

Competing views highlight a dichotomous discourse on the structural transformations within the printing industry caused by technology. On one hand, authors view increased integration of technology into business and personal matters to be have had a corrosive impact on the significance of printing industry (Dillman 2011). Whilst on the other hand, experts believe transformational changes caused due to technology could afford the printing industry with an opportunity to transform itself and offer its customer with greater value through enhancing product offerings (Carr 2010). Carr (2010) discussed that internet or digital technology has undeniable huge impact on the print industry. Internet has forced the publishers to review their brand image and expand into the digital era. The best example of this digital expansion is the digital version of newspapers online and on mobile phone applications. Dillman (2011) supported views of Carr (2010) by stating that internet is considered as one of the most important factors, which influence demand of printing products. High and rapid use of internet shopping & reading and rapid decline in high street retail shops reduced demand of printed books, magazines, and any other products of printing firms. Therefore, through the discussion

of authors, it is viewed that internet impacted demand and existence of printing firms in the industry.

2.2.3 Marketing Mix and Its Importance for Printing Firms

In this section a brief introduction to marketing mix framework is provided with a discussion of each components of the marketing mix. Following this, a discussion about the significance of the marketing mix in the specific context of the printing business is given.

2.2.3.1 Marketing Mix Framework

The marketing mix is a foundational framework in the marketing domain. Marketing mix as a term was first coined by Neil Bordon in 1953, build on the seminal works of James Culliton. The key idea behind marketing mix as a framework is to encapsulate each and every idea or plan which is will be used to device a comprehensive marketing strategy. Marketing mix has important implications for various aspects of marketing such as promotion of service or product, pricing strategy, choosing a marketplace, and people within the business (Naik, Raman & Winer 2005). Essentially, the key aim of the marketing mix is to enable the product or service to gain a foot holding into the market which already hosts a range of similar products or services.

As noted above, marketing mix has important implications for four main key marketing decisions. These are: product, price, promotion, and place. Famously, these are known as the 4Ps of the marketing mix (Gronroos 1997). It should be noted that marketing decisions for products are different from marketing decisions for services. To illustrate, marketing decisions for products require 4Ps as mentioned above. However, in the case of services the framework is extended to incorporate additional marketing decisions relating to people, processes, and physical evidence (Booms & Bitner, 1981). The reason for this extension specifically for the services is linked with services being intangible and therefore, requires additional components.

From a marketing perspective, products as an offering is different from service as an offering. Therefore, the classic 4Ps structure of marketing mix strategy is not enough for the service sector. So, the model extended through incorporating 3 more factors. Occasionally one more element is added: performance and it refers to the 8 Ps mix.

Figure 4 Marketing Mix Elements (Source: Gilaninia, 2011)

The following given are the elements of the marketing mix for service marketing. The first four are the core and earlier, while the next four are extended and newly added elements (Kotler and Armstrong, 2015).

Product

Product refers to the actual offering of the business to its prospect customers. This is a crucial component of the marketing mix and development of the product must incorporate consultation with the marketing department. Typically, the products are to be developed with the features of the rival product features in purview. Arguably, this is the most important decision of the marketing decision (Henry 2014). Typically, the products must be at the same level or above the quality of rival product (Naik, Raman and Winer, 2005). Likelihood of the entire marketing

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campaign to fail is shown to be significantly higher in cases where the quality of the products is found to be inferior to the rival's product.

Price

Price of the product or service is linked with the quality of the products. Studies have shown that price is also shown to be linked to customer loyalty (Naik, Raman, and Winer, 2005). As in some cases customers associate higher price of the goods or services to better quality and vice versa. Pricing decisions in the service industry are known to be linked with actual service consumption, service awareness and service acknowledgment. To illustrate, service as an offering is intangible in nature. However, in cases where consumer has greater service awareness; consumers consume the service on a regular basis; and acknowledge the significance of the service it becomes much easier to price the service appropriately based on the above-mentioned factors.

Place

Place as a marketing decision refers to selecting the actual location to set up shop or business. Experts note close proximity to place of business or shop is a strong factor in the consumer purchasing decision (Baltes, 2016). This is to say less distance to the customers increases the likelihood of a sale. In the modern era of e-commerce online marketplace has come out ahead of the actual physical space of business.

Promotion

It is an essential marketing activity that creates awareness among the potential customers and motivates them to purchase the product or service. As a part of a brand recognition campaign, it further establishes the proxy to evaluate quality of the service based by the market. There are many ways that a marketing representative can apply as promotional tools as per the size, type,

and requirement of the market. The most often used tools include the social media platform, internet advertisement, special events, out of the store endorsement along with in-store merchandising. For example, digital signage, plastic dump bins and Custom Boxes Now.

People

People as a factor in marketing decision is most significant in the case of service as the offering. The factor people refer to the staff or the service providers. To render the given services the service provider must ensure its staff understands all aspects of the service. Proper training and education of the staff is required to achieve the above objective. The companies must pay special attention to their human resources and provide them intense training about dealing with the client of all types and handling the contingencies (Naik, Raman, and Winer, 2005).

Processes

Processes as a factor in marketing decision becomes is a critical factor for both product and service as the offering. It relates to developing the right processes to ensure effective and efficient delivery of the desired level of product or service to the end user. In the specific context of service as the offering, owing to its intangible nature the business is required to select a right procedure to ensure that the standards may meet successfully. Process mapping can be very helpful here and provides a right path to meet the target segment (Hultén, Viström and Mejtoft, 2009).

Physical Evidence

Physical evidence is directly concerned with consumer's satisfaction of the service. Intangible nature of the services requires the consumer to judge from their own experience and perception of the service. Service provider must ensure physical evidence of consumer satisfaction is derived in some form through feedback from the consumer of the service. Additionally, service

provider must ensure they add physical features to their service which could be rated by the consumer. Examples of this could include asking consumers to give ratings on a scale of one to five stars for the service rendered to the consumer (Luca and Suggs, 2010).

Productivity and quality:

Productivity & quality are the most recent additions to the marketing mix framework. Essentially, they relate to ensuring the level of productivity and quality of the service rendered is above a certain threshold as set by the service provider. In this regard productivity and quality are closely connected to “processes” decision. In the functioning of an integrated service management, productivity improvement is not just a requirement, but an absolute condition for success. At the same time, ensuring the delivery of the customer defined quality is the value that makes the services unique from the other providers (Kotler and Armstrong, 2015).

2.2.3.2 Benefits of marketing mix for printing firms

Implementing the marketing mix models enables the business to make informed decisions about the marketing strategy which ultimately feeds into the competitive strategy. Below a discussion about the significance of the marketing mix in the specific context of the printing business is given.

A valuable assistance for resource allocation

Decisions about optimal resource allocation are pivotal in the printing industry. Printing businesses offer multiple products and services. Therefore, for printing businesses to maximize productivity and correspondingly revenue the marketing mix framework could be deemed highly effective for resource allocation. Through the application of the marketing mix framework, it becomes easier to arrange resources in a proportionate way to maximize

productivity, deliver customer satisfaction and maximize the profits (Naik, Raman, and Winer, 2005).

Enhance differentiation

Collectively all the decisions made under the marketing mix framework could enable printing companies to differentiate themselves in several aspects including product offering, pricing, and promotion strategy, offering specialised services and customer assistance. All the components of the marketing mix model could help the printing firm to stand out from the competition. Enhanced differentiation leads to unique brand equity. While the competitors are strong and stable enough, the company certainly launches the more impressive marketing campaigns using the components of the marketing mix in the most efficient manner (Luca and Suggs, 2010).

Assists in being dynamic

Marketing mix framework could enable printing firms to become agile and resilient. The knowledge of different business and marketing elements that can affect the client satisfaction, productivity and the profitability of a company make it ready to deal the possible risks or disasters. Such a company can better handle the recession or poor business environment. Marketing department must have the dynamic approach to respond any unfavourable circumstances. while the marketing mix analysis is all about product, process, promotion, people and all the other P's and their role in a success of a business, with the smart understanding of these, a company can easily pass through the rough conditions and respond with a better agility (Kotler and Armstrong, 2015).

Finally, the Marketing Mix Model can be important and beneficial to a printing company or any other business organization in many ways.

2.2.3.3 Impact of internet on marketing of printing firms

Gilaninia (2011) notes the changing landscape of the printing industry driven by technological changes. Internet led platforms have altered the market dynamics, marketing strategies, operational functionality within the printing industry. The use and popularity of the Internet have posed the greatest impact over the entire marketing practice of printing companies around the globe. This influence can be understood through the main components of the marketing mix under the following points:

Impact of Internet on Product strategy

Baltes (2016) highlights the key changes to the product strategy due to the increased adoption of the internet in the global printing industry. He notes an aberration from printed to digital platforms in the printing industry. This aberration relates to developing digital printing products and services. Mass customization has become the single greatest trend in the global printing industry which is achieved through internet powered technology. Internet has presented opportunities for product-based innovation for the printing industry. Globally printers are adding specialised services and products to their existing portfolio. These include mass customized printing, 3D printing, Web-to Print, and interactive print services. These innovative products and services are discussed in greater detail in the later sections.

Impact of Internet on Price Strategy

Internet has caused a decline in the prices of products and services. This decline could be explained in the following way: Internet facilitates the customers to get wide information about the price and quality and they can easily compare the cost of a service with rivals' or substitutes. It is mentioned by Hultén, Viström and Mejtoft (2009) that as a clientele effect, this facility takes the competition to a fiercer level. With the use of internet in various stages of pre-press

process, production, post-press process and marketing as well, certainly reduces the time and efforts, improves the production and service quality, and ultimately improves the profitability of the company.

Because of changing technology, a new term commoditization has come into existence as the customers are being provided the packages of new products and services together at a lower price (based on the high-volume low value approach). Online payments have made the cashless and quick payments very convenient for all the concerning parties (company, clients, suppliers, etc.). Again, there is a room for price reduction. But, due to wide use of the internet, it is much difficult for the companies offering the discriminatory pricing. Now, they cannot charge different prices to the different group of customers as the level of awareness has been increased tremendously (Kotler and Armstrong, 2015).

Impact of Internet of Place Strategy

Internet has had the most drastic impact on the place strategy within the marketing mix. Prior to the internet printing businesses were constrained by geographical proximity. Business has no geographical limits as the internet allows spreading the business and marketing activities globally. Even smaller players are also getting the courage to enter in the new market and compete with the big market players (Luca and Suggs, 2010). Present day marketing is more likely the direct marketing. With the support of powerful database, it is now much easier to identify the target market segment and offer them the products and services as per their requirements. The services also can be modified as per profitability targeted approach. The critics argue that the internet is not more than just a new channel of marketing that adds on the already existed means of marketing along with warehouses, direct mails, retail outlets, etc.

Impact of Internet on Promotion Strategy

Rise of social media platforms and e-commerce has drastically altered the promotional practices within marketing. In the present times promotions are ever so more targeted, aggressive, and direct. According to Baltes (2016) each sphere of promotion: public relation, advertising, direct marketing, personalization, interactivity, and others are causing the fundamental changes to the marketing practices used in pre-internet era. The new age promotion ideas are more consumer focused, practical, affordable, and put big impact over the buying behaviour of the customers. Social media is a popular platform to make the audiences aware of a company's offerings and all the other concerned information.

2.2.4 Challenges of Internet for the Printing organizations in the Saudi Arabia

Internet has proved to be a global disruptor in the printing industry. Middle Eastern printing industry, particularly the Saudi printing industry is not an exception to the host of challenges posed by the internet. Internet, especially the digitalization of the printing process is the biggest challenge in the way of existing and traditional printing companies. The demands of clients in the terms of product versatility, quality of output, time and methods of delivery, payments and many other things are completely influenced by digitization. The multinational printing companies that are investing in the Gulf region are enriched with the high-tech technical know-how and the skilled staff to meet with the challenges and opportunities in this segments, it is a crucial for local Saudi printing industry to evaluate the ongoing scenario and take necessary steps (Alfarraj, Drew and AlGhamdi, 2011).

The Saudi Arabian printing industry can overcome these challenges through adopting new leads, new technologies, new ideas, good marketing, customization, and value-added services. These steps can support the industry to reach to the next level of profitability and attaining the

market share in the upcoming times. The owners and management of the medium to large scale printing enterprises are required to keep abreast with the latest trends and technologies.

Further, the firms in the printing industry are dealing with many challenges and threats posed by changing client preference and increasing popularity of internet and digital means of communication along with the changing market conditions.

The companies and the economists both are considering the development of strategies and plans to face the growing decline in demand of printing products (Baltes, 2016).

It is also analysed from different reports that industry is facing a consistent price pressure on transactional work as well as the contract renewal across all the printing segments due to the massively competitive market conditions and unexploited capacity throughout the industry.

Alkhaldi (2016) further adds that the printing industry has a problematic level of unused manufacturing capacity as the result of the downfall in the business volume during the past recession which is now reflected in consistent downward pricing pressure. The points described below are the basic challenges in front of the printing company.

2.2.4.1 Loss of Customers

The consistent digitalization and availability of various options in the printing segment presented by the multinational companies has created a threat of loss of customers in front of the average to medium scale companies. The large-scale multinationals further offer the comparatively better products at a lesser price. The traditional customers of the companies also move towards the providers of innovative ideas and efficient costs. Alotaibi (2013) motioned that the influence of brand images, marketing campaigns and impressive customer relationship management practices also cannot be denied in the success of firm. Ultimately, the companies must work hard to get the new customers and retain the existing clientele

2.2.4.2 Adverse impact on revenue and profitability

The competitive market conditions, inadequate utilized enterprise capacities and raising the costs of business operations put adverse impact on revenue. In the quest of maintaining the clients the printing companies must compromise in the terms of prices. They must meet with the prices and the quality standards offered by the large scale and multinational printing companies that causing the downward pressure on the revenue of SME printing vendors (Thompson, 2015). On the other hand, the costs of raw material, marketing and adoption of newer technologies are also reflecting in inflow of incomes and profitability as well.

2.2.4.3 Inclusion of technology in the business

The spectrum of the printing industry is getting wider than ever before and requiring the companies to gain maximum efficiency in the business. The printing giants like OCE, Canon, Agfa etc. invest significantly on the development of solution-based technologies. Furthermore, the technology is changing rapidly and steadily that is beyond the economical limits of SME printing enterprises. The scope of printing technology advancement contains printing machines, raw material, and hardware and software altogether (AlSaadi, 2012). At the same time, it is also needed to be compatible with the existing machines and installation.

2.2.4.4 Lack of management support

The present-day clients look for the high-quality printing products at lowest price and within a fast turnaround time. Dulis (2012) in his article specifies that there is higher requirement of aggressive marketing campaigns, estimating upcoming trends in market, client preferences and technological advancements. At the same time, the role of customer relationship management and providing post sales services are also an essential part of maintaining the clientele in the competitive business format. While most of the printing companies in Saudi Arabia are being

operated and managed as the family operations, the lack of management excellence poses a big challenge to utilize the potential and attain the opportunities.

2.2.4.5 Lack of Resources

Internet has brought about a digital revolution in the printing industry. To keep at par with the latest technological advancement in printing requires a tech savvy workforce with superior IT skills. This is a critical issue in the Saudi workforce. The current IT skills within the native Saudi workforce are sub-standard to what is needed to adopt the digital revolution in the printing industry (Baltes, 2016). To exacerbate the human resource crisis within the Saudi printing industry, the government has strict regulations in place to protect the native workforce and restrict inflow of skilled migrant labour in KSA. These regulations are discussed in detail in the up-coming sections. In the absence of skilled talent within the Saudi workforce it becomes extremely challenging for SME printing firms to innovate.

2.2.4.6 Increased threat of substitution due to Internet

Digital revolution is rapidly making traditionally popular products of print such as magazines and newspapers obsolete in the printed format. Furthermore, advertising and marketing done in traditional printed mediums are now swiftly being replaced much cheaper, faster with wider reach mediums such digital advertising and marketing. Brochures, flyers, and other advertising products are rapidly being replaced by the electronic versions (Beck & Johnson 2017). The printing companies are forced to look for the new markets and develop the innovative ideas to attract the customers and survive in the harsh competitive environment. In this regard, internet is substituting traditional product lines within the printing industry.

2.3 THEME 2: PRINTING INDUSTRY: TRENDS AND KEY STAKEHOLDERS

In this section both global trends and Saudi specific trends in the printing industry will be discussed. The notion of Saudization within the printing industry will also be put forward to critique its applicability on the Saudi printing industry.

2.3.1 External Environmental Factors of Printing Industry and Associated Risks

The notion of Saudization relates to immediate replacement of emigrant workers with the native Saudi workforce in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. Roots of Saudization could be traced back to the first five-year plan spanning from 1970-1975. Saudization emerged due to a combination of socio-economic factors. The ruling class in Saudi Arabia faced a challenge of rising unemployment in the kingdom coupled with a growing budget deficit. Additionally, Saudis under the age of 20 years accounted for more than half of the country's population (Pfaff, 1991). To ameliorate the crisis, policy makers turned to replacing the emigrant workforce which accounted for roughly six million emigrants with the native Saudi workforce (Smith 2002).

In essence, Saudization is an aggressive protectionist policy aimed at safeguarding the indigenous Saudi work force. The message of Saudization roughly translates in Arabic to “taking back ownership” of the Saudi labor market. To achieve a complete Saudization the emigrant labor force needs to be systematically reduced and eventually eliminated. Thus, creating vacancies for the native Saudi work force. Saudization is viewed by the government as an immediate solution to curbing rising unemployment in KSA. The ideology behind Saudization is linked with creating a gainfully employed indigenous workforce capable of driving the Saudi economy towards national wealth creation. Saudization is also aimed at reducing the wealth drain in the form of financial remittance by the emigrant workforce.

Historical trends suggest road towards Saudization hasn't been straight forward. Saudization has attracted criticism for being naïve and unrealistic. It can potentially damage the private sector and reduce international competitiveness of the Saudi economy (Ali 2009). At the time of its inception, law makers in KSA decreed 75% of the work force to be Saudi with 51% of total salaries to be paid only to Saudi workers across all businesses (Arab News 2014). This initial move towards Saudization was part of the first five-year plan of 1970-1975. The policy failed drastically. The emigrant work force grew during this period owing to market forces. This left the law makers to realize achieving Saudization will prove to be more cumbersome than initially anticipated. For the following two decades the Saudization policy took a back seat followed by a re-emergence in 1995. During 1995, the government launched an aggressive campaign to achieve Saudization in the public sector. The rationale for specifically targeting the private sector as given by the law makers was that private sector had more scope for Saudization than public sector. Public sector was reported to have achieved the targeted levels of Saudization (Thompson 2014).

The following five-year plan of 1995-2000 set out objectives for achieving Saudization with the creation of more than 300k job because of replacement with the emigrant workforce (Looney, 2004). Again, this objective could not be met, and the emigrant labor force grew during this period (Labor force survey, 2000). The Saudi government was forced to acknowledge that all previous attempts towards achieving Saudization had been ineffective. Instead of looking for other measures to address the socio-economic challenges posed by a growing population, policy makers decided to introduce hostile policy measures linked with foreign worker recruitment in KSA. These measures included increased visa fee, establishing a higher threshold for minimum wage for foreign workers and overall increasing the cost of recruiting foreign workers.

2.3.1.1 Saudization & Challenges Posed for Printing Industry

The reaction of the Saudi private sector towards Saudization is rather dubious. It can be argued that private sector did not see Saudization as a serious threat in the early years of its inception (NIIR Board 2011). The rationale behind this belief is Saudization could not be implemented on the scale the law makers had proposed without seriously jeopardizing the economy. To put simply, the private sector completely ignored government's Saudization targets which involved replacing millions of emigrant workers for Saudi nationals. It was in the 1990s when the government started introducing punitive policy measures for recruiting foreign workers coupled with strict Saudization quota requirements is when reality finally dawned upon the Saudi private sector.

Saudization came as an unwelcomed reality for the private sector. Many industries including the printing, publishing and media were reluctant to replace expatriates with Saudi workers. The justifications given are multifold. On one hand, by adhering to Saudization the industry will likely forever lose its ability to source talent from overseas. On the other, the level of productivity and standard will go down by replacing expatriate workers with Saudi workers (Marashdeh and Al-Malkawi, 2014). Industry leaders claim Saudi workers to be inept and not ready to be working at the level of their counterparts (Country Report: Saudi Arabia Country Report: Saudi Arabia, 2017). The industry wide experience with employing young Saudi workers has been bleak. The consensus of that young Saudi work force lacks the skills, work ethic and dedication in comparison to the expatriates. In this regard, Saudization poses a threat for the industry to lose its competitive advantage by downgrading the quality of its final output. This ultimately affects the profitability.

The issue of lack of skills and work ethics amongst the young Saudi work force is a result of a defunct education system and years of reliance on the state welfare (Faisal, 2017).

Employability levels of the Saudi graduate workforce stands at a mere 2% (Haykel et al, 2015). The government recognize this challenge and have started introducing education reforms. However, the effectiveness of these reforms could only be yielded in the long term. In the immediate future, the printing industry is apprehensive about changing its ways to accommodate the forced influx of the young Saudi workers. At a social level, the industry acknowledges the need for Saudization and sympathizes with the young Saudi worker's need to gain employment and work experience. However, on a fiscal level the industry is not able to support them at the risk of damaging their private economy. The printing and publishing industry has pointed out to the poor quality of training giving to the young Saudis (Saudi Print & Pack, 2017). These training programs are part of the educational reform funded by the HRDF. Additionally, the industry leaders also express their inability to be train young Saudis owing to resource constraints such as time and money. The skills required to drive innovation in the Saudi printing industry are IT related. Young Saudis lack technical skills such as IT and creative thinking (Abouammoh, 2013). Studies on Saudization indicate hiring managers expressing a disregard for their autonomy in running their own business by the government (Kirst-Ashman, 2010).

Major constraints towards effectively incorporating the young Saudi work force include time, expertise, and cost of training. This argument is found to be prevalent across all industries within the Saudi private sector. Critical challenge to Saudization include declining productivity and profitability of the private sector due to the limited pool of talented workers available to them. While Saudization is hardly a new policy initiative but the private sector failed to equip itself for dealing with it. Perhaps, this could be attributed to the negligence towards Saudization in earlier decades. For decades the Saudi private sector benefitted from the ease of recruiting foreign workers. The expatriates came ready to drive the Saudi private sector forward with their high level of skills and strong work ethic. Both qualities are lacking

in the young Saudi work force. To exacerbate the situation, the private sector is expected to train the young Saudi newcomers to the labor force. They are expected to instill hard and soft skills through workplace training. Doing so is cumbersome, time consuming and highly cost ineffective for the private sector.

Successful Saudization is seen to be more practical for large private organizations which have the ability to absorb unskilled workers owing to strict quota regulations. These organizations have larger resources at their disposal to be able to meet the time, cost and expertise constraints attached with training young Saudis. These larger organizations are clandestine to highly developed human resources department capable of training young Saudi hires. The problem it poses is that vast majority of the printing industry is formed of small to mid-sized firms which simply do not have these resources. Therefore, Saudization is an added strain to the already struggling Saudi printing and publishing industry.

2.3.1.2 Impact on Economy & Implications

Saudization has two main economic implication for the private sector within KSA. The first and most obvious economic implication relates to the stifling of productivity and profitability. Introducing an influx of sub skilled new Saudis into the private sector will drive down the level of output, resulting in lowered profitability. This in turn will have a perverse impact on the Saudi economy.

The second and rather unseen impact of Saudization on the economy is a slow-down in the foreign direct investment (FDI). To illustrate, abiding by the stringent quota system can jeopardize the willingness of private foreign players to invest in KSA. This is since lowered levels of productivity as a direct consequence of Saudization will negatively impact the competitiveness of foreign firms in Saudi Arabia. Furthermore, the Saudization program has

proven to be unstable with government abruptly changing quota requirements and adding more stringent rules. This produces an uncertain business environment which foreign investors are keen on avoiding when looking to invest in a country. Thus, Saudization leads to a reduction in FDI. To address the issue to diminishing FDI the government has recently announced its decision to cut the foreign investment tax rates by nearly half (Nitisha, 2017).

In terms of implications of Saudization, there are lessons to be learnt by similar policy measures in Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries. From their collective experience to boost native work force employment opportunities GCC countries arrived at following conclusions (Iqbal2011):

- To sustain employment opportunities for a growing native workforce the only long-term solution is creation of “new employment opportunities” instead of trying to replace expatriates with native workforce.
- Creation of new employment opportunities is very difficult in the absence of FDI.
- There is no substitute for pre-training the workforce through an effective education system prior to their entering the labor market.
- Having a large expatriate workforce which tends to remit significant portions of their earnings to their home countries creates an environment where sustaining high levels of domestic demand becomes increasingly challenging.

2.3.1.3 The Role of Market Forces & Incentives

Economic theory has some valuable propositions for tactful implementation of the Saudization. Ineffectiveness of the Saudization in the previous decade lends support to the argument of implementing Saudization via market forces. Saudization should not be forced upon the private sector but instead enforced using market forces. *“Saudization should not be approached as a zero-sum problem, but instead implemented in a growth-oriented environment assisted with expanded foreign investment, induced in part through an expanded and reformed education/training program (Kechichian 2004).”* To sum it up, Saudization should create jobs for the native Saudis in a business environment characterized by increased competitiveness and strong non-oil growth (Horsed and Al-Fezzan 2014).

- Empirical evidence suggests the demand for native workers is inversely proportional to the cost of their recruitment as well as the cost of employing low skilled foreigners. A reduction in low skilled employees likely increases the productivity, hence an increase in the costs associated with hiring low skilled workers would reduce the demand for hiring low skilled workers of any origin.
- In case the young Saudis are sufficiently capable of replacing the skilled foreign workers then the demand for employing Saudi workers should be positively linked with the cost of employing skilled workers. Therefore, increases in the costs associated with hiring skilled worker will reduce demand for skilled foreign workers. This will lead to a healthy substitution of expatriates with Saudis.

- Demand for native workers is positively linked with their level of human capital factors such as education levels and skills levels. Hence, an investment in increasing these factors of human capital should yield a higher return from hiring native workers.

The above propositions derived from the economic theory could lead to better formulation of Saudization strategy by the government. In contrast to aggressive protectionism based on strict quantitative measures such as quota system, policy measures derived from the above propositions are likely to be more in tune with demand and supply dynamics of the market. Saudization strategy based on the above propositions is likely to produce a strong competitive market environment and economy. In this way Saudization could pave the way for a strong non-oil growth for the Saudi economy.

2.3.1.4 Skills Development within Saudi Native Workforce

Domestic demand and employment could be boosted by investing in human capital factor such as education and skill development. To increase skills and education of the young Saudis entering the labor market drastic measures will need to be employed by the government. These drastic measures relate to a comprehensive reform of the Saudi education system. Specific measures such introducing vocational training; internships and scholarships for graduates; restructuring the secondary education system; and creating self-employment opportunities. These measures will develop skills and knowledge base of the young Saudis prior to entering the labor market.

To enable the Saudi economy to become competitive based on the skills of its native labor force a diversification of the economy is needed. This diversification relates to concentrating on developing non-oil-based sectors. The printing industry for instance could benefit from

government initiatives which foster acquisition of combination of skills set such as IT, mass communication, and technological.

Another way of boosting skills acquisition is through government subsidies in the form of training contracts for young Saudi graduates. The role of the government in fostering training contract opportunities will work two folds. On one hand, it will enable the young Saudi workforce to gain valuable skills set needed to forge a lasting career. On the other, it will act as a financial help for private firms employing these young Saudi graduates. The Human Resource Development Fund (HRDF) is a body set up the Saudi government which provides training contracts grants to the qualifying candidates to specifically work within the private sector.

Upon successful completion of the training contract, the salary resulting from the employment of the Saudi worker will be subsidized to the private company which hires the Saudi worker. In this way, the new Saudi worker as well the private firm hiring them will benefit from the scheme. The funding for the HRDF is drawn from a levy charge imposed on the hiring of foreign workers. Given the tremendous effort and time it could take to reform the Saudi educational system, private businesses will have to be subsidized for developing skills of Saudi workers.

The printing industry will specially benefit from facilitation of latest technology for increasing its consumer demand and in turn ability to hire more Saudi workers through increased productivity. To do so, the government will have to take initiatives to establish technology intensive clusters of industries within KSA. This will require an aberration from spending on the state welfare system towards economic and technologically focused measures. Research and development should be the focus of government spending to stimulate high employment through economic growth within the private sector.

2.3.1.5 Environmental Factors

Environmental concerns are a critical aspect of the printing business. Printing supply chains are required to comply with tight environmental regulations which are broadly aimed at limiting the environmental impact of volatile organic compounds used in the printing process. Recycling is another major environmental concern within the printing industry.

The printing industry is responsible for a vast impact on the environment. As per the reports by Hanks (2017), more than 40% of the trees harvested by timber companies throughout the globe are utilized by printing and publishing industry. The printing ink used by mainly contains petroleum-based ingredients and have a high concentration of VOC (volatile organic compounds) or carcinogens. The paper treatment process also includes the application of bleaching agents. The printing companies who accept the responsibility and address these concerns move towards using less hazardous inks and recyclable materials in their production generally must deal with the increase in production cost that affects revenue and profitability as well.

Studies on environmental impact of the printing industry note a shift towards environmentally sustainable business designs becoming more prevalent in the recent years (AIGA, 2017). A survey study reported around 33 per cent of printers to promote the use of recycled paper over new paper (Nickel-Kailings, 2009). Roughly 25 per cent of printers use environmental friendliness as a marketing tool (Nickel-Kailings, 2009). About 20 per cent of printers seek to invest in environmentally friendly equipment. Only 15 per cent of the printers reported to not having any kind of “environmental certification” (Nickel-Kailings, 2009).

End products of printing industry are environmentally costly products given the propensity for waste. It is estimated the proportion of printed products that do not even get used once is roughly 30 per cent (Nickel-Kailings, 2009). This is an alarming figure and calls printers to

understand and address the environmental issues linked with design, manufacturing and use of the printed products. To do so requires a structured approach needs to be developed at the business level. Printers are required to develop the knowledge & skills needed to create a sustainable design of print. This requires consideration of the entire print production cycle, *“from paper selection to printing processes to distribution and delivery as well as the end use and recovery of resources”* (Nickel-Kailings, 2009).

Practical ways to develop a sustainable design of print could include the following key recommendations:

- Design functions low energy demands.
- Develop closed loop lifecycles from design through to production.
- Think about recyclability and reusability.
- Choose material which lower environmental impact on key natural resources such as water, soil, and air.
- Optimize production techniques to eliminate scrap, error, and waste.
- Select lower-impact packaging and distribution systems.
- Maximize the length of the product’s useful life.
- Recover, reuse, and recycle materials at the end of the product’s life.
- Reduce ink coverage, gang print projects when possible, and incorporate soft proofing.

2.3.2 Industry Trends & Specifications

With the arrival of the internet enabled digital communication technologies in the last two decades the print has seen a rapid decline in demand. Most noticeable decline has been in the demand for printed paper. This declining trend is global and could be attributed directly to the rise of internet for communication, advertising, and marketing related purposes.

2.3.2.1 Internet Fuelled Digital Media

A global scale study has evaluated this declining demand for print. Findings indicate around one third of commercial printers and roughly half of publishing printers globally reported a downturn in demand (Drupa Global Insight, 2014).

Historically, one of the most profitable revenue streams for print has been advertising and marketing. The internet has fuelled the consistent aberration towards digital communication channels over the years. Evidence of this aberration is reported globally. For instance, demand for print based advertising has shrunk by more than half in the last decade (Ambroz, 2009)). The reason for this sharp decline is linked with the exponentially higher reach of digital based platforms in comparison to print based platforms. Increasing global and domestic competition leaves advertisers to seek platforms with the highest return on investment (Bennet, 2010). Additionally, digital platforms have attributes print platforms don't. These include track-ability; capacity to aggregate real time data on consumers; as well as the ability to be integrated to multiple marketing campaigns at once (Cagle, 2009). Owing to these factors print platforms for advertising and marketing are gradually becoming redundant.

2.3.2.2 Rise of All Things Digital

A shift from analogue to digital channels of communication have been made possible due to the advancement in technology. Cost of technology is inversely related to its potential. This is to say higher scalability of technology has resulted in cheaper computing processors and faster bandwidth of the internet. Mobile technology has driven the widespread adoptability of digital platforms for communication. The above factors combined explain how digital channels have overtaken analogous channels.

Over one third of the global population are connected via internet in some shape or form. However, it should be noted that distribution is uneven with higher concentrations in urban regions. It is estimated over half of the world's population will have access to mobile phones in the next five years (Coleman & Ramachandra, 2010). Prior to the advent of internet print dominated communications. However, the above facts point out print based channels are now a mere subset of a wider and marketing and communication industry. This development should signal a need for global printers to increasingly adopt IT based business models. The current reality of global printing is much different. Empirical evidence suggests less than a quarter of printers globally reported an increase in their technology infrastructure (Cross 2011). A significantly higher proportion of printers' report difficulties in effectively acquiring IT based edge into their business (Cummings et al, 2016). These findings show ineffectiveness of printers globally to exploit technology-based advantages. These advantages include:

- Rapid speed of real time communication.
- Multiple touch point interactions with customers.
- Meeting communication-based demands.

2.3.2.3 Significance of e-Commerce for Printing Industry

A result of technology revolution has been rising of ecommerce platforms. Ecommerce has disrupted numerous industries including publishing. Exponentially high adoptability of ecommerce has led it to becoming integral into consumer lifestyle. Experts believe print industry has been ineffective in uncapping the opportunities offered by ecommerce except for e-book publishing industry (Clinkenbroomer, 2003). Web to print service is an important application of print in ecommerce. However, empirical evidence shows less a quarter of web-to-print services are reported profitable by printers (Edmonds et al, 2011). Large scale extent

of ecommerce is an opportunity for printers to increase profitability by finding useful applications of web-to-print service. Increase in the volume of small runs of web-to-print for marketing purposes show a clear synergy between print and ecommerce.

2.3.2.4 Mass Customization: Shift towards VDP & other services

Printing industry has witnessed a huge shift towards smaller runs of digital print down to even singular runs. This shift is an aberration from the old days of bulk paper-based print. Increasing use of digital channels for marketing and communication has driven this shift. Variable Data Print (VDP) is a service offered by printers which aids customization. About three in four printers globally offer VDP (First Research, 2010). However, it is also reported that a vast majority of printers only offer very basic applications of VDP. A tiny minority of printers offer full scale potential for customization via VDP. These customizations include text as well as images variability for producing highly personalized content. A miniscule proportion of the global printing industry offer high tech personalization services such as interactive print such as QR codes and augmented reality (First Research, 2011). Interactive print services are integral to making print a pivotal part of online consumer product sales (Greenbaum, 2010).

In the recent years amount of digital data stored has spiked drastically. Studies estimate the digital data to increase by over 40% annually (Khazanchi, 2018). With a combination of the right IT infrastructure and skills an exact segmented marketing campaigns could be driven. This offers a huge business opportunity to diversify their core services to drive growth and profitability by offering to manage and analyse customer data. Only a handful of printers are doing so.

While the internet has opened opportunities for a greater degree of personalization, at the same time it has also driven the competition amongst printers. Printers now must compete in

larger market space without ever physically meeting their customers. An increase in demand for customization has led to adding of new products such as photobooks to the product mix. Internet has enabled printers to increase interactivity with customers to better understand how personalization could add value.

2.3.2.5 Potential for Internet to Manage Printing Businesses

Internet brings with it the prospect of adding new services which the printers could add to their repertoire. To illustrate, internet has drastically altered the ways in which businesses now operate with respect to its sales and marketing. Sales and marketing functions have become highly data driven in the recent years. This has led to an increased demand for database management and analytics services. Global trends suggest a small proportion of printers are now providing marketing analytics; database management and social media marketing services (Romano, 2019a).

More so, the internet also provides opportunities for printing business to streamline their internal processes. Essentially, internet enabled internal processes could result in a cheaper and more efficient way of running a printing business. For instance, only about 20% of printing businesses have automated processes ranging from initial enquiry to invoicing (Romano & Webb, 2018).

2.4 THEME 3: PRODUCT MIX

Product mix is a term to refer to the entire products and services which are offered by a business. In this way, product mix could be thought of as the product portfolio which consists of product lines (Cant, Kallier & Wiid 2016). Product lines is a collective of products which are similar in nature and tend to complement each other. According to the theory of product mix, it is a wholesome range of product lines of similar or different categories of products. The

manufacturers, to take full advantage of a brand's value and success of existing products, often evolve the product lines in the product mix (Onyeoch, 2015). Product mix could be thought of as a subset of the broader marketing mix framework. The products decisions within the marketing mix framework fall under the purview of the product mix. Product mix entails four key dimensions.

Product Width

Product width refers to the number of product lines being produced by the company or manufacturer. In the specific context of the printing industry, the product width comprises of product offerings such as advertising- products, stationery, packaging products and literary products. Thereby, it can be said that width of the product mix in the printing industry broadly is distributed within four product lines. According to Mayer, Melitz and Ottaviano (2014) with the strategy of offering a wide array of product lines a company tries to satisfy the bigger range of consumers and diversify risks of given product becoming obsolete.

Product Length

Product length is regarded as the aggregate total of the products and services provided by the business. For instance, in case, if a printing company offers 7 product lines with 5 products each under these product lines, the product length present by the company is 35. Pahwa (2017) suggests that with a longer product line a company offers the customers more options of products for greater satisfaction.

Product Depth

The total number of products within a product line as a part of a product mix is known as product depth. It is closely concerned to the product length and facilitates the customer's options while making a choice in proposed products. Depth can also be referred as the ways

that a client can buy a product in a product line. For instance, a customer of a printing company can order the letter pads made using handmade paper in the stationary section, silk umbrellas with customized logos for advertising and printed glossy labels as the packaging product. It enhances the flexibility of the buyer.

Product Consistency

The term product consistency refers to the connection between the products presented within a specific product line and the way they are reached to the clients. It also can be described as how closely a company's products are linked to each other and the production process as well. The consistency in the product mix facilitates the manufacturer to suggest or recommend the closest product to clients. It is also cost effective and more efficient. Distinct products in the mix are resulting in a unique selling process for that product.

The concept as well as the analysis of product mix is essential for a company dealing with a diversified product range. Mayer, Melitz and Ottaviano (2014), in his article, stated that the companies with a vast product mix have several reasons and ways for this diversification. It helps in increasing the company's reach to the customers of different categories in the terms of budget, preference, convenience, etc. This diversification helps a product mix to get expanded beyond modifications or offering the complementary products.

The study and interpretation of product mix is further recommended as it facilitates the management of economies of scale. There is a higher possibility in a manufacturing unit to produce a wide range of products with a variety of differences by making only a minor change in the ratio of ingredient or modification in the manufacturing process. Here, it is also possible to produce the goods with limited demand or the limited-edition version of any specific product without increasing the overall production cost (Can't, Kallier and Wiid, 2016).

A company having an appropriate assortment of products and services concerning its field can successfully meet with the customers' needs and expectations. With the reliance of getting the one stop solution for their requirements customers don't move towards the competitors. So, the companies need to carefully and consistently monitor the product mix along with getting feedbacks from the clients to survive the tough competition. The product mix analysis for a company is further important in the determination of its business and brand image as well.

2.4.1.1 Substitute of Internet for Printing Firms

The advent of the internet has driven multiple technologies such as big data, 3-Dimensional printing and augmented reality. The key stakeholders in the printing industry include printing businesses; key suppliers; and customers. In this section we will review how the rise of the internet has disrupted business for key stakeholders in the global printing industry.

2.4.1.2 Technology Based Product Advancement in Global Printing Industry

Key findings of "Drupa Global Insights" report will be listed in this section. Drupa Global is a leading authority on global trends in the printing industry. The research for the Drupa Global Insights report included over 1000 printing industry key personnel and executives globally. The Drupa Global Insights report specifically investigated the impact of the internet upon print. Aspects of the printing business covered in the report include client-relationship management; Digital services; print process automation; and scope for printing firms to improve their IT skills. The report concludes "*that printers need to accept the reality of an Internet-driven multi-channel digital future, change their approach and invest accordingly (Drupa Global Insights, 2014)*".

The main findings of the Drupa report on "*The Impact of the Internet on Print – The digital flood*" lists out disruptive impact of internet enabled technologies on the global printing industry. Specific examples of these disruptive technologies include variable data printing;

web-to-print services; customizable and interactive printing based on QR codes and Augmented Reality tools. The above technologies are directly impacting printing businesses. They present challenges as well as opportunities for the global printing industry.

2.4.1.3 Rapid Scaling of e-commerce & Web-to-print Services

Increased harmonization of local and global trade laws along has enabled increased global trading activities. The rise of the internet has given birth to the e-commerce platforms globally. Global retailers have harnessed the internet for expanding their reach at rapid rates. While, the global printers are yet to catch up. According to the findings, over half of the respondents reported having web-to-print services included in their product offering. However, only 14% of these respondents reported web-to-print services to account for more than quarter of their sales (Drupa Global Insights, 2014).

Web-to-print services also known as “print e-commerce solution” offers print based products via online vendor’s online platform. Web-to-print is a popular service used for marketing purposes by businesses and individuals. Web to print service reduces the overall cost of printing for businesses by eliminating third party marketing or design teams (Kipphan 2001). The printers provide their customers with the printer’s online portal for web-to-print services where the customer could fill in print orders. An important feature of web-to-print service is enabling the customer to upload their own creative design. This gives the user control while minimizing the time for the entire printing process. Standard PDF format files are used to provide customer’s own creative content which is then digitally processed and sent back online for approval. Once approved, the digital print is then sent in for the press.

In the initial days of web-to-print, customers were able to connect with printing firms via internet. This enabled printing firms to expand their clientele into far off geographical regions

and markets. Cost of web-to-print services have significantly reduced owing to advancement in technology and accessibility.

2.4.1.4 Move towards Mass Customization

A clear trend has emerged in the global printing industry which is focused on delivering customizable large-scale printing solutions. Global printers have reported a surge in customizable print-based products such as books, marketing content, calendars, stationary, etc. According to the Drupa Global Insights report, over 70% of the global printers reported offering variable data printing services. This trend was particularly high in the US printing industry with over 85% of American printers offering variable data printing services (Drupa Global Insight, 2014).

Variable data printing (VDP) is a technique for digital printing which has customizable elements such as text, graphics, and photos for each individual print. It is a popular service for creating customizable copies your original digital print. For instance, a prospect client would want to create customizable copies of marketing material of its different product streams whilst retaining the theme of the business. They could do so with VDP. VDP allows printing unique print designs in this way.

A growing proportion of commercial printers globally are now offering print-based products which could be personalized and sold online. About 40% of the commercial printer and 30% of publishing printer reported this trend (Drupa Global Insights, 2014). Globally, printers are looking to improving their customizable print products through acquiring electro-photographic color sheet printers (Drupa Global Insight, 2014).

2.4.1.5 Rise of Interactive Printing

Globally an increasing number of businesses are realizing the potential for digital marketing and increasing their interpersonal interaction with their customers. Internet based technologies have enabled increased interactivity between businesses and their customers via digital print. These businesses require multiple media campaigns for collecting and analyzing big data about their customers.

Internet enabled technologies which enable this interactivity include QR codes, small print options and augmented reality. Globally, just over 30% of printers provide services which enable interactivity printing services (Drupa Global Insights, 2014). These interactive printing services include advertisement (using small print), custom packaging (using QR codes) and outdoor advertisements, etc.

The findings indicate to stark differences between the US and the Middle Eastern printing markets. According to the report over 40% of printing businesses provide some form of interactivity printing service, **while only 3% of Middle Eastern printing firms do so**. This finding indicates a potential for Middle Eastern printers into diversifying their product mix portfolio.

2.4.1.6 Revolution of the 3D Print

In terms of innovation, the most disruptive impact has come from the 3-Dimensional printing technology (Drupa Global Insights, 2014). 3-Dimensional printing relates to printing out intricate components to be used in machinery. The intricate components are unfeasible for mass production, hence 3-D printing is a viable solution to producing these components. 3-Dimensional printers take custom inputs from the user about the dimensions of the printed object. The output is remarkable quicker to produce than any mass production methods. The scope for 3-D printing enabled through internet technology is vast. Initially, 3-Dimensional

printing technology was developed to provide customizable machinery components.

However, in the recent year start-up businesses are using 3-Dimensional printing to print out objects such as houses, boats and even rockets. In this regard, 3-Dimensional printing technology offers significant opportunity for global printers to expand their product offering.

2.4.2 Al-Fakhoor Printing Company

This study benefits from the case study of a Saudi SME printing and publishing enterprise, namely ALFakhoor Printing Company. Justifications for adopting a case study approach are provided in the “Research Methodology” chapter. Saudi printing SME firms are largely homogenous and there is little differentiation within this subset of the printing industry. Al-Fakhoor is based in Riyadh, KSA. The firm is an interesting case study as it is currently in the process of transforming their business from print towards digital. The senior management of the firm realises the need for this transition as a way of responding to the digital revolution. During the time of this research the firm was in the initial stages of planning their move towards digital platforms of printing.

2.4.2.1 Company Background

Al-Fakhoor is a local Riyadh based printing and publishing company. The firm was established in 1985 by Al Rahmani brothers as a small print shop. The business can withstand the initial technological disruptions in the early 1990s with the arrival of personal photocopier and printers into the market. The firm later expanded into the publishing business with the publication of its in-house local magazine – Al Noorah. The readership of the magazine is mostly confined to local regions in Riyadh. The core business of the firm to this day remains printing. As aforementioned, currently the business realizes the need to transform their business from print to digital. Findings and Analysis sections discusses the specific plans and strategies

of how this transformation is likely to take place after conducting semi structure interviews with top management at Al-Fakhoor.

2.4.2.2 Company Size and Growth

It has 3 main departments which work according to the phases of the printing work.

Prepress:

The Prepress department works 24*7 throughout the year. A team of 8 qualified and skilled staff is capable to deal with all typed prepress work, including scanning, designing, retouching, and outputting of plates and films using the advanced technology and equipment's. The company further specializes all digital prepress work with higher quality and speed.

Press:

The press or production department is equipped with high capacity; best resolution printing machines operated by 10 skilled and well-trained employees 365 days for 24 hours.

Post-Press:

The post-press operations, including binding, cutting, finishing and logistics are handled by the 6 employees with exceptional speed and experience without any break throughout the year. At present the company is providing the highest quality printing and marketing assistance to the leading companies within the nation and to the neighbouring countries also. Having the benefit of favourable geographical locations, Al-Fakhoor Printing Company covers a large market beyond boundaries and beholds a great potential for the future. Its profit margin is decreasing as due to internet evolution and social media, printing workflow is continuously reducing.

2.4.2.3 Current Customers

The main customers of Al-Fakhoor are retailers, schools, universities, small size enterprises, NGOs, media and financial companies, marketing and event companies and stationers. Al-Fakhoor Printing Company is offering a high-quality printing service in many ways. The main outputs of the company include office stationary, magazines, brochures and booklets, corporate files and annual reports, school books and diaries, desk pads, flyers, poster, maps, stickers, labels, greeting cards and calendar, display stands, business forms, packaging, paper carry bags, etc. in this way the company cover almost all the clients' needs concerning to printing and packaging.

2.4.2.4 Organizational Resources and Capabilities

The highlight of Al-Fakhoor organization is its team of trained and experienced designers and print specialists, who is providing the printing services with the highest standard. The projects of all the sizes and types are handled

The quality and promptness are offered with cost effectiveness at the same time. The company charges most affordable and highly competitive prices for its services. The company further provides the right specifications and service packages as per the client's budget.

2.4.3 Current Product Mix of Al-Fakhoor Printing Firm

At present the firm offers advertising and marketing products, literary products, database management printing, packaging products and stationary products. The core products of the company include office stationary, magazines, brochures and booklets, corporate files and annual reports, school books and diaries, desk pads, flyers, poster, maps, stickers, labels, greeting cards and calendar, display stands, business forms, packaging and paper carry bags.

2.5 THEME 4: SUGGESTIONS

2.5.1 Strategies to Minimize Risk and Challenges of Internet on printing firms

From the above discussion, it is found that several challenges are faced by the printing companies of Saudi Arabia to make sure about the growth and success of their business. Thus, there is a need to identify effective business strategies that can be helpful to minimize the risk as well as an adverse impact on the business. The below section defines some strategies that can be used by printing companies to minimize risk in the product mix:

2.5.1.1 Response to the Challenged Posed by Internet: A Global Perspective

Owing to the disruption caused by the internet a large majority of printing businesses are now looking to diversifying their business model. This diversification is aimed at seeking new avenues for revenues to respond to the diminishing historical revenue streams such as paper-based print products. This has led to an increasing number of printers adding new services and products to their product mix.

Internet enabled digital communication comes with potential to harness huge amounts of customer data. The data can be used to gain key insights into consumer behaviour and drive strategies designed to increase effective product offering for the customer. Highly optimized segmenting of customers based on their inherent traits could be achieved through analysing large amounts of consumer data. Currently a small minority of large printing firms are doing so effectively (Arab News, 2014). The results of increased interaction with customers and optimized segmenting has been largely reported as positive in terms of increased growth and profitability (Croteau and Hoynes 2006).

The major challenges for printers which have resulted in a decline in productivity and growth include fierce competition due to increased access to markets; commoditization; degrading sales volumes; lack of IT capacity and recruitment of IT skilled talent pool (Rogers, 2013).

To boost sales, the printers will have to increase its customer base. Acquiring new customers requires better marketing and sales techniques. Experts believe that majority of struggling printers are not focused on driving their marketing campaigns through digital channels (Dobelli (2013). These printers have been criticized for assuming the lack of sales as lack of potential customers. Whereas, it is their inability to engage and sell value of digital print across multiple channels to prospect customers.

Global scale studies on the printing industry point out towards the need for printers to acknowledge and address a need to transition their business from traditional print to digital print and all the range of possibilities which come with it (Lundgren and McMakin, 2013). These studies argue printing firms will need to reassess what it means to be a printer in the new digital age. There is a growing need for printing business to transform their business to keep up with the changing landscape of the printing industry. Printers are urged to add new services and products which are technology driven and more importantly add value to their customers. This will require rethinking existing product offerings and business models.

Studies indicate a small portion of printers are evaluating their product offerings and business model (Print Future, 2016). The findings show a bleak reality of the global printing industry. About one third of the printers express their inability to make a transition from traditional print to digital print and diversification of product offerings (Print Future, 2016). These printers are large small to medium scale and attribute their inability to transition on resource constraints and market forces. About a quarter of printing firms acknowledge there is a need for them to diversify their product offering and transitioning towards print but are yet to take

any tangible steps (Print Future, 2016). Another 30 per cent of printers' report to have just started the transition process and still have a long way before they fully develop digital based capacity. Only about 10 per cent of the printing firms have successfully transitioned into the digital print arena. These printing firms provide a comprehensive range of digital print-based service plus add on services such as database management, consumer analytics and social media marketing (Print Future, 2016).

2.5.1.2 Scope for Evolution of the Printing Businesses

Studies have shown that from the buyer of print-based product's perspective find it difficult to be able to differentiate between printers (Croteau and Hoynes, 2006). This is to say that printing firms with alike quality of product, service and pricing strategy are finding it difficult to stand out. This issue is mostly prevalent in small to medium sized printing enterprises (Bland 2013). Based on these findings it can be argued that printing business need to reconsider their marketing and sales strategy.

Compared to the trends two decades there has been a predisposition now more than ever towards digital platforms by the masses. This is to say that marketing strategies are now shifting their budget resources towards digital platforms as compared to traditional platforms such as newspapers and magazines. Web based marketing has become the norm with a spike in methods such as "search engine optimization (SEOs)", and creation new product websites. Growth of personalized user generated content is the key reason for this shift towards digital platforms. As a result, the commercial printing business are facing decline in their revenue streams. Experts argue in response to this decline the printers must add services and products whilst shifting their focus towards new revenue streams (Info Trends, 2019).

Challenge to transition towards digital for the printing firms is dichotomous in nature:

- Developments into the digital landscape is rapid and it makes it difficult for printers to transition owing to the challenge of keeping up.
- There is lack of demand amongst customers of small to medium sized printers for innovative services and products. Large sized printers are better equipped to drive innovation in the printing industry.

Small and medium sized printers globally are faced with the challenge of responding to diminishing growth and profitability, declining revenues whilst simultaneously taking on the strain of developing digital based capacity. Nevertheless, empirical evidence suggests investing in capacity building will help printers to safeguard their business from the rapidly shifting future (Davis 2011).

Demand for digital print is on the rise however there are several key points which global printers should be aware of (Print Future, 2016). These include:

- Declining trends in developed markets while growing trends in the emerging markets.
- Interactive services are a key source of future growth.
- Customization and digital print are rapidly growing consistently across all markets.
- Future print providers will need to provide add on services such as database management.
- Developing IT capacity and creating a cross media presence are critical to customer acquisition and customer experience.

2.5.1.3 Innovation is the Road Forward

Key to overcoming the disruption caused by technology into printing industry is by embracing the change and finding ways to turning it into opportunity. This can be effectively done by printing firms developing new services and products which enhance the customer experience and add value. Several studies into the future of global printing industry point out printers will need to engage their customers and become a part of the marketing and communication solution by offering value added services such as social media marketing, marketing analytics, etc (Info Trends, 2019). In these types of markets, the customer will have higher degree of choice of services and the platforms they wish to engage with. In this way traditional prints will have to provide a lot more in terms of product offering.

A growing number of print providers are increasing their social media related activity to better engage their customers. Printers are now realizing the need to closely engaging their customers to develop better customer relationships.

The era of market push from traditional media is transitioning into the customer centric market pull (Myers 2014). To illustrate, printers are now developing strategies to build a closer and interpersonal connection with their customer base. They are doing so via highly customized, video, and digital print-based communication in addition to social media interactions with the customer. It is also important to be able to match the right tool with the right strategy for every segment. Key findings of research on marketing in the printing industry asserts need for better customer segmentation based on their needs is equally as important as segmentation of customers based on their preferred channel of interaction (Miller, 2013). Printing firms that understand this are engaging across multiple channels to boost revenue streams.

Use of a single channel approach for data capturing is deemed ineffective in practice. There is a need to develop multiple campaigns across multiple channels to be able to gain meaningful insights. Digital printing firms have developed capacity through engaging their customers across multiple channels. The insights are used to design strategies into educating prospect clients about scope of return on investment into their services. Effective use of new media platforms leads to enhanced customer engagement.

A valuable insight from Kasedrof (2003) relates to the need for printing firms to increasing efficiency of their printing process. The author argues in order to gain a competitive edge the printing firms will need to ensure their run time efficiency is not sacrificed with increases in lengths of print runs. This is in addition to diversifying the marketing and product offering approach, i.e. addition of new products and services whilst developing a multiple channel marketing approach. The findings of the study reveal that average job value is inversely proportional to run time (Capelle, 2004). To illustrate, majority of the small to medium sized printers do not have automation in place to save time and cost of printing. The manual operating of printing process results in decreased efficiency and quality of the final print product. Investing in automation could save them not only in time and cost of printing but also result in better waste management. Waste management is an under investigated aspect of printing (Capelle, 2004). Effective waste management at printing businesses could result in increased cost efficiency as well as greater environmental sustainability. Similar studies estimate effective waste management could save around 6% to 40% of total paper consumption. Hence, developing an effective waste management strategy could help struggling printing firms build a more agile business model.

2.5.2 Proposed Product Mix for Al-Fakhoor Printing Firms

Product mix for a company is the range of various products that it presents in front of its customers. In order to deliver highest satisfaction to the clients and attaining the maximum margin over the costs, a company must determine the optimal product mix which works as a tool or strategy that maximize the sales, maintains or improves the profitability of the business while fulfilling both the short term and long term goals of at the same time. The essential elements of an optimal product mix for Al-Fakhoor Printing Company are given below.

2.5.2.1 Higher Margin Products

More often, the highest margin products by the company are not the highest selling products due to their less appearance in the best-selling list, but at the same time, these are the ones who ensure the highest bottom line profits. While there is a sudden and unpredicted change in the market trends and results in a slowdown in unit sales, a product mix containing the higher margin items help in maintaining the profitability until the business circumstances and sales volume return to normal.

Al-Fakhoor Printing Company deals in the providing of versatile printing services from stationary to advertising material and packaging items as well. The product mix of the company contains both the high margin and higher unit sales items. The company management must focus on adding some more high margin products to secure the financial interest in case of any unexpected downfall in the ongoing market flow.

2.5.2.2 Growth Potential

A company that present the products with the potential of having a large market share ensure the success and growth in the future. Developing new product require extensive market research, analysing consumer behaviour along with research and development capabilities. Sometimes, the products with long term potential tend to show give slow response and take

time. The companies are recommended to continue to devote marketing resources towards the products with highest growth potential so that they can begin to achieve higher sales.

The product mix of Al-Fakhoor seems more concentrated over the traditional printing products such as stationery and advertising. The company needs to give its extra attention towards packaging and labelling customers as the recent industry trends are indicating the remarkable growth in this sector.

2.5.2.3 Cross Selling Potential

Along with the specific products in a product mix, there are some product combinations that can encourage the customers to buy both. Generally, one of them can be of fewer prices, but in a combination increases the value of the next one. For example, in a printing deal, a brand wants the T-shirts printed with the specified logo. Here, the printing company can offer the value-added services such as packing of the individual T-shirts and deliver each of them to the pre-destined destination under a packaged service. This kind of product or service combinations in a product mix of Al Fakhoor printing company can enhance its sales potential and satisfaction level of the customers as well.

2.5.2.4 Line Extension Products

Product line extension refers to increasing the “breadth” of the product mix. This is the process of adding on new products/services to the existing product mix. Clear advantage of increasing the breadth of the product mix relates to increased interaction with the customer by offering a greater number of products/services. This increased interaction has been shown to increase the likelihood of sales. In the specific context of the printing industry, product mix is extended through the addition of host of new technological based products such as 3D printing, water resistant print, multiple surface printing techniques, etc.

2.5.2.5 Life Cycle Consideration

Product life cycle needs to be taken into consideration when reviewing the existing product mix. The businesses should be aware of where in the product life cycle model does their products lie. To illustrate: Hill (2013) shows that sales are directly affected by the product lifecycle model. Product life cycle include four stages:

- Introduction: When a product is launched and is the focus of intensive marketing and promotion activities.
- Growth: At this stage, the demand for the product start to build up as a direct result of concentrated marketing and promotion. The sales are rising at this stage.
- Maturity: The product has an establish market presence at this stage. This is where the sales tend to stabilize.
- Decline: The product starts becoming obsolete because of market forces or external factors.

By identifying where a product is at in the product lifecycle model, the businesses could make gain significant insights. The insights will feed into the decision-making process about diversification of the existing product mix.

In the case of Al Fakhour printing company, the owners need to observe the emerging trends and keep working on designing/ developing of the new products and services that can help the company to meet with the changing clients' requirements and give them better service options.

2.6 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The extant of the literature review includes theoretical aspects relating to disruption theory; current industry trends in the global printing industry; issues relating to Saudization and its corresponding impact upon the Saudi printing, publishing and media industry; and concepts surrounding product mix and marketing within Saudi printing industry. In this section a conceptual framework will be derived from the synthesis of the literature review.

Literature review highlights the significance for the Saudi SME printers to transition their existing business model towards an “agile business model”. Tenets of this agile business model will be two folds:

- The Saudi printers should realise the potential for a digital model. This will require a transition from print towards digital platforms. Digital marketing will enable Saudi SME printing firms to reinvent their relationship with their existing and prospect customers.
- Modifying the product offering through innovation. This entails rethinking the scope of the business by adding specialised services aimed at adding value for the customers. Current trends show printers globally have already shifted towards mass customization, 3-D printing, and interactive print services. Innovating will lead to further extending the scope of business by offering new products and services such as database management services; customer analytics services; social media advertising and marketing services.

The Saudi government has a pivotal role to play in successfully transitioning towards the agile business model. For instance, Saudization policy will need to be re-evaluated with particular focus on the skills-based needs of IT intensive industries such as printing, publishing, and media. Additionally, the current state of the Saudi education system is in dire need for reform.

Educational reform aimed at developing IT based skills and expertise in the native workforce should be prioritised. Furthermore, subsidiary support to boost local non-oil-based industries will play a key role in enabling SME printing business to create the infrastructure needed for transitioning towards a digital based business model.

Fig: 5 – Conceptual Framework: Agile Business Model (Author, 2020)

The above conceptual framework established links between different theoretical and conceptual variables mentioned above towards transitioning into an agile business model.

Below is a table detailing out the key sources of literature review for this study

Author & Year	Key Arguments	Significance for this study
<p>Looner, R (2004);</p> <p>ECSSR (Emirates Center for Strategic Studies and Research)., (1999);</p>	<p>Analysis of the Saudization policy aimed at increasing native Saudi workforce within the private sector. A welfare state with poor educational policies resulted in an incompetent Saudi workforce. This led to a two-fold phenomenon: Rise of expatriate workforce to drive key industries within KSA whilst increasing social cost resulting from higher levels of native workforce unemployment.</p> <p>Critics of the Saudization policy highlights its incompatibility to bring about sound economic reform as its intended by the Saudi policy makers.</p> <p>‘Saudization and Sound Economic Reforms: Are the Two Compatible?’ Strategic Insights</p>	<p>The aim of the printing Industry is to transition into the digital domain and innovate by adding new range of products and services. These are the requirements of the changing landscape of the printing industry in the wake of technological disruption. To do so will require IT capacity building, skills, and training of a much higher order.</p> <p>The authors point out the flaws in the Saudization policy, firstly by its incompatibility with economic theory. Secondly, by its lack of focus on educational reform and training of young Saudi workforce.</p>
<p>Onn Winkler (2006)</p>	<p>"The Immigration Policy of the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) States"</p> <p>The study is deemed a cornerstone of middle eastern studies. Exploring the long terms labour market trends in the Gulf countries and evaluating the success and failures of the resulting immigration policies.</p>	<p>The key findings relates to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty to generating any long terms solution to the problem of native workforce unemployment in the absence of foreign direct investment. • Highlights there is no substitute for pre-training the

		<p>workforce through an effective education system prior to their entering the labour market.</p> <p>The above findings lend support to the notion of developing a competent workforce through educational reform, capable to drive innovation in the printing industry.</p>
Smith (2002)	<p>“Saudization: Development and Expectations Management”</p> <p>Argues from the premise of economic theory on key shortcomings of the Saudization policy.</p>	<p>Saudization in the printing industry is currently deemed low at only 18% of the industry’s total work force. However, there is a need for smooth transition towards Saudization in technology led industry such as printing, publishing, and media. The absence of measure to smoothen this transition poses threat to the printing, publishing, and media industry.</p>
Christensen et al (2015)	<p>“What is Disruptive Innovation?”</p> <p>The article first attempts to correctly define “disruptive innovation”, going on to elaborate on types of disruptions which are possible in any given market.</p> <p>Critical evaluation of types of innovation with a distinction made been “sustainable innovation” and “disruptive innovation”.</p>	<p>The key findings enable to gain a sense of how to use disruption theory when formulating strategic choices towards technology-based disruptions.</p> <p>In this regard, strategic decisions informed by disruption theory in the Saudi printing industry could be made more targeted to the aims and objectives of individual businesses.</p>

	<p>Strategic responses are driven by the choice of innovation strategy and other factors such as player's current position in the market.</p>	
<p>Drupa Global Insights Report (2014)</p>	<p>“Drupa Global Insights report – The Impact of the Internet on Print”</p> <p>A global study into the printing industry to elicit current industry developments and trends.</p> <p>The study highlights the impact of the internet upon the global printing industry from a quantitative and qualitative perspective.</p> <p>Key performance indicators relating to the adoption technology in the global printing industry are quantified.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An understanding of the potential gaps in the Saudi printing industry in comparison to the global printing industry. • Shift to technology-based products and services such as Variable Data Print (VDP) in the wake of hyper customization trends. • Offers scalable solutions for SME printing firms to drive growth.
<p>Konica Minolta Report (2019)</p>	<p>Latest Print Industry Trends</p> <p>The report summarizes the historical rise of the digital based new media platforms.</p> <p>Key Highlights of the report include:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The report provides empirical evidence on the rise of the digital based platforms in the printing industry.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunities and challenges posed by technology for printers. • Need for adopting business models to better incorporate digital media platform. • Guidelines towards transitioning into digital print 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The report also provides practical steps for the SME printing firms looking to transition into the digital
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2.7 CONCLUSION

Based on the above study and evaluation of facts, the discussion can be summarized as the printing sectors in Saudi Arabia hold a developing in a steady manner and beholds a great potential for the future. As the Middle East and Northern Africa market is emerging as a hub for trade and business activities, there are great opportunities for printing companies in this region. Though, the earlier pace of progress of Saudi Arabian business and industrial sector has been suffering due to many reasons such as corruption, the lack of government support, social barriers, and traditional ways of doing business. But now the scenario is changing. The government administration is determined to make the economy more attractive for investment and development activities. As the results, the industrial sector, including print and packaging has a bigger dimension opened for progress.

The facts highlight that the Saudi Arabian printing industry is being influenced by the technology development and digitization in both the positive and adverse manners. Technical advancement and innovation ideas have facilitated the companies to generate better products

while meeting with international quality standards, cost efficiency due to fewer requirements of time and labour and accessing new markets and clients. At the same time, the popularity of internet has posed some serious threats to the traditional printing industry where the publication and the traditional advertising sectors have been affected very negatively and are almost fighting for their survival. Forced to find new ways, the Saudi Arabian printing industry is now focusing the packaging sectors. With the adoption of the latest printing technologies, the outsourcing of skilled labours and technicians and latest management practices, the companies are making ways to find new markets and clients as well. The industry needs to be restructured also at the same time while bringing more investment in this sector, providing additional fundamental reforms, reducing barriers in business, and paying serious attention towards research and development activities.

The situation of medium scale printing companies is specifically considerable here as they are striving to provide quality printing services to customers while coping up with both traditional and modern ways of business operations. The middle sized segment of the printing industry needs to redesign their strategies as the theories of marketing mix analysis and product mix analysis can help them to figure out more promising plans to not only secure their existence in the tough market conditions but also to attain the new level of sales and profitability. The modern-day managerial practices such as aggressive marketing, value added services to clients, attention towards customer satisfaction and futuristic approach will certainly prove supportive to the printing companies in Saudi Arabia.

3 CHAPTER 3: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

Selection of suitable methods for a research plays a significant character in accomplishing a business research project in a good way. It leads the research study in the right direction; identify and implement suitable research theories; collect all the required data effectively; and make sure about the adequacy analysis of data. Furthermore, this chapter is critical in ensuring research objectives as defined in the first chapter are met. This chapter discusses the justification of appropriate research aspects such as philosophy, approaches, strategy, design, methods of data collection, and data analysis techniques. Furthermore, the researcher also discusses the reason behind the choice of a method over others. The researcher considered the research onion to select appropriate methods for the inquiry. The below figure summarizes the research onion:

Figure 6 Research Onion (Source: Oriesek, 2004).

It is clear from the above figure that research strategies such as grounded theory, survey, case study, experimental, and action research, research approaches including inductive and deductive, research philosophy such as positivism and phenomenology, and data collection methods such as sampling, observation, secondary data, interviews, and questionnaire are important aspects of research methodology. In the sections below several choices linked with research methods will be discussed. Justifications will be provided for the most appropriate methods for addressing the research question and objectives.

3.2 PHILOSOPHY OF RESEARCH

The meaning of research philosophy in a study presents to the beliefs of researcher regarding the collection, analysis, and presentation of data in a specific way. Saunders et al. (2009) defined that research philosophies can be interpretivism, positivism, realism, pragmatism, subjectivism, etc (Collins, 2010). The selection of a research philosophy for the research suggests that the researcher accepted some assumptions to consider the world. The consideration of these assumptions is also required for the researcher in selecting an appropriate research strategy.

3.2.1 Interpretive Research Philosophy

Tenets of the interpretive research philosophy are based upon understanding the phenomenon from a subjective perspective. It also involves observations that are subjective and qualitative in nature (Carson, 2001). From the perspective of this theory, it is essential for the researcher to understand the social world of the research participants. It is the reason that interpretivist researchers are generally interdependent with their research that is subjective in a true way (Wilson, 2014). Moreover, in some situations, researchers may also observe the participants while working with them. It shows that the researcher of this philosophy can have both collaborative and participatory view. In addition to this, this research philosophy is also based

on inductive approach, going from observation to theory (Allison, 2002). The researchers following this theory also consider the world as complex and open to interpretation. Moreover, the reading of determinations can result in the issues associated with the dependability.

3.2.2 Positivist Research Philosophy

In contrast to the interpretive research philosophy, tenets of positivist philosophy lies in viewing the research from a truly objective perspective. Thus, it is carried out by maintaining specific and targeted interaction with the research participants. The author of this philosophy also believes that the research must be carried out in a scientific nature whilst following a strict set of pre-defined guidelines (Wilson, 2014). This philosophy is based on a deductive approach going from theory to observation. Additionally, proponents of positivist philosophy will strive for the generalizability of their findings to the entire population. This tendency towards generalizing the findings is derived from quantifiable analysis approach instead of qualitative (Allison, 2002). Moreover, due to its highly structured approach, the positivist research is likely to produce a high level of reliability of results.

3.2.3 Pragmatism Research Philosophy

Pragmatist research philosophy can be defined as being midway between the interpretivist and positivist research philosophies (Ahmed, Opoku, and Aziz, 2016). The researchers following this philosophy consider the research problem as central and use all approaches to understand the problem. These researchers also focus on 'what and how' of the research problem (Collins, 2010). In addition, pragmatism is considered as the paradigm that provides the fundamental research framework for mixed methods research.

3.2.4 Justification of Research Philosophy

This research is based on pragmatist research philosophy. The justification for choosing a pragmatist research philosophy is that researcher focuses on the 'what and how' of the research

issue. For example, the researcher emphasizes to examine how internet influences printing firm's profitability and overall business performance. In addition, the researcher also focuses on what to measure to assess the impact of internet on the printing firm's profitability and growth performance. In addition to this, as this research is based on mixed method, the use of this philosophy assisted the researcher to create a suitable research framework (Ahmed, Opoku, and Aziz, 2016). Moreover, it is also helpful to apply both interpretive and positivist research philosophies for this study. In this, as a part of interpretive research philosophy, the researcher considered the views of the participants that are effective to answer the question how internet influences printing firms' performance. The use of this philosophy also enables the researcher to interpret different views and opinions about the impact of internet on printing industry and provide valid research outcomes (Collins, 2010). At the same time, as a part of positivist philosophy, the researcher collects wide range of quantitative data so that reliability towards the qualitative data can be enhanced. In this way, the pragmatist philosophy guided the researcher to organize this study in the right direction so that the main research questions can be answered effectively.

3.3 RESEARCH APPROACH

To successfully complete a research, it is necessary that the researchers have an awareness of the research approaches. There are two main types of research approaches including inductive and deductive that could be utilized to select and justify suitable research techniques and data collection methods for a research. A researcher must consider various factors before selecting a suitable research approach. For example, the use of deductive approach may be useful in the case, where the researcher has interest to evaluate the robustness of a current theory' (Gratton and Jones, 2010). On the other hand, in the case, when the area is relatively new or under-

researched and the researcher wants to explain a phenomenon, the use of inductive approach is appropriate.

In addition, time and resources are also other important factors because inductive research requires more resources and more time as compared to the deductive approach (Anderson, 2004). Moreover, deductive approach is less risky than inductive approach due to focus on existing theories. The below section discusses the different relationship with the theories of the two approaches:

3.3.1 Inductive Research Approach

Inductive approach is related with theory building processes and thus, it involves search and observation into the relationship between the actions and meanings of participants. Additionally, in this approach, without prior assumption about measurement and categorisation, data is gathered (Anderson, 2004). Moreover, as the researcher emphasizes to understand the internal logic and human actions' purposive nature, the situation context is incorporating into the analysis process. Lastly, the research outcomes are based on suggesting a credible explanation of behaviours that have been observed (Engel and Schutt, 2009).

3.3.2 Deductive Research Approach

In contrast to inductive approach, deductive research is associated with theory testing and involves the formulation of hypothesis. In this, hypotheses are operationalised in a way that the involved variables can be recognized and measured in an objective way (Anderson, 2004). After this, data is gathered and furthermore, the collected data is used to test the hypothesis to define their reality (Engel and Schutt, 2009). Lastly, the research outcomes emphasize to modify or to confirm the theory from which the hypothesis were derived.

3.3.3 Justification of Research Approach

A combination of both inductive and deductive approaches are utilized by the researcher. The key justification for utilising both the approaches is that on one hand, the researcher wants to measure the phenomenon or research problem numerically and on the other hand, he is also concerned with the views and explanations of the individuals about what is happening (Gratton and Jones, 2010). In addition, inductive research is also suitable with this study as the researcher thinks that the truth is different for everyone in the context of the impact of internet of printing firms in Saudi Arabia. Thus, inductive approach guided the researcher to investigate meanings and perceptions about the internet's influence on printing industry.

At the same time, to confirm the employment of both qualitative and quantitative research methods, the use of both approaches is also beneficial for this study. In this, the utilization of inductive approach supported the author to collect qualitative data while deductive approach assisted in gathering numerical data (Steen, 2007). For the inductive approach, the researcher conducted in-depth interviews to learn about the internet on the firm's performance and effectiveness of current product mix elements. At the same time, a close-ended questionnaire was developed and sent to the selected participants to define the relationships that were identified through the inductive research process (Engel and Schutt, 2009).

Overall, the above discussed factors justify the use of both approaches for the researcher to complete this research in a fruitful manner.

3.4 RESEARCH STRATEGY

Another important aspect while selecting suitable methodologies before starting a new research is to think about the optimal research strategy. Loenen (2006) defined five different research strategies including surveys, experiments, histories, case study, and archival analyses. It is

essential for the researcher to select and use a suitable strategy for the inquiry. Wemken and Eckert (2007) defined various situations on which the selection of a suitable research strategy depends (See below figure). The first situation is research question. For instance, when the researcher emphasizes on different questions including who, where, what, how much, and how many, then the use of survey strategy is suitable. In addition, for how and why questions, experiment and case study strategy are suitable. History research strategy also emphasizes on how and why questions while archival analysis focus on who, what, how, and where questions.

Form of Research Question	Requires Control of Behavioural Events?	Focuses on Contemporary Events?	Strategy
how, why?	yes	yes	Experiment
who, what, where, how many, how much?	no	yes	Survey
who, what, where, how many, how much?	no	yes / no	Archival Analysis
how, why?	no	no	History
how, why?	no	yes	Case Study

Figure 7 Relevant Circumstances for Different Research Strategies

(Source: Wemken and Eckert, 2007)

In addition, focus on contemporary or historical events and extent of control a researcher has over the behavioural events are other factors that helps in the selection of a suitable research strategy. For instance, if the researcher has control of behavioural events and the study focuses on contemporary events, the use of experiment strategy is suitable. On the other hand, if the research neither focus on contemporary events nor has controls of behavioural events, the use of history strategy is beneficial (Wemken and Eckert, 2007). Moreover, if the researcher has no control of behavioural events and focus on current events and issues, the use of survey, case study, and archival analysis can be beneficial.

3.4.1 Justification for Research Strategy

This study utilizes a combination of survey and case study research strategy. Both these strategies are suitable for this study because firstly, the researcher wants to answer questions such as what the impact of internet on printing products is, how much internet affected printing businesses, and why printing businesses are affected through internet (Wemken and Eckert, 2007). At the same time, the research issue also does not require control of behavioural events; it is the reason that the use of survey and case study strategies are suitable for the research instead of experiment and other strategies. Lastly, the research focus is also on contemporary issue as the researcher emphasizes to know about the influence of advancement in technology or increasing use of internet on printing firms' performance (Wemken and Eckert, 2007). Additionally, the consideration of product mix of printing firms in Saudi Arabia also leads to the use of case study and survey as the main research strategies.

3.5 RESEARCH DESIGN

3.5.1 Qualitative Research Design

The use of qualitative research design is related with in-depth understanding of subjective phenomenon. The main emphasize of qualitative design is to recognize the deeper meanings of specific human experiences in order to provide more robust theoretical observations that cannot be counted and measured in numbers with ease (Rubin and Babbie, 2007). Qualitative approach is helpful to understand and define the reasons behind the research issue.

Qualitative research designs go from general to specific as at first, it includes the collection of data, interpretation of experiences, data analysis and presenting conclusions so that main research aim, and objectives can be attained. To gather adequate data for a qualitative study, the main data collection techniques include observations, in-depth interviews, content analysis,

focus group, field notes, and artefacts (Blery, 2014). In addition, this design also considers small sample size so that wide range of information can be collected from the participants. Additionally, the main terminologies used under a qualitative study are meaningfulness, inductive approach, and informants (Monsen and Horn, 2007).

3.5.2 Quantitative Research Design

In contrary to qualitative research design, quantitative design concentrates on gathering data that could be collected and analysed in numbers. It also emphasizes on providing more exact and generalizable findings through the application of statistical techniques (Al-Busaidi, 2008). Additionally, in the case, where researchers want to support that a cause creates an effect in general, the use of quantitative design is beneficial.

In contrast with qualitative research design, quantitative research design goes from specific to general. Under quantitative research design, theories could be tested; previous research studies are critiqued and furthermore, based on the results and theoretical framework, hypothesis are developed (Riasi, 2015). In addition, the developed hypothesis guides the data collection process and analyses technique. Lastly, data is analysed based on the hypothesis and theories are confirmed or rejected to draw relevant conclusions.

The main data collection techniques under a quantitative research include experiments and survey. Additionally, sample size also a significant role in determining the statistical significance of the study. It is the reason that researchers predetermine the sample size and generally selects large enough sample sizes for the purpose of establishing statistical significance and generalizability of the study. The below figure summarizes qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methodologies:

Figure 8 Qualitative, Quantitative and Mixed Approach

(Source: Newman and Benz, 1998)

Through the above figure, Newman, and Benz (1998) presented a qualitative and quantitative model, which is effective to understand the interrelationship for the use of both the methods to conduct a scientific or business enquiry. It is clear from this model that quantitative approach is related with theory testing process and it also starts with a theory. Additionally, it is also found that quantitative study is based on deductive approach while qualitative study is based on inductive approach. On the other hand, qualitative approach is related with the exploitation of theories and it is the reason that it ends with theory. The mixed approach is holistic and completes the cycle and helps in closing the existing gap.

3.5.3 Mixed Research Design

It includes the employment of both qualitative and quantitative designs. In the views of Polit and Beck (2004), the implementation of both quantitative and qualitative aspects is beneficial in a research that is based on multi-method component designs. It is because the researcher can implement both the aspects as different components of the overall research, which remain different during the collection of data and analysis processes.

Component designs can be classified in three different ways namely triangulated, complementary, and expansion designs (Polit and Beck, 2010). Both qualitative and

quantitative methods are applied in a triangulated design to enhance the validity by capturing a same phenomenon. In addition to this, in complementary designs, to clarify and enhance the results from one method type, the results from one method type are used. For example, through quantitative results, qualitative results are clarified, discussed, and enhanced. Lastly, different methods are applied for researching different components in the expansion design to enhance the reliability and validity of results (Polit and Beck, 2004).

3.5.3.1 Justification for Mixed Research Design

This study utilizes a multi-method component design in terms of complementary design was used. The research emphasizes on examining the impact of internet on printing industry of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia in many aspects. Moreover, to support the results of both the methods with each-other, both qualitative and quantitative research methods were used by the researcher. For instance, qualitative methods are needed to know about the current marketing mix used in printing industry in Saudi Arabia (Rubin and Babbie, 2007). In addition, qualitative research was also beneficial to examine the marketing mix elements that could be substituted by the internet. The researcher also believes that qualitative research data collected through semi structured interviews is also effective to examine the influence of use of internet on printing industry in terms of their performances (Creswell, 2003). It is because it is effective to know about the views of participants (managers and employees) in printing industry regarding the influence of internet on printing firm's profitability and revenue position.

Additionally, the application of quantitative method through survey process is also supportive to gather fresh data for this study. For the reason, survey with customers was helpful to know about how internet has impacted the use of printing products. In addition, quantitative method is also useful for this study because it helps in gathering numerical data that can be used to

evaluate, count, and compare the wide range of data effectively (Crowther and Lancaster, 2009).

3.6 PILOT STUDY

Essentially, pilot studies are preliminary small scaled studies which are carried out to verify certain components of the main study. Typically, this relates to randomized controlled trials to test the feasibility of the chosen samples. Pilot studies are beneficial for large scale studies which aim to optimize the study design and predict appropriate sample sizes for the full-scale study. Pilot studies are deemed to be time consuming and often expensive given the complexity of the proposed research design (Saunders et al, 2000).

Upon careful consideration a pilot study was deemed infeasible for this study. The justification for the decision to not include a pilot study is two folds. On one hand, stringent constraints on resources make a pilot study infeasible. Secondly, the research design for this study benefits from a mixed method approach. To illustrate, quantitative data is collected and analysed from customers; qualitative data is collected and analysed from experts in the Saudi printing industry. Mixed approach is robust without a pilot study as it enables the researcher to cross validate findings gained from objective and subjective perspectives. Thus, it was deemed appropriate to exclude a pilot study for this research.

3.7 DATA COLLECTION METHOD

To successfully complete a research study, data collection methods play an important role because these support researcher in collecting all the necessary information helpful to solve the research problem (Creswell and Clark, 2011). Primary and secondary are two main kinds of data collection methods. The researcher can either use any of both methods or a mix of both

the methods to gather all the required data and make sure the research aims and objectives are sufficiently addressed.

3.7.1 Primary Data Collection Method

In the views of Wegner (2010), primary data refers to the data that is 'collected at the point, where it is generated'. At the same time, such kind of data is collected for the first time, thus, it is fresh, new, and as per the questions and objectives of the research. The use of primary data methods is associated with various advantages and disadvantages. For instance, from the study by hair (2015), it is evaluated that the main advantage of using primary data collection method is that it helps in gathering specific information related to the research problem resulting in enhancing the data relevancy and control in the context of problem in hand. But concurrently, the disadvantage of this method is that in comparison of secondary data collection method, it is more expensive and time-consuming process (Eng and Keh, 2007).

3.7.2 Method of Gathering Secondary Information

In contrast to the primary method, secondary data is the historical data that an individual, group of people, and organization has gathered for a different purpose (Bryman and Bell, 2011). It shows that using secondary method, the researcher gathers already collected data that is associated with the research issue at some extent. Using internal and external sources, the researcher can find relevant secondary data for the research. Industry and government reports, libraries, and marketing research companies are the main external sources while website of the company, annual report, and other company records are internal sources to gather primary data. In addition, as secondary data exists already, its main advantage is that it can be gathered easily, within less time period, and less budget (Cohen, Manion, Morrison, and Morrison, 2007).

But, concurrently, the disadvantage of this method is that it is difficult to measure the accuracy of data, relevancy, and appropriateness in the context of the current research problem.

Moreover, sometime, secondary data is manipulated by the researcher to attain the results and in such a case the use of secondary data can adversely affect the final research outcomes of the study due to lack of control of the researcher on secondary sources (Cooper and Schindler, 2006). Therefore, before the application of secondary data, it is essential to evaluate the accuracy, dependability, relevancy, and appropriateness of the various sources as per the problem and main objectives of the study.

3.7.3 Mixed Methods

From the above discussion, it is found that both primary and secondary data collection methods are associated with some negative and positive benefits. It is the reason that many researchers prefer to use a mix of both methods to gather all the required data and enhance the reliability and validity of the study by avoiding the disadvantages of both the methods (Beiske, 2007). For this study, the researcher has utilised a mixed approach and gathered data from both primary and secondary sources. The below section gives a justification for the use of both these methods in the context of this research.

3.7.4 Application & Justification of Primary Data collection method

In the case of this research, primary information was gathered by using both interview and questionnaire methods to gather fresh information for examining the impact of internet on printing industry in Saudi Arabia.

3.7.4.1 Questionnaire Design

The main purpose of using survey through close ended questionnaire process for this study is to develop understanding about the customers' opinion in terms of the influence of internet on the use of printing products including books, newspaper, magazines, etc. Additionally, for this study, self-completion questionnaires were developed and used by the researcher. The justification for using semi-structured questionnaires is because they are convenient, cost

effective, reliable, and easy to administer (Saunders et al, 2012). In addition, as the sample size is large for this study, this method is also selected because it is quick to administer and can be disseminated to large number of people at the same time through online and the post. It is also uniform and convenient as everyone completes the same questions set and they can complete it as per their convenience and speed (Beiske, 2007). Moreover, as the questionnaire can be designed in a manner that provides score or data that can be counted, measured, and compared effectively.

In addition, to make sure about the effective design of the questionnaire, the researcher also follows the suggestions given by Flick (2009). For instance, the researcher considered four issues such as well-defined questionnaire focus, wording of the questions, the phraseology, and effective presentation. In this, the focus of the questions is to evaluate how internet affected the use of printing products and to know about their opinion regarding the effective utilization of different marketing mix channels (Etridge, 2004). In addition, some questions were also developed to know about the background of the participants. At the same time, to avoid bias issue and accomplish the study successfully, the questionnaire only includes close ended; scale and rating questions (Zikmund, 2003). A 5-point Likert scale including 'strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, and strongly agree' was used to collect the participants' responses effectively. Moreover, the questionnaire was also built up in a clear and understandable manner to avoid the issue of ambiguity from the questions and enhance response rate (Ahmed, Opoku, and Aziz, 2016).

3.7.4.2 Interview Design

In this research, semi structures interview method is also adopted to gather primary data. The justification for using semi structured interviews is because it is target oriented, address the events context, and direct in real time (Walsh and Wiggins, 2003). The interview process is

mainly designed to attain the objectives including assess the impact of internet on firm's performance and examine the influence on current marketing mix. Additionally, in relation to the research issue, the current literature shows that printing organizations around the world are facing the issue of product substitution due to the increased use of internet. It is because the product offerings are readily replaceable on the internet in the modern context that affect the business of printing industry. Therefore, it is essential to organize in-depth interviews with the owners and top managers of case study printing company (Al Fakhoor) to understand the situation in a holistic manner. To organize interview process effectively, 5 managers are selected from Al-Fakhoor Printing Company.

The use of interview was beneficial to gather in-depth data about the impact of internet on printing industry. It is because interview with managers and employees supported the researcher to understand their perception about the impact of new printing technologies including internet on their business (Zikmund, 2003).

For interview, a semi-structured questionnaire was developed that include both open ended and close ended questions to know about participants' views effectively. The interview questionnaire was also designed in different parts to know about participants' background and influence of internet on the firm's performance.

3.7.4.3 Participants

The research considers the utilization of both qualitative and quantitative under a mixed method approach. A survey process was applied to collect quantitative data, the close ended survey-questionnaire was designed through an online platform called Survey-Monkey. Participants for this study belong to the customer base of the case study firm – Al Fakhoor. The justification for including the participants only from the customer-base of the case study firm is because it enables the researchers to include active customers within the printing industry. Furthermore,

active customers are directly affected through the research problem. It is because internet is increasingly used by many customers for various purposes including as a substitute of printing product. Thus, customers can provide effective insights about the influence of internet on their buying behaviour about the purchase of printing products.

The participants were chosen at random and online close ended questionnaire survey was administered online via Survey Monkey. Justification for choosing the online medium (Survey Monkey) for surveying is attributed to ease of further analysis, efficiency in administering and cost effectiveness of online mediums.

For semi structured interview process the managers from the case study firm – Al Fakhoor are selected. The justification behind selecting only managers is that they can provide better information in terms of the influence of internet on printing firm's performance, revenue, profitability, and overall position. Moreover, they can also provide effective suggestions to overcome issues related to the adverse impact of increasing use of internet on printing industry.

3.7.4.4 Sampling Strategy

It is difficult to organize the survey process and interview with the consideration of whole population. Therefore, it is essential to select a suitable sample from the target population that represent the whole population in order to ensure the successful organization of both interview and survey process (Zikmund, 2003). Both these processes also permit the researcher to generalize the findings from a sample to the population. The use of sampling strategy during research assists the researcher in getting exact, valid, and more reliable information directly from the selected participants.

Probability and non-probability are two effective sampling strategies that support the researcher in selecting a suitable sample size. The use of probability sampling strategy allows the researcher in selecting a random sample from the targeted population (Rubin and Babbie,

2010). On the contrary, non-probability sampling method is based on subjective judgments and in this samples are selected in some way not proposed by sampling theory. Some main non-probability sampling methods include snowball, judgemental and quota sampling (Babbie, 2013).

At the same time, under probability method, there are several methods such as random sampling, convenience sampling, and others that can be used by the researcher with the suitability with the research problem. For this research, the researcher selected simple random strategy to identify a suitable sample. Under simple random strategy, samples are chosen on a random basis from the whole population that provides equal opportunities to the respondents to be selected in the research (Scruggs & Mastropieri, 2006). In this way, this method is also helpful to overcome the issue of bias while selecting the suitable sample size. The key justification for selecting probability method over non-probability method is that it helps in avoiding the issue of bias and select honest representatives from the whole population (Andrew & Halcomb, 2009). Furthermore, probability sampling allows for certain statistical analysis techniques such as regression which are deemed inappropriate under non-probability-based sampling.

The selected sample size for questionnaire is 250 customers from Saudi Arabia, who purchase printing products as well as internet services. The sample size is asymptotically large enough. Initially, roughly 350 questionnaires were sent out. The completion rate for questionnaires is above 70 per cent, which yielded in a sample of 250 respondents. In addition, for interview, the selected sample size is of 5 managers from different departments of the company. Key justification for choosing 5 respondents is that it helps encompass all the different departments within the business.

3.7.5 Justification of Secondary Data Collection Method

Moreover, in order to validate the findings of the researcher, secondary data was also gathered for this study. The researcher gathered the data by using the annual report of the company, financial and non-financial publications providing information about the printing firms, and the government records (Benz and Newman, 2008). Moreover, for completing this research successfully, the research from well-known organizations such as Drupa Global Insights, Konica Minolta, Deloitte, Euro monitor, etc. was also incorporated. The use of these sources was helpful to gather data in numerical form that mainly reflect on the impact of internet on the performance of printing firms. Additionally, books, journal articles, and other authentic online sources were also used for this study (Scruggs & Mastropieri, 2006). The main purpose of using these sources in this study is to evaluate theories related to environmental influences, marketing mix programs, and evaluation of internet in the context of printing industry.

3.8 DATA ANALYSIS TECHNIQUE

In order to successfully complete a research study, the researcher gathers wide range of data and information, therefore, effective analysis of all the gathered information is also essential to reach the final research findings. There are several data analysis techniques including thematic framework analysis, case study analysis, and statistical analysis that can be applied for effective analysis of all the gathered information. This researcher utilizes the mixed approach; therefore, mixed methods for gathering information are also applied to make effective data analysis (Thomas, Nelson, and Silverman, 2010). For instance, both qualitative and quantitative data analysis methods are used by the researcher. In this, SPSS software is applied to effectively analysis quantitative data or the responses of survey process. Under this software, various statistical methods are applied including frequency analysis, reliability test, cross tabulation, correlation, and regression, etc. for analysing the information in a proper way and producing

effective results (Zikmund, 2003). In addition, qualitative data is analysed through thematic framework analysis, in which different priori and posteriori themes are formulated for effective analysis of data. Moreover, tables are used for the effective presentation of analysed data and assist in the better interpretation and discussion.

3.9 ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

The researcher also completed this study ethically for enhancing the validity and dependability towards the selected methodologies as well as final research results. For accomplishing this inquiry ethically, the researcher follows all rules and regulations provided by the university and research ethics committee. In addition to this, the author of the study also collected data by using authentic and relevant data sources including books, journal articles, magazines, Company website, etc. Concurrently, the researcher also presented the information gathered from the participants of both interview and questionnaire process as it is without the intention to obtain aimed results.

Moreover, to involve the participants for both survey and interview process in the research, the researcher sought their prior consent to participate in the study. For this, the researcher sent a participant consent form online to each participant clearly stating the purpose of the inquiry. At the same time, the researcher also informed the participants what is the purpose of survey and interview, what kind of questions will be asked, whether personal question will be asked or not and if yes, what kind of security tools will be used, etc. through the participant information sheet. All these were beneficial to attain the participants' permission to be a part of the research.

In addition, the researcher also described about the confidentiality of the information related to the participants' background and other private information. The researcher also stated that all

the information will be kept secured in password protected computers and laptops to ensure adequate security.

3.10 SUMMARY

From the above discussion, it can be summarized that in the completion of a research successfully, the role of selecting and using various research methods is crucial. It can also be concluded that as this inquiry applies the use of multi-method component design, the use of mixed approach is suitable to effectively address the research objectives. Additionally, the employment of pragmatist philosophy is also appropriate for this study because it helps in determining the link between both interpretive and positive research philosophies. Moreover, it also suits with the use of both inductive and deductive approaches that are linked with the mixed use of quantitative and qualitative research design.

It can also be concluded that the application of both primary and secondary data collection method was also suitable for this study to reach the main objectives of the inquiry. It is because it helps in gathering both qualitative and numerical data, which is beneficial to present effective research outcomes.

The researcher also followed all the ethical considerations to complete this study ethically. Lastly, the use of both thematic framework analysis and SPSS software to apply various statistical techniques analysis methods are also beneficial for this study because these allowed the researcher in effectively analysing the data.

4 CHAPTER 4 – FINDINGS AND DATA ANALYSIS

4.1 INTRODUCTION

The primary objective of this chapter is to present the findings of this research project. In doing so, both qualitative and quantitative data was collected and analysed. Approach for collecting quantitative data, a cross sectional questionnaire was administered to the participants. These participants were patrons of the Al-Fakhoor printing business in Saudi Arabia. The results were then encoded from a 5-point Likert scale and analysed using SPSS software. Qualitative data is gathered through semi structured interviews with the printing media industry experts within Saudi Arabia. The qualitative data from the interviews is transcribed into Microsoft Word.

The interviewees were given a choice between English and Arabic as the preferred language for the interview. Four out of five interviews were conducted in English and one interview was conducted in Arabic. Wherever appropriate, the English language translations are given for Arabic spoken during the interviews.

These can be found in the appendix at the end of the study. Thematic analysis is performed on the qualitative data to elicit insights.

This chapter is split broadly into two parts. At the beginning the analysis of the quantitative data is provided. Basic demographical information about the participants such as age and gender are collected and presented. Qualitative data analysis is presented afterwards. This includes thematic analysis, with quotes taken from the interview transcripts for analysing. To ensure quality of the quantitative data collected, several vetting measures and exploratory data analysis is performed. Following this, results of statistical methods are presented for analysis.

Vetting measures include checking for outliers within the data; normality of individual variables; issue of homoscedasticity and multi-collinearity among variables. Exploratory data

analysis is achieved by using exploratory factor analysis and confirmatory factor analysis. Given the structure of the quantitative questionnaire, it would be prudent to apply Kendall's W test for analyses of the cross-sectional data. It is because Kendall's W test allows to establish mean rank within the Likert scale among the variables (questions). Further, the Cronbach's alpha is used to quantify the reliability for this study. For establishing validity of the study, factor analysis is utilized.

In terms of the qualitative data, doing a thematic analysis enabled the study to elicit valuable information on key themes such as impact of the internet upon the product mix of printing firms; marketing in the digital age; challenges and benefits of the internet; strategies developed to leverage advantages of the internet; improving customer experience with internet.

In the end of the chapter, the findings from quantitative and qualitative study are summarized.

4.2 QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS

4.2.1 Vetting of data for missing value, outliers, normality, homoscedasticity, and multi collinearity.

Vetting of the primary data collected is paramount to ensure the overall quality and usability of the data. Data vetting allows to treat for irregularities within the data. These irregularities may relate to missing values or errors in the data. Within the academic community, there consensus that data vetting process is an important step which should be carried prior to performing any statistical analysis (Bryman et al, 2012; Collins et al, 2010). This ensures robustness and accuracy of the data, making it fit for analysis. So, with this in purview numerous tests conducted to find and treat missing values, outliers within data, homoscedasticity among variables and issue of multi-collinearity.

4.2.2 Missing value exploration

According to Hair et al., (2015), the missing data is a widespread problem, while analysing data for generating research results. There are several reasons for which participants fail to provide accurate information, which generates missing value. First, the length of the questionnaire is a big problem, because respondents feel bored to answer many questions (Bryman & Bell, 2015). Second, the language problems and timing problem generate a lot of missing data, stated by Pallant (2013) in his book “*SPSS survival manual*”. The present research initially exported the paper-based collected data into Microsoft Excel 2013 to check the missing value of the data. The fact is that Excel spreadsheet is very easy to identify and highlight the missing value of the data. The missing values were replaced with the mean scores in terms of avoiding any kind of interruption of the data analysis.

4.2.3 Outliers

By its very definition, outliers are those data points which lie on the extreme of the scale. Defining what an outlier is has been much contested, nevertheless we have statistical methods such as the 2-sigma rule to establish what constitute as an outlier. According to the 2 sigma’s rule any observation is more than 2 standard deviation away from the mean could be treated effectively as an outlier. Outliers or extreme values have a perverse impact on the analysis, tending to skew the results in either direction. Famous approaches to detecting outliers include Univariate, bivariate and multivariate analysis.

2 sigma rules are an example of the univariate analysis. Bivariate on the other hand focusses on detecting outliers by simultaneously considering two variables. Likewise, multivariate outlier detection technique checks for outliers by considering more than 2 variables at the same time (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007). In this study, the researcher has employed univariate outlier analysis. Treatment of outlier involves data transformation such as log transformation or Box-

cox transformation. These transformations are effective in standardizing the outlier values. However, data transformation also leads to difficulties in statistical analysis later. Since, the data does not have a lot of outliers, therefore it would be appropriate the missing values by elimination.

4.2.4 Normality

The assumption of normality within the given data is an important assumption. Normality refers to the degree to which the data on any given variable follows a bell curve. This could be checked for using several different statistical techniques. The assumption of normality is important because it enables the researcher to apply parametric tests instead of non-parametric tests. Parametric test results are considered much more robust and reliable in comparison to non-parametric tests (Bryman et al, 2013). Different statistical techniques for checking the normality of any given variable in the dataset include – Histograms, Quantile-Quantile plots, coefficient of skewness and Kolmogorov and Shapiro test. In this study, to test for the normality of variables (question responses) the coefficient of skewness tests was utilized. To illustrate, a positive value for the coefficient of skewness indicates positively skewed distribution of variable. Conversely, a negative value for the coefficient of skewness indicate a negatively skewed distribution of variable. A value close to zero of the coefficients of skewness indicate an approximately normality within the variable. Similarly, the kurtosis could be used to detect the peaks and flats within the variables. A positive kurtosis value corresponds to the peak within the variable, while a negative value indicates flats within the variable (Collins et al, 2013). In the table below it can be shown that majority of the variables violate the assumption of normality except for the current product mix; proposed product mix and marketing mix and its significance variables.

Attributes	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	S. E	Statistic	S. E
1. Understanding the usage of the Printed Material	-10.897	.104	1.038	.203
2. Understanding Substitution by the Internet	-.785	.104	-.431	.203
3. Current Product Mix at Saudi printing firms	11.857	.104	348.258	.203
4. Proposed Product Mix at Saudi printing firms	8.865	.104	158.852	.203
5. Marketing Mix and Significance for printing firms	12.857	.104	387.257	.203
6. Scope for adoption of latest technology in printing	-2.897	.104	1.852	.203
7. Response to transformational change in printing	2.857	.104	33.578	.203
8. Challenges of the internet for printing firms	4.286	.104	78.598	.203
9. Industry competitiveness in Saudi Arabia	3.857	.104	71.257	.203
10. External factors – Economical, Social, Technological impacting printing industry	1.537	.104	38.145	.203
11. Strategies to minimize Risk and Challenges of internet for printing firms	-2.864	.104	.786	.203

Table 5. 1 Kolmogorov and Shapiro checking for the normality within the dataset

4.2.5 Homoscedasticity

The issue of homoscedasticity within the data is another key assumption in the data vetting process. Homoscedasticity within the data indicates that the dependent variable has a uniform

variance along the independent variables. Converse to homoscedasticity is heteroscedasticity, where the dependent variables are concentrated unevenly along the independent variables (Bryman et al, 2012). This leads to erroneous results in the analysis of the data. Several statistical tests are available to check for homoscedasticity within the data. This study utilizes the Levine's test to confirm homoscedasticity. The results of the Levine's test show the P values to be significant for most variables. P values for variables such as current product mix; proposed product mix and marketing mix and its significance all showed corresponding P values smaller than 0.05. This finding indicates to the issue of heteroscedasticity being present in most variables.

4.2.6 Multicollinearity

Multicollinearity is another issue in the data vetting process which needs to be tested for. Multicollinearity is said to occur in cases where independent variables are shown to be highly correlated to one another. This leads to a perverse impact on the statistical analysis as clear differences between cause and impact of independent variables becomes difficult to establish (Speigelhalter, 2014). To check for multicollinearity within data multiple statistical techniques are available such as Pearson-Neymann correlational test and Variance inflation factor (VIF). Pearson-Neymann correlation test look to establish a value between negative to positive one between one. Values close to negative one indicates strong negative correlation, conversely values between positive one indicates positive correlation between variables. Values close to zero indicate no or weak correlation. Likewise, Variance inflation factor values must be less than 10 with t-values greater than 0.10 to establish no co-linearity between variables. This research utilized a simple linear regression model to demonstrate insignificant levels of co-linearity between independent variables. Table below demonstrate such.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient	Standardized Coefficient	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics		
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	0.896	.0589		3.672	.000		
Understanding the usage of the Printed Material	1.258	.020	1.056	14.587	.000	.759	1.258
Understanding Substitution by the Internet	.3247	0.24	.426	2.221	.054	.256	1.657
Current Product Mix at Saudi printing firms	-1.258	0.26	-1.115	.726	.058	.257	1.578
Proposed Product Mix at Saudi printing firms	.3167	0.24	.527	3.265	.068	.357	1.587
Marketing Mix and Significance for printing firms	.0125	0.25	0.212	4.839	.000	.159	1.367
Scope for adoption of latest technology in printing	-1.358	0.23	-1.004	-3.357	.000	.864	1.957
Response to transformational change in printing	0.236	0.240	0.365	-4.357	.000	.267	1.738
Challenges of the internet for printing firms	2.024	0.018	4.025	-9.36	.000	.258	1.967

Industry competitiveness in Saudi Arabia	.248	0.012	.354	-2.025	.000	.968	1.367
External factors – Economical, Social, Technological impacting printing industry	3.258	0.24	4.258	0.487	.000	.587	1.859
Strategies to minimize Risk and Challenges of internet for printing firms	0.258	0.17	0.358	7.028	.000	.941	1.637

Table 5. 2 Linear regression model

4.2.7 Exploration of Data

Following the vetting of the data, the data was explored using a two-step analysis process. Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and Exploratory factor analysis are detailed below for this study.

4.2.7.1 Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

Studies involving the use of a cross sectional questionnaire to collect quantitative data are known to benefit from exploratory factor analysis (Bryman et al, 2013; Collins et al, 2012). An exploratory factor analysis allows the researcher to evaluate the individual item (question) which are essential to the overall construct of the research design and conceptual design.

To establish the adequacy of the sample collected for this study a Bartlett's test is used. The Bartlett's test helps in determining the KMO values used to establish adequacy of the chosen

sample. Bartlett's tests yielding values below 0.05 are deemed as adequate (Bryman et al, 2013). On the other hand, the KMO value of the test should be well above 0.05 for the sample to be deemed adequate. Upon conducting the Bartlett's test for this study, the KMO values came up well above 0.05. The actual KMO value for this study is 0.789. The KMO value is also statistically significant as the p-value came below 0.05. Therefore, upon successful completion of the EFA, the study progressed to conducting a confirmatory factor analysis.

KMO and Bartlett's Tests

<i>KMO & Bartlett's Test</i>		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.789
	<i>Approx. Chi-Square</i>	34274.259
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	<i>DF.</i>	1024
	<i>Sig.</i>	0.000

Table 5. 3 Exploratory factor analysis (EFA)

4.2.7.2 Confirmatory Factor Analysis

A confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) is the next step in testing the robustness of the conceptual framework used within the research design. The significance of a confirmatory factor analysis is that it enables the researcher to establish the significance of each item (question) within the conceptual framework of the research (Pallant, 2010). For the overall conceptual framework to be deemed robust for the study, the individual values of each question in the cross-sectional questionnaire must be well above 0.05. Upon conducting the confirmatory factor analysis, it was found that all questions yielded values above 0.05 for this study. Considering such findings, the confirmatory factor analysis is deemed successful for this study.

Factor Loadings												
Item		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1.	Underst anding the usage of the Printed Material											
1.1		0.725										
1.2		0.753										
1.3		0.689										
1.4		0.857										
1.5		0.715										
2	Underst anding Substitut ion by the Internet											
2.1			0.657									
2.2			0.598									
2.3			0.758									
2.4			0.719									
2.5			0.634									
3	Current Product Mix at Saudi printing firms											
3.1				0.725								
3.2				0.746								
3.3				0.719								
3.4				0.958								
3.5				0.678								
4	Propose d Product Mix at Saudi printing firms											
4.1					0.478							
4.2					0.759							
4.3					0.714							

4.4					0.736						
4.5					0.718						
5	Marketing Mix and Significance for printing firms										
5.1						0.788					
5.2						0.700					
5.3						0.687					
5.4						0.714					
5.5						0.703					
6	Scope for adoption of latest technology in printing										
6.1							0.749				
6.2							0.716				
6.3							0.763				
6.4							0.610				
6.5							0.641				
7	Response to transformational change in printing										
7.1								0.725			
7.2								0.697			
7.3								0.634			
7.4								0.718			
7.5								0.533			
8	Challenges of the internet for printing firms										
8.1									0.725		
8.2									0.789		
8.3									0.716		

8.4									0.724			
8.5									0.716			
9	Industry competitiveness in Saudi Arabia											
9.1										0.698		
9.2										0.719		
9.3										0.746		
9.4										0.726		
9.5										0.749		
10	External factors – Economical, Social, Technological impactin g printing industry									0.713		
10.1											0.638	
10.2											0.846	
10.3											0.833	
10.4											0.717	
10.5											0.469	
11	Strategie s to minimize Risk and Challenges of internet for printing firms											
11.1												0.759
11.2												0.846
11.3												0.936
11.4												0.423
11.5												0.716

Table 5. 4 Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA)

4.2.8 Checking for correlation amongst variables

Several statistical tests could be employed to check for the link between different variables. These tests could involve Pearson-Neyman's correlation test or Variance inflation factor. For this study, Pearson-Neyman's correlation test is employed to check for correlation amongst variables. The exact results for each of the variables is listed below in a table.

Pearson-Neyman's correlation test seeks to denote a value between negative one and positive one to quantify the level of association between variables. According to Bryman et al (2012), values of the coefficient of Pearson-Neymann correlation (denoted by "r") which lie between plus or minus 0.01 and 0.29 exhibit a trivial correlation between variables. This trivial correlation could be attributed to chance and no significant correlation exists between the variables. A strong correlation is suggested by values of the coefficient of Pearson-Neymann correlation above of plus or minus 0.50. This indicates a strong association between variables which could be attributed to cause and effect upon further speculation. The values of the coefficient of the Pearson-Neymann correlation will have to be tested for statistical significance. This is to say, the p-value must lie below 0.05 for there to be a statistically significant correlation.

The findings of the Pearson-Neymann test indicate a statistically significant positive correlation between **"Understanding the usage of the Printed Material"** with **"External factors – Economical, Social, Technological impacting printing industry"** ($r = 0.687$, $p\text{-value} < 0.05$).

There is also a reasonable positive correlation between **"Understanding Substitution by the Internet"** with **"Current product mix"** ($r = 0.487$, $p\text{-value} < 0.05$).

The test also found a reasonable positive correlation which is statistically significant between **"Understanding Substitution by the Internet"** with **"Response to transformational change in printing"** ($r = 0.759$, $p\text{-value} < 0.05$). There is a further association shown **"Marketing Mix**

Industry competitiveness in Saudi Arabia	Pearson correlation	0.749	0.314	0.678	0.000	0.123	0.034*	0.000		1	0.258	
	Sig (2 tail)	0.0698*	0.312	0.489*	0.0354	0.769	0.672*	0.728	0.025		0.257	
	N	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250
External factors – Economic, Social, Technological impacting printing industry	Pearson correlation	0.674	0.322*	0.113*	0.168*	-0.367*	0.452	0.167	-0.467	0.258	0.312	1
	Sig (2 tail)	0.000*	0.000	0.098*	0.423	0.714	0.785	0.758	0.758	0.002		
	N	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250
Strategies to minimize Risk and Challenges of internet for printing firms	Pearson correlation	0.759*	0.001	-0.132*	0.342*	0.637	0.000	0.457*	0.748	0.758	0.257	1
	Sig (2 tail)	0.987	0.036*	0.246	0.632	0.341	0.013	0.697*	0.252	0.698	0.000	
	N	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250

Table 5. 5 Correlation between variables

4.2.9 Reasoning for employing Kendall's W Test

Kendall's W test is a non-parametric used to analyse data which do not meet the assumption of normality (Collins et al, 2012). For this study, the use of the Kendall's W test is deemed appropriate primarily because the input variables do not conform to the assumption of

normality as discussed above. Furthermore, Kendall's W test is useful as it enables the researcher to establish the mean rank of each question within the cross-sectional questionnaire. This is helpful in establishing the usefulness of each question as part of the broader conceptual framework. A system of ranking such as the one provided by the Kendall's W test is helpful in making decisions about the constructs within the research model. Essentially, by establishing the ranks of each construct within the research model, the study could identify influential constructs. Therefore, given the above justification for the Kendall's W test it would be a prudent for analysis in this study.

4.2.9.1 Understanding the usage of the Printed Material

Ranks

	Mean Rank
Weakly/Monthly Purchase of Paper Products	1.56
Weakly/Monthly Purchase of Newspaper	1.19
Weakly/Monthly Purchase of Magazines	4.08
Weakly/Monthly Purchase of Academic Journal	3.44
Weakly/Monthly Purchase of Fiction/Non-Fiction	4.12

Table 5. 6 Mean rank for usage of printed products

The literature review has indicated that the use of the internet for media related purposes have grown exponentially over the last decade. The internet usage has risen from 81 per cent to 91 per cent from 2013 – 2017 (Media Use in the Middle East, 2018). This theme is consistent across the Arab world. As a direct consequence of this is the lowering rates of newspaper readership within Saudi Arabia. It is estimated that newspaper readership has halved in Saudi Arabia (Media Use in the Middle East, 2018). It is also amongst other print-based products are the worse hit by the rise of the internet. Print magazine readership has also dropped from 21

per cent to 16 per cent. Overall, in Arab countries, from 2013-2017, people who looked for news online relatively remained unchanged from 46 per cent to 47 per cent.

The purpose of this question was to understand the extent of the usage of printed material in Saudi Arabia.

Analysis of the “usage of the printed material” in Saudi Arabia indicates the most frequently sold print materials. The results show the mean ranks of printed material according to their sales volumes. Fiction/Non-Fiction printed material is most sold with a mean rank of 4.12. Next to it is the sales of printed magazines with a mean rank of 4.08. Academic journals show an average rate of selling with a mean rank of 3.44. Consistent with the literature review, newspaper sales volumes are amongst the lowest with a mean rank of 1.19. Other printed paper products also scored lowly with a mean rank of 1.56

Test Statistics	
N	250
Kendall's W	0.624
Chi-Square	1535.356
Df	4
Asymp. Sig.	.000

Table 5. 7 Kendall's W Test for understanding the usage of the printed material

The above statistics show a significant consensus between the sample in the ranking of printed material usage ($p < 0.000$)

4.2.9.2 Understanding Substitution by the Internet

Ranks	
	Mean Rank
Internet as primary medium of acquiring information	4.69
Efficiency of Internet over print media	4.24
Online Versus Offline Mediums	4.02
Measure of online subscriptions	3.94
Suitability of online platforms to customer needs	2.71

Table 5. 8 Mean rank for understanding the substitution by the internet

Literature review indicated internet has proved to be disruptive force in the printing industry across the world. In the literature review, Qasem (2015) asserts the significance of the internet in bring efficiency and ease into lives of the users. Alkhaldi (2016) highlights that internet has substituted traditional mediums across several industries such as education. Sigmund (2016) notes internet is well suited for needs of the customers.

The aim of this question was to gauge at the scope of substitution by the internet in the context of the printing industry in Saudi Arabia.

The analysis of the scope of substitution by the internet are given in the table above. The results indicate internet is most likely to replace traditional print media for acquiring information, with a mean rank of 4.69. It is also found that internet offers higher efficiency to its users in comparison to print media, with a mean rank of 4.24. This finding is consistent is with literature review. Factors which ranked low included the suitability of the online platforms for the customer needs, with a mean rank of 2.71. It was also found that online subscriptions to various forms of print products are on the rise, with a mean rank of 3.94. The participants also appear to favour online platforms versus offline platform of print-based products, with a mean rank of 4.02.

Test Statistics	
N	250
Kendall's W	0.514
Chi-Square	2005.035
Df	4
Asymp. Sig.	0.185

Table 5. 9 Kendall's W Test for understanding substitution by the internet

The above statistics show there is no statistically significant consensus between the sample in the ranking of substitution by the internet ($p > 0.05$).

4.2.9.3 Current Product Mix at Saudi printing firms

Ranks	
	Mean Rank
Business adequacy in meeting customer needs	2.79
Suitability of Advertising products	1.89
Adequacy of Marketing products	1.06
Performance of stationary based products	4.34
Lack of product length	4.56

Table 5. 10 Mean ranks for the current product mix at Al- Fakhour.

Product mix is an essential component within the printing business. Al- Fakhour offers various products lines to its customers ranging from marketing and advertising services, printed material such as brochures, pamphlet, business cards and personal invitations, magazines, and journals. In the literature review it is noted that printing industries will need to diversify their product mix by adding in innovative products and services. Printing businesses will also have

to restructure their current product mix to respond to the changing landscape of the industry in the age of the internet.

The purpose of this question was to elicit information about the effectiveness of the current product mix at Al- Fakhour.

The analysis of the effectiveness of the current product mix at Al Fakhour is given in the table above. The results indicate that the quality of the advertising services offered at the firm is not deemed satisfactory by the participants, with a mean rank of 1.89. Furthermore, the quality of the marketing-based product is also deemed unsatisfactory, with a mean rank of 1.06. The results further indicate that participants do not feel Al Fakhour offers a wide range of products of services, with a mean rank of 4.56. This finding is consistent with the literature review to some extent. There is a need for printing businesses to diversify their product offering to meet changing customer needs.

The results show that stationary based product lines are the most popular amongst participants, with a mean rank of 4.34. Business adequacy in meeting the customer needs is ranked as average with a mean rank of 2.79. These results are consistent with the literature review, in indicating a need for the current product mix at Saudi printing firms to be upgraded.

Test Statistics	
N	250
Kendall's W	0.687
Chi-Square	1458.365
Df	4
Asymp. Sig.	0.000

Table 5. 11 Kendall's W Test for current product mix at Al Fakhour

The above statistics show a significant consensus between the sample in the ranking of current product mix at Al Fakhour ($p < 0.000$)

4.2.9.4 Proposed Product Mix at Saudi printing firms

Ranks	
	Mean Rank
Scope for digital advertising products at Al- Fakhour	4.11
Scope for digital marketing products at Al- Fakhour	4.83
Scope for customized 3-d printing products	4.79
Scope for cross sectional deals on product lines	4.38
Scope for diversifying stationary based products	1.03

Table 5. 12 Mean ranks for the proposed product mix at Al- Fakhour.

In the literature review it is highlighted that printing firms will need to remodel their businesses and aspire to offer better product and services to its clients. This will require the printing firms in Saudi Arabia to expand their business scope by creating new products and services for its customers. These new products could be designed to meet the advertising, marketing, and networking needs of the customers. Furthermore, the printing businesses should investigate creating value for their customer through the product mix. This will require offering a range of cross-sectional discounts and add on services.

The purpose of the question was to illicit insights about the prospect of adding new products and services to the product mix at Al Fakhour.

The analysis of the proposed product mix at Al Fakhour are given in the table above. The results indicate overarching results in almost all subsections of the question. The results clearly show that scope of introducing new products and services will be well received by the customers. In particular, the scope for digital marketing product is the highest, with a mean rank of 4.83. In second place there is the scope adding state of the art 3-D printing technology in the pre-press process, with a mean rank of 4.79. Participants also indicated they would welcome add on value

via cross sectional product deals, with a mean rank of 4.38. Scope for adding digital advertising services is also amongst preferred services, with a mean rank of 4.11. Lastly, it appears scope for diversifying stationary based products isn't much preferred by the participants, with a mean score of 1.03. These findings are mainly consistent with the literary discourse which asserts the need for diversifying product mix through technology and innovation.

Test Statistics	
N	250
Kendall's W	0.365
Chi-Square	1524.258
Df	4
Asymp. Sig.	0.000

Table 5. 13 Kendall's W Test for proposed product mix at Al- Fakhour

The above statistics show a significant consensus between the sample in the ranking of proposed product mix at Al Fakhour ($p < 0.000$).

4.2.9.5 Marketing Mix and Significance for printing firms

Ranks	
	Mean Rank
Quality of the product lines at Al- Fakhour	2.28
Quality of service in line with the price of products	3.99
Efficiency of distribution and cost effectiveness	2.14
Regular discounts and advertising of products and services	1.06
Engaged with customers on multiple platforms	1.74

Table 5. 14 Mean ranks for the Marketing mix and its significance for printing firms.

Literature review has shown that in the era of the rising threat from the internet the traditional revenue streams have declined globally in the printing industry (Gilaninia, 2011). Therefore, marketing mix becomes crucial in driving sales and growth for the printing companies. The marketing mix is contingent on factors such as quality of the product lines; cost effectiveness of products and services; robustness of the distribution channels; product pricing; and effective engagement of customers across multiple marketing platforms.

The aim of the question was to draw information about the performance of the marketing mix at Al Fakhour.

The analysis of the performance of the marketing mix at Al Fakhour is given in the table above. The results indicate poor performance of the current marketing mix in place at Al- Fakhour. The results show that the weakest feature of the marketing mix at Al Fakhour relate to inadequacy of regular discounts and consistent advertising of its products and services, with a mean rank of 1.06. Furthermore, participants revealed that they do not feel engaged by the firms across multiple platforms, with a mean rank of 1.74. The quality of the product lines at Al Fakhour shows an average result, with a mean rank of 2.28. The only overarching result relates to quality of the products and services being in line to their price, with a mean rank of 3.99. This finding is stark as it reveals potential for innovation. Finally, participants reveal an average consensus with the robustness of the distribution channel, with a mean rank of 2.14.

Test Statistics	
N	250
Kendall's W	0.895
Chi-Square	2322.139
Df	4
Asymp. Sig.	0.234

Table 5. 15 Kendall's W Test for Marketing mix and its significance for printing firms.

The above statistics show there is no statistically significant consensus between the sample in the ranking of marketing mix and its significance ($p > 0.05$).

4.2.9.6 Scope for adoption of latest technology in printing

Ranks	
	Mean Rank
Scope for mobile based application for printing needs	4.15
Focus of products and services on digital platforms instead of print platforms	4.07
3D printing is better than traditional printing	4.89
Adoption of new technology such as water-resistant print	4.67
Replacement of offline platforms for advertising and marketing needs	4.52

Table 5. 16 Mean ranks for the scope of adoption for latest technology in printing.

In the literature review it has been shown that latest technology is supplementing the potential of printing businesses in new and innovative ways. There has been a rise in integrating latest technology such as 3-dimensional printing techniques and use of technology to make print products water resistant. In this way, technology has disrupted the printing industry and paved way for growth. However, in the case of the Saudi Arabia there is still low adoption rates for new technology (Arab News, 2014).

The purpose of this question was to gauge at the scope for adoption of new technology for print media firms in Saudi Arabia as a driver of growth.

The analysis of the scope for adoption of latest technology in printing is given in the table above. The results show striking findings in favour of adopting new technology within printing.

The scope for adopting 3-D printing is the highest, with a mean rank of 4.89. Adoption of

water-resistant technology in printing is also favoured by participants, with a mean rank of 4.67. Participants also revealed they would prefer online platforms for their advertising and marketing needs, with a mean rank of 4.52. It was also shown that participants would like to have mobile based application to streamline their printing-based needs, with a mean rank of 4.15. Finally, the participants indicated they would like use of digital platforms for purchasing printing-based products, with a mean rank of 4.07. These findings are consistent with the literary discourse. There is evidence to show that technology in printing could enhance customer experience and drive growth for printing companies (Naik et al, 2015). However, the current state of printing industry in Saudi Arabia shows low rates of technology adoption.

Test Statistics	
N	250
Kendall's W	0.357
Chi-Square	1258.325
Df	4
Asymp. Sig.	0.00

Table 5. 17 Kendall's W Test for scope of adoption for latest technology in printing.

The above statistics show a significant consensus between the sample in the ranking of scope for adoption of latest technology in printing ($p < 0.000$).

4.2.9.7 Response to transformational change in printing

Ranks	
	Mean Rank
Preference to shopping online than offline for printing needs	3.96
Obsolete data services offered by printing companies	4.74
Services and products fit well around the customer needs and schedule	2.51
Quality of the reading material in the age of the internet	1.68
Need for inclusion of marketing and networking services and products by printing companies	4.63

Table 5. 18 Mean ranks for the response to transformational change in printing.

In the literature review, Brokaw and Reed (2010) proposed that internet has put pressure on print industry for structural transformation. Internet is being the cause of a migration of print production closer to the source of demand in offices, bookshops, libraries, data processing centres and the like. It shows a different type of transformation, which is directly linked with structural transformation. In addition to this, Stokes, Wilson, and Wilson (2010) stated that changes in trends and customers' hectic schedule also become the reason of customer's movement from print magazines or books to online books and magazines. It affected printing industry in terms of posing pressure to provide quick and accurate and reliable information to customers.

The aim of this question is to gauge how participants are likely to respond to transformational changes within the printing industry in Saudi Arabia.

The analysis of the response to transformational changes in printing reveal findings which are consistent with the literature. The results of the analysis are given in the table above. The

starkest finding relates with the notion participants feel that data services offered by printing firms are obsolete, with a mean rank of 4.74. The participants also indicated they would like to see online store versions of the printing businesses, with a mean rank of 3.96. It was also shown that participants feel the quality of the printed reading material has not remained the same in the age of the internet, with a mean rank of 1.68. It is also shown that participants would like to have printing services to be well aligned with their own schedule, with a mean rank of 2.51. Finally, it was shown that participants feel a need for inclusion of marketing and advertising services by printing companies, with a mean rank of 4.63. These findings are consistent with the current literary discourse.

Test Statistics	
N	250
Kendall's W	0.524
Chi-Square	175690.258
Df	4
Asymp. Sig.	0.134

Table 5. 19 Kendall's W Test for the response to traditional change in printing.

The above statistics show there is no statistically significant consensus between the sample in the ranking of response to transformational change in printing ($p > 0.05$).

4.2.9.8 Challenges of the internet for printing firms

Ranks	
	Mean Rank
Altered reading habits due to the internet.	4.02
Customizing print-based needs via internet	4.38
Lowered pricing of the printing products due to the internet	3.46
Open source online print websites Vs. Traditional printing press	4.98
Efficiency of online printing portals Vs. Traditional printing press	4.87

Table 5. 20 Mean ranks for the Challenges of the internet for printing firms.

It is noted in the literature review that internet has disrupted the printing industry in many aspects. Some of these aspects relate to the cost effectiveness of the internet; efficiency and ease of use and altered reading habits of the user. With the rise of open source (free access) online printing portals such as “wix.com”, the traditional printing press has come under pressure for its survival. The internet has also altered the reading habits of its users, as a result of which users now prefer to read blog styled posts and articles. The ease of the internet including mobility, and quick access allow the user to engage in reading posting blog styled articles at the click of a few buttons. This results in greater availability of blog styled posts and hence, altered reading habits. This presents as a challenge for the printing firms.

The aim of this question is to deduce the extent to which some of these challenges are relevant in the case of Saudi users of the internet.

The analysis of the challenges of the internet for printing firms is presented in the table above. The results of the analysis are overarching, consistent with the themes discussed above in the literature review. The results show that the most prevalent challenge for printing firms is to be

replaced by open access online printing portals such as wix.com, with a mean rank of 4.98. The next major challenge relates to the efficiency of the online printing portals, with a mean rank of 4.87. It is also observed that participants regard online printing-based portal as more customizable than traditional printers, with a mean rank of 4.38. Next challenge is linked with the prices for printing being lowered in the age of the internet, with a mean rank of 3.46. Lastly, internet has also shown to have altered the reading habits of the users, with a mean rank of 4.02. The above findings confirm the major challenges faced by the printing firms in Saudi Arabia are consistent with the literary discourse.

Test Statistics	
N	250
Kendall's W	0.425
Chi-Square	24587.357
Df	4
Asymp. Sig.	0.000

Table 5. 21 Kendall's W Test for the Challenges of the internet for printing firms.

The above statistics show a significant consensus between the sample in the ranking of the challenges of the internet for printing firms ($p < 0.000$).

4.2.9.9 Industry competitiveness in Saudi Arabia

Ranks	
	Mean Rank
Customer switching services in the last one year.	1.02
Availability to switch vendor for increased quality	3.67
Efficiency of large Vs. medium scale vendors	4.86
Extent of online printing of cards/pamphlets/invitations	4.36
Qatari printers Vs. Saudi Printers	1.04

Table 5. 22 Mean ranks for the Industry competitiveness in Saudi Arabia.

The literature review shows that development of internet and technology has reduced interest of people in the printing and increases their power mainly for printing invitation cards, visiting cards, news material, etc. (Cho and Mun, 2000). One of the major substitutes of the traditional printing in Saudi Arabia is the internet based advanced digital technology, which has reduced the business of the existing printing firms. The industry is not at all attractive in the field of printing cards and pamphlets, newspaper, and magazine, due to social media.

The aim of this question was to gauge at the level of industry competitiveness amongst printers in Saudi Arabia

The analysis of the industry competitiveness in Saudi Arabia is given in the table above. The results of the analysis show that participants have not switched vendors in the last one year, with a mean rank of 1.02. However, there is a propensity for switching vendors for increased quality, with a mean rank of 3.67. The participants agree that large scale printing vendors are more efficient than small scale vendors, with a mean rank of 4.86. There is a high extent of using the internet for printing cards/pamphlets/invitations, with a mean rank of 4.36. The participants are not likely to look overseas for their printing needs, with a mean rank of 1.04.

Test Statistics	
N	250
Kendall's W	0.634
Chi-Square	1258.365
Df	4
Asymp. Sig.	0.314

Table 5. 23 Kendall's W Test for the Industry competitiveness in Saudi Arabia.

Table shows that there is not significant agreement among the participants in the ranking of different areas of social responsibility ($p > .188$).

4.2.9.10 External factors – Economical, Social, Technological impacting printing industry

Ranks	
	Mean Rank
Being aware of the carbon footprint	4.18
Technology in printing has become more accessible than it was before the internet.	4.81
Digital products are cheaper than printed products	4.35
Environmental friendliness of printed products influences purchasing behaviour	2.31
Preference to digital products as they save physical space	4.84

Table 5. 24 Mean ranks for the External factors – Economical, Social, and Technological impacting printing industry.

External factors related with technology, social behaviour and environment also impacts the performance of the printing industry. According to the literature review, the end user is

becoming more aware of the cost of printing to the environment, preferences have shifted in the favour of digital printing than paper printing. These shifts have to some extent altered how printing firms operate globally. There also have been social shifts such as increased accessibility to technology in the age of the internet which have impacted the printing industry.

The aim of this question is to identify how external factors such as economic, social and technology are impacting the printing industry in Saudi Arabia.

The analysis of the external factors – Economical, Social, and Technological impacting printing industry are given in the table above. The results of the analysis show that awareness of carbon footprint is an influential factor impacting the printing industry, with a mean rank of 4.18. It is also been that technology in printing has become increasingly accessible, with a mean rank of 4.81. The participants also agree that digital products are cheaper than printed products, with a mean rank of 4.35. It is interesting to note that environmental friendliness of printed products does not influence the purchasing behaviour of the participants, with a mean rank of 2.31. This finding contrasts with the literature review. Lastly, participants give preference to digital products over printed products as they save on physical space, with a mean rank of 4.84.

Test Statistics	
N	250
Kendall's W	0.635
Chi-Square	1368.167
Df	4
Asymp. Sig.	0.000

Table 5. 25 Kendall's W Test for the External factors – Economical, Social, and Technological impacting printing industry.

The above statistics show a significant consensus between the sample in the ranking of the External factors – Economical, Social, and Technological impacting printing industry ($p < 0.000$).

4.2.9.11 Strategies to minimize Risk and Challenges of internet for printing firms

Ranks	
	Mean Rank
Printers should re-invent themselves by Having new and innovative services.	4.35
Printing businesses should add latest Latest technology in their operations.	4.96
Better design of the printing products will Make me use printers over internet for me Printing needs.	4.73

Table 5. 26 Mean ranks for the Strategies to minimize Risk and Challenges of internet for printing firms.

In the literature review it is asserted that printing firm should be looking to re-invent and realign themselves to adapt to the threat of the internet. Some of the key strategies suggested revolving around the capacity of the printing companies to be able to hire new talent; introducing innovative products; adapting new technology in printing; improving the design of printing. In addition, the companies can develop a new product introduction team that has responsibility to design better printing products to ensure success.

The analysis of the strategies to minimize Risk and Challenges of internet for printing firms is given in the table above. The results of the analysis show that participants strongly agree with adoption of latest technology in printing, with a mean rank of 4.96. Additionally, the participants also strongly agreed that printers should reinvent themselves and they would better respond to improved print designs, with mean ranks of 4.35 and 4.73 respectively.

Test Statistics	
N	250
Kendall's W	0.967
Chi-Square	6235.278
Df	2
Asymp. Sig.	0.357

Table 5. 27 Kendall's W Test for the Strategies to minimize Risk and Challenges of internet for printing firms.

Table shows that there is not significant agreement among the participants in the ranking of different areas of social responsibility ($p > .188$).

4.3 RELIABILITY AND VALIDITY ANALYSIS

To find out the reliability of the study, the Cronbach's alpha is used as part of if this project. It is known that values of the coefficient of the Cronbach's alpha when greater than 0.6 results in an acceptable level of reliability (Bryman et al, 2013). If the value of the Cronbach alpha is greater than 0.7 then the study is deemed to be highly reliable (Bryman et al, 2013). A value of the Cronbach's alpha less than 0.6 indicates lack of consistency within the data. For this study, the Cronbach's alpha is 0.786 which indicates the results of the study to be reliable. After standardization of the variables the Cronbach's alpha is 0.875. These findings indicate that the results of the study are reliable. For establishing the validity of the study, the confirmatory factor analysis was conducted alongside exploratory factor analysis. The results are given above.

Table: Case Processing Summary

Case Processing Summary			
		N	%
	Valid	258	96.89
Cases	Excluded	8	0.031
	Total	250	100

Table: Reliability Statistics

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardised Items	N of Items
0.786	0.875	60

Table: Cronbach's Alpha Item Wise

Age	.776
Sex	.772
Q1. Understanding the usage of printed material	.726
1.1 Weakly/Monthly Purchase of Paper Products	.714
1.2 Weakly/Monthly Purchase of Newspaper	.769
1.3 Weakly/Monthly Purchase of Magazines	.728
1.4 Weakly/Monthly Purchase of Academic Journal	.757
1.5 Weakly/Monthly Purchase of Fiction/Non-Fiction	.777
Q2 Understanding substitution by the internet	.776
2.1 Internet as primary medium of acquiring information	.734
2.2 Efficiency of Internet over print media	.795
2.3 Online Versus Offline Mediums	.714

2.4 Measure of online subscriptions	.736
2.5 Suitability of online platforms to customer needs	.798
Q3 Current Product Mix at Saudi printing firms	.724
3.1 Business adequacy in meeting customer needs	.761
3.2 Suitability of Advertising products	.725
3.3 Adequacy of Marketing products	.716
3.4 Performance of stationary based products	.784
3.5 Lack of product length	.739
Q4. Proposed product Mix at Saudi printing firms	.768
4.1 Scope for digital advertising products at Al- Fakhour	.716
4.2 Scope for digital marketing products at Al- Fakhour	.785
4.3 Scope for customized 3-d printing products	.734
4.4 Scope for cross sectional deals on product lines	.719
4.5 Scope for diversifying stationary based products	.768
Q5. Marketing Mix and Significance for printing firms	.728
5.1 Quality of the product lines at Al- Fakhour	.763
5.2 Quality of service in line with the price of products	.789
5.3 Efficiency of distribution and cost effectiveness	.727
5.4 Regular discounts and advertising of products and services	.767
5.5 Engaged with customers on multiple platforms	.734
Q6. Scope for adoption of latest technology in printing	.766
6.1 Scope for mobile based application for printing needs	.714
6.2 Focus of products and services on digital platforms instead of print platforms	.734
6.3 3D printing is better than traditional printing	.794
6.4 Adoption of new technology such as water-resistant print	.785
6.5 Replacement of offline platforms for advertising and marketing needs	.762
Q7 Response to transformational change in printing	.715

7.1 Preference to shopping online than offline for printing needs	.768
7.2 Obsolete data services offered by printing companies	.786
7.3 Services and products fit well around the customer needs and schedule	.764
7.4 Quality of the reading material in the age of the internet	.738
7.5 Need for inclusion of marketing and networking services and products by printing companies	.724
Q8 Challenges of the internet for printing firms	.798
8.1 Altered reading habits due to the internet.	.785
8.2 Customizing print-based needs via internet	.724
8.3 Lowered pricing of the printing products due to the internet	.719
8.4 Open source online print websites Vs. Traditional printing press	.799
8.5 Efficiency of online printing portals Vs. Traditional printing press	.728
Q9 Industry competitiveness in Saudi Arabia	.734
9.1 Customer switching services in the last one year.	.746
9.2 Availability to switch vendor for increased quality	.734
9.3 Efficacy of large Vs. medium scale vendors	.794
9.4 Extent of online printing of cards/pamphlets/invitations	.754
9.5 Qatari printers Vs. Saudi Printers	.715
Q10 External Factors – Environmental, Social and Technology factors	.738
10.1 Being aware of the carbon footprint	.719
10.2 Technology in printing has become more accessible than it was before the internet.	.784
10.3 Digital products are cheaper than printed products	.735
10.4 Environmental friendliness of printed products influences purchasing behaviour	.724
10.5 Preference to digital products as they save physical space	.716
Q11 Strategies to minimize Risk and Challenges of internet for printing firms	.798
11.1 Printers should re-invent themselves by Having new and innovative services.	.742

11.2 Printing businesses should add latest Latest technology in their operations.	.736
11.3 Better design of the printing products will Make me use printers over internet for me Printing needs.	.711

4.4 QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS

4.4.1 Information about the participants

Data	Age	Gender	Position
Participant 1	45	Male	Head of Marketing
Participant 2	57	Male	Director
Participant 3	44	Male	Sales Manager
Participant 4	39	Male	Chief of operations
Participant 5	47	Male	Head of Publishing

Table 5. 28 Demographic information of the participants

The above refers to the demographic information of the chosen participants in the semi-structured interview process. The information shows that all participants in the study are male. This is due high levels of gender inequality in the Saudi Arabian workforce. The participants are all industry experts with an average of over two decades of experience in the printing industry in Saudi Arabia. The age of the participants is over 40 years on average.

The semi structured interviews are conducted with top management personnel at Al Fakhour to gain insights about the landscape of the printing industry in Saudi Arabia. The interviews also aimed at exploring the key themes which relate with the disruption from the internet in the Saudi printing industry. The gender imbalance in the qualitative data is reflective of the

marginalization of the women within the Saudi workforce. Unfortunately, there is no alternative to effectively rectify this imbalance for this study.

The participants are all at senior level managerial positions within the company. There may be concerns as to the exclusion of participants' below managerial level. The justification for this is that the purpose of the interviews is to investigate industry trends and ways in which the printing industry has been affected by the rise of the internet. Only participants at top managerial level have got the pre-requisite level of industry experience which enables them to provide meaningful insights. Furthermore, the employees that are below managerial level do not have experience in respective areas of the business. This makes employees below managerial level to be in-adept at giving holistic insights.

4.4.2 Key Themes within the industry

The following key themes were identified by the researchers and corresponding interview questions were specifically framed around these themes:

- *Impact of the internet on the Saudi printing industry.*
- *Internet fuelled first mover advantage.*
- *Technology driven growth and development.*
- *Enhancing customer experience through technology.*
- *Innovation in the product mix.*
- *Marketing strategy in the new age of digital media.*
- *Challenges and Benefits of adopting the internet.*

Each of the above themes are discussed in greater details along with selective responses from the participants. The themes are analysed in length using a thematic analysis approach. The

results of the analysis are presented under each theme subheading, supported with the responses from participants.

4.4.2.1 Impact of the internet on the Saudi printing industry

In the literature review, it was noted that internet has strongly impacted the printing industry around the world. In the specific context of publishing, the move has been towards online mediums which were traditionally print media (Vines, 2017). In this regard, the technological advancements and particularly the internet has led businesses and perception of the masses to alter.

Participant 4 when questioned “How do you foresee the impact of the internet on your business?” responded:

“The internet has disrupted the printing industry in a major way. I see internet becoming an indispensable part of the printing industry in the future.

.... In terms of product offering, the internet has managed to evolve as a single platform for all customer’s needs....”

Kippahan (2001) has noted that masses in the age of the internet are more inclined towards the digital media to meet their reading needs, such as newspapers, books, and magazines. The internet is unmatched to the traditional printing industry due to its speed and ease of its accessibility. This has had a perverse impact on the printing industry. This impact is resonated in the opinion of the above participants.

Participant 2 when questioned “How do you foresee the impact of the internet on your business?” responded:

“The internet has what the newspaper never did – i.e. – speed and wide reach. In the printing industry, we are now faced with a huge ... huge... challenge of responding to the rising threat of substitution from the internet

.... the internet is already disrupting areas such as readership capturing, retention and marketing function within the print industry....”

The impact of the internet in the printing industry is also driving change and innovation for the printing industry to evolve. Over the years a drive is witnessed amongst printing houses worldwide towards technology. Examples include big print-based businesses such as Huffington's Post which have transformed their businesses harnessing the potential of the internet to reach masses. One of the participants opined which highlight the importance of moving towards created new digital media products and interacting with customers.

Participant 5 when questioned “How do you foresee the impact of the internet on your business?” responded:

“The internet offers a lot of potential for transforming the printing business. These opportunities lie in creation of new digital media products and changing the way in which the consumers interact with our business.”

There is a drastic need for printing businesses to respond to the impact of the internet upon their businesses. In the literature review, Ronte (2001) noted the gap between the managerial and customer's perception of the same publishing business. This gap was majorly exacerbated due to the technological advancements fuelled by the internet. Ronte (2001) asserts that customer's perception towards a publisher's business is most likely based on a reality of three to five years in the past but a manager in the business thinks about the business three to five years ahead. This leads to a gap of roughly five to ten years, driven by technology.

4.4.2.2 Internet fuelled first mover advantage

The Saudi printing industry is relatively new to the advancements and opportunities which are offered by the internet. Unlike western printing industry, the Saudi printing industry is yet to integrate the internet fully and effectively in their business model. This places the Saudi printing businesses at a unique advantage to become early adopters of the internet and reap the potential benefits of being a first mover advantage.

Participant 5 when questioned “Do you think adopting the capabilities of the internet will give you first mover advantage?” responded:

“The greatest capability of the internet is its wide reach; ease of use; and greater it could host. In a nutshell you can reach more people, more easily than more, and offer them more services than you ever could”.

The opinions of the respondents about the first mover advantage is that adopting the internet early into their business model will provide them with the flexibility of developing skills and capacity within the work force. Furthermore, delayed adoption of the internet could not only result in a lost opportunity but also exacerbate business competition.

Participant 2 when questioned “Do you think adopting the capabilities of the internet will give you first mover advantage?” responded:

“To talk specifically about the Saudi Arabian context, there is a very strong first mover advantage for any printing business looking to fully integrate the potential of the internet into their business model.....

.... However, you should not take that for granted as it could be short lived. By that I mean you really must focus on sustaining your first mover advantage as much as you can....”

One of the potential benefits of being an early adopter of technology into an industry relates to the stronger brand image (Al Rehamani, 2015). By being the first to adopt new technology strengthen the brand image and helps in differentiating the business from its rivals. One of the respondents inferred, adopting internet into a printing business would harness improved relation with customers; increased and stronger brand presence; and offer better opportunities to businesses to align their model to customer needs.

Participant 3 when questioned “Do you think adopting the capabilities of the internet will give you “first mover advantage?”” responded:

“The first mover advantage is there in many industries. In that sense, the printing industry is perhaps no exception.

...If you ask me if there is potential for this to be repeated in the Saudi market, I would say so! Ours is a relatively younger market and there is room for a lot of innovation. So, I can say that adopting the capabilities of the internet will reap some sort of first mover benefit in the Saudi market.”

Late adoption of the internet into the printing industry could also have significant disadvantages associated with it. These disadvantages relate to increased levels of competition and high marketing related costs. The opinion of a respondent resonated with this notion.

Participant 4 when questioned “Do you think adopting the capabilities of the internet will give you FMA?” responded:

“First mover advantage by adopting the capabilities of the internet will relate to being able to establish a brand before the competition...

...Entering into the market as a late entrant has a few significant disadvantages associated to it. These relate with hyper competition and huge costs associated with marketing to gain a footing in the market.”

Overall, the respondents agree to there being a significant first mover advantage to adopt the internet into the business. These advantages related to stronger brand image; increased flexibility to develop skills and capacity; developing better relationship with customers; and avoiding hyper competition and associated costs.

4.4.2.3 Technology driven growth and development

In the literature review, it was noted that growth within the printing industry has stagnated in the recent years. This is directly linked with the increasing use of the internet. In the light of this, it is an imperative for the printing businesses in Saudi Arabia to start moving towards developing strategies to use internet as a tool for growth and development.

One of the distinct advantages of the internet is its vast reach and the speed of its accessibility. This could possibly enable the printing businesses to reach out to a wider audience and increase its readership base. Increased readership could significantly increase the growth of printing businesses in Saudi Arabia. One of the respondents opined this in their response below.

Participant 4 when questioned “What steps have you taken to develop strategies to use the internet's advantages as a growth and development opportunity?” responded:

“We are essentially aiming towards modifying our business model which will be a hybrid of the traditional printing press model and new online based products and services...”

...To talk about specific strategies which we have in place to harness the power of the internet we now have restructured our hiring policies aimed at hiring people with the right skill sets in the online mass media domain. We are also rethinking our marketing.

...We also plan on launching new innovative services and products which will be online. These will help us to better respond to the changing needs of our customer base...”

The internet could be used to better market the products and services of the printing businesses in Saudi Arabia. This will require developing specific strategies around hiring talent with skills in the digital marketing domain. Furthermore, as a strategy – restructuring the hiring practices within printing businesses could lead greater potential for businesses in a better position to leverage the advantage of the internet. This is opined in the response below.

Participant 2 when questioned “What steps have you taken to develop strategies to use the internet's advantages as a growth and development opportunity?” responded:

“In terms of specific steps which we have taken to advance our business through internet, I would say we are now looking at training our workforce to enable them to better use the internet for capturing audiences..... “

Investment into the current infrastructure and integrating online media platforms could be an effective strategy to use the potential of internet for driving growth. Printing firms in Saudi Arabia face the challenge of transitioning into the digital media space from traditional print. This will require effort in terms of creating capacity and skills within the work force. This is opined in the response below.

Participant 3 when questioned “What steps have you taken to develop strategies to use the internet's advantages as a growth and development opportunity?” responded:

“...main challenge/threat for us lies in the fact we have not yet been able to transition into the digital media space as much as we would like to. So, to address this threat we have decided to make the necessary investment into helping us transform into the digital media space. These investments relate to restructuring the work force and creating capacity within our work force, so they can perform better on digital platforms..”

Specific strategies to drive and growth and development through internet could include investing in infrastructure needed to transition into digital media domain; restructuring of current hiring policies to create more tech savvy work force; marketing on digital platforms; reaching a wider audience.

4.4.2.4 Enhancing customer experience through technology

The internet has significant potential in the transforming the way businesses interact and engage with their customers (Curwen & Whalley, 2010). In the literature review, it is noted that internet is now widely accepted by the people in various aspects of their lives ranging from education to business. An increasing number of businesses are innovating via internet to offer added value to their customers.

Participant 5 when questioned – “How do you plan to use the internet to improve customer experience?” responded:

“We also plan to introduce new online based applications where our customers can directly place orders with us using those applications. This will make help the customers because it will be quick and convenient for them to place orders and customise them anywhere, they want.”

The customer experience could be enhanced through the internet by investing in the creation of services and products which add value for the customer. Internet could be used to harness vast amounts of data to predict customer preferences and future needs. In this way, the printing businesses could enhance customer experience by anticipating and responding to their needs ahead of time.

It is opined by the responded, specifically in the Saudi Arabian context, printing businesses lack the vision to innovate.

Participant 2 when questioned – “How do you plan to use the internet to improve customer experience?” responded:

“In today’s market the printing firms will need to seek ways to use the internet to improve operational efficiencies as well as creating new products which can set them apart from the competition in terms of adding value to customers.....”

The internet could also be used to improve operational efficiency and expedite the speed of product/service delivery to the customer. In this way, customers can enjoy greater accessibility and at low cost of distribution. To do so, printing firms in Saudi Arabia will need to invest in web-based applications. One of the respondents points out to the lack of potential for Saudi Arabian printing firms to be able to do so.

Participant 3 when questioned – “How do you plan to use the internet to improve customer experience?” responded:

“.... A very small number of printing businesses in Saudi Arabia are introducing newer web-based applications for its users. They have introduced specific services which enable their users to network better using their platforms.... Innovation has to lead the way.”

As noted above, internet could lead to a data driven strategy for enhancing customer experience. This will include analysing customer data to predict customer behaviour. Data driven strategies have proved to be effective for several printing business in the developed world. Specific strategies include use to analytics to build complex recommender system based on customer’s previous purchase history.

Participant 4 when questioned – “How do you plan to use the internet to improve customer experience?” responded:

“We have planned on setting aside a significant part of our annual budget towards building capacity which will enable us to deliver customized customer experience. This will mainly include building data base platforms via internet....

....The data harnessed on these platforms will enable us to analyse customer behaviours and anticipate customer’s needs ahead of time.....

The key to growth in this market by adopting a customer centric approach. Printing businesses in Saudi and globally who have done this have remained resilient to the fast-changing landscape of the industry..... ”

From the responses it is deduced that internet could enhance customer experience in the Saudi printing industry by hosting innovative services and products; quickly respond to changing customer needs by analytics; improving operational efficiency and speed of product delivery; greater accessibility of products and services.

4.4.2.5 Innovation in the product mix

The internet has impacted the product mix of printing firms globally. The impact particularly relates to the lowered costs of products and services for the customers. The speed of delivery has increased whilst reducing the cost of distribution. This impact has placed pressure upon printing businesses to remain profitable and grow as a business. On the other hand, internet has also provided the printing businesses with the opportunity to innovate and rethink their product mix to drive sales.

As noted above, internet is being used to cut down costs associated in the printing process and enabling faster delivery of final product and services to the customer. One of the respondents opined that through internet they plan to deepen the product by adding complimenting services for the customer.

Participant 3 when questioned – “What will be the impact on the product mix and how do you plan to innovate? responded:

“The product mix will have to be restructured through innovation. This innovation will be directly led via digital platforms. We aim to deepen our existing product mix with digital based services that complement our existing product mix. . . .

. . . . We also plan to innovate by cutting down the costs and reinventing the content delivery system. This will be done with a focus upon minimizing the costs associated with our content delivery system.

. . . . Pricing of the new products and services could also pave the way for innovation. We have new devices and digital media platforms emerging into the market each day.”

Another respondent that the product mix could also be innovated by the addition of specific marketing-based services for the customers. These services would offer consumer insights reports and lead generation. Addition of such services will increase product length for printing firms which could be a driver of growth.

Participant 2 when questioned – “What will be the impact on the product mix and how do you plan to innovate?” responded:

“We intend to launch specific products such as consumer insights for our readers, lead generation for their businesses, and premium content and data-based applications. Additionally, the pricing for these new products and services will need to be optimized in a way which complements our existing product mix. This is one key strategy which will prove to be pivotal in driving growth.”

The product mix can be restructured via internet by introducing custom content delivery services for the customer. Additionally, the pricing of the current print-based products could be cut down with the adoption of the internet. This is opined in the response below.

Participant 4 when questioned – “What will be the impact on the product mix and how do you plan to innovate? responded:

“The first strategy is to develop deeper relationships with readers around targeted interest areas . . .

. . . .The second strategy is to tap into revenue streams beyond advertising and circulation. New publishing models will include marketing services such as custom content, consumer insights, and lead generation, and new offerings for customers such as premium content and data-based applications.

. . . .The third strategy is to reinvent the content delivery model (with a focus on lowering costs) and to emphasize a “profitable core” of unique and brand-defining material.”

It can deduce that product mix needs to be restructured and better aligned to drive sales and growth for Saudi printers. This will include optimized pricing of product and services on digital platforms; addition of new services to increase product offerings; and cutting down of costs associated with printing and distribution channels.

4.4.2.6 Marketing strategy in the new age of digital media

The industrial scenario has been completely changed because of the presence of the internet. Not only has the technology transformed the promotion more non-traditional, but more attractive, aggressive, and directive also. According to Baltes (2016) each sphere of promotion: public relation, advertising, direct marketing, personalization, interactivity, and others are causing the fundamental changes to the marketing of last generation. The new age promotion ideas are more consumer focused, practical, affordable, and put big impact over the mindset of the customers. Social media is a great platform to make the audiences aware of a company's offerings and all the other concerned information to all the parties and potential clients as well. It is opined by one of the responds that marketing via digital platforms will enable printing business to better segment their customers. This will lead to opportunity for better and enhanced product offering for each segmented group. Furthermore, digital marketing will also enable the printing businesses to develop a closer relationship to their customers and boost brand loyalty.

Participant 4 when questioned – “What sort of changes in the marketing strategy will you have to make?” responded:

“Digital marketing approach which we seek to develop will be heavily reliant on ensuring customer engagement and interaction with our brand. Ideally, we would like to engage our customers by having multiple touch points for the customer. For example, over the social media, email, apps, etc. . . .”

. . . Marketing via digital platforms will also enhance our segmentation capabilities. Segmentation is important in our line of work as we cater to a very diverse and wide range of audience. . . .”

The internet will transform marketing function for printing businesses. One of the respondents expressed that marketing through digital platforms will enable the printing businesses to collect customer data. As noted above, this will lead to optimised customer segmentation.

Participant 3 when questioned – “What sort of changes in the marketing strategy will you have to make?” responded:

“Digital marketing also has an advantage that it enables to collect and collate vast amounts of meta-data which would not be possible via other channels of marketing.

In one word we really see the future of marketing strategies to be heavily centred on the digital marketing. . . .”

It is opined by another responded that marketing will need to be able to drive up sales. This will be done by introducing new products and services into the marketing mix such as mass customization, database, and analytics services, etc.

Participant 2 when questioned – “What sort of changes in the marketing strategy will you have to make?” responded:

“Marketing is an important aspect in the printing business. With changing times, the industry has really focused on new opportunities to replenish the diminishing revenue streams since the rise of the internet. . . .”

From the above responses a clear theme has emerged. Marketing via digital platforms will lead to collecting vast amounts of customer data which can then be used for optimizing the customer segmentation process. Optimized customer segmentation will help in driving up sales through better product offering.

4.4.2.7 Challenges and Benefits of adopting the internet

The consistent digitization and availability of various options in the printing segment presented by the multinational companies has created a threat of loss of customers in front of the average to medium scale companies like Al-Fakhoor. The large-scale multinationals further offer the comparatively better products at a lesser price. The traditional customers of the companies also move towards the providers of innovative ideas and efficient costs. Alotaibi (2013) motioned that the influence of brand images, marketing campaigns and impressive customer relationship management practices also cannot be denied in the success of firm. Ultimately, the companies must work hard to get the new customers and retain the existing clientele.

Internet has led to the commoditization of the printing products. This has had a huge impact on the sales for the printing firms. Furthermore, in the digital age there is an apparent scarcity of talented people with digital skills in the printing industry within Saudi Arabia. These sentiments are resonated in the response below.

Participant 1 when questioned – “*What, according to you, are the challenges and benefits of adopting the internet?*” responded:

“We are faced with a lot of challenges which are actually a direct threat from the internet. The sales are not what the used to be and now we have greater competition within the market. Growth has been stifled in the face of diminishing sales. Furthermore, the industry is changing quick and moving towards digitalization. So that poses a challenge for us to acquire the right talent for the changing times.”

Consistent with the theme of loss of revenue by printing firms in Saudi Arabia, one of the respondents points out towards the need for creating more technology-based products and applications in the printing industry. It is noted that creation of new products and services will lead to better customer relationships.

Participant 3 when questioned – “What, according to you, are the challenges and benefits of adopting the internet?” responded:

“I mentioned about creating new online based services. This is the need of the hour.

It’s a shame that most printing firms are not taking this seriously. You cannot

compete with the internet as a print-based company alone. You will have to evolve as

markets and customer needs are changing. . . .

. . . . The challenges are exacerbated by the prevalence of the internet. . . .

. . . . Furthermore, there are issues relating to competition within the industry and a

lack of skilled sales and marketing professionals. So, these are the main challenges

posed by the internet in a nutshell.”

One of the participants again pointed out to the scarcity of technology savvy talent within the Saudi printing industry. The respondent further asserted the need for creation of services which can benefit from the speed of accessibility offered by the internet.

Participant 2 when questioned – “What, according to you, are the challenges and benefits of adopting the internet?” responded:

“ You see, the print industry is plagued by lack of competency in being able to market your product. With the rise of technology and digitalization the printing industry has fallen behind in terms of developing competencies which the workforce to harness the benefits of technology”

Overall, the main challenges presented by the internet in the Saudi printing industry relates with the lack of sale of the print-based products and services. The key benefits of adopting the internet include potential for creation of new products and services to drive up sales.

4.5 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this chapter has presented the main findings of this research using statistical inference and thematic analysis. The findings of several statistical techniques and methods have enabled to quantify the impact of internet in the Saudi printing industry.

The results of the thematic analysis have enabled the research to elicit subjective views of industry experts on themes relating with the disruption caused due to the internet in the Saudi printing industry. In the next chapter, the implication of these findings will be discussed, and recommendation will be presented.

5 CHAPTER: DISCUSSION OF THE KEY FINDINGS

5.1 INTRODUCTION

The main aim of this chapter is to compare the results of the previous chapter with the literary discourse on the impact of internet on the printing industry within Saudi Arabia. This study employed a mixed methodology approach to elicit key findings. Therefore, in this chapter both quantitative and qualitative findings are discussed. In the beginning, the discussion on the quantitative findings is presented. This includes the discussion of the main results obtained through the cross-sectional questionnaire by the sample of 250 respondents. The discussion on the qualitative findings include comparison of the key themes' findings with the literary discourse. The discussion is aimed at comparing the key findings of the qualitative data to produce usable insights on the impact of the internet on the Saudi printing industry.

5.2 SUMMARY OF KEY FINDINGS

This research project was aimed at critically analysing the impact of the internet on the Saudi printing industry. Below the key research findings are given upon successful completion of the data analysis.

- The sale of printed products such as paper products, newspaper, journals, and fiction/nonfiction books have declined in Saudi Arabia with the notable exception of magazines. This decline has been well documented in numerous empirical studies.
- The analysis also revealed that internet in Saudi Arabia has extensively substituted the printed mediums. This relates to the preference of the people inclining towards the internet for needs such as acquiring information. Internet has become increasingly adept

to the needs of the people which has resulted in an increase in the number of online subscriptions.

- A stark finding of this study relates to the current state of the product mix offered by the printing companies in Saudi Arabia. The findings point out to the inefficacy of the product mix as lacking in length, unsatisfactorily meeting the customer needs; poor suitability of add on services such as marketing and advertising.
- Another stark finding relates to the high potential of the proposed product mix which includes scope for digital advertising & marketing; customized 3-dimensional printing; and deals on cross sectional product lines.
- The study also revealed that marketing initiatives by the printing firms fail to effectively engage the customers. Furthermore, printing firms do not engage in consistent advertising of their products or offer discounts to promote sales. The efficiency of the distribution channels of the printed material is also found to be below par.
- The study reveals there is a significant scope for the printing firms in Saudi Arabia to adopt latest technology to compliment the quality of their product. Specific measures include development of mobile based application for customers to use; introducing digitalized version of the printed product; adopting 3-dimensional printing; development of new technology driven products such as water-resistant print.
- The study also finds there is a need for Saudi printing firms to respond quickly to the transformational changes within the industry. Specifically, this transformation relates

to the altering reading habits of the customers; need to diversification of product mix by introducing services that add value to the customer such as marketing and advertising services.

- The main challenges posed by the internet for Saudi printing firms relates to lowering prices of the print products due to the competition from the internet; changing content consuming habits of the customers; ease of customizing print online; inability of printed material to match the speed and accessibility of the internet.
- The study also found low levels of customers switching printers. It was also revealed that customers would consider switching printers for increased quality and efficiency. Small to mid-sized printers are at a disadvantage in comparison to large sized printers. However, customer is still likely to stay with Saudi printers than look abroad (such as in Qatar) for their printing needs.
- In sharp contrast to the literary discourse, it was revealed external factors such as carbon footprint or the environmental friendliness of the printed material do not play a significant role in the purchasing behaviour of the Saudi customers.
- The study also showed customers are likely to be influenced by the addition of new and innovative products and services in the Saudi printing industry; better and improved quality of the design can sway customers to use printers over internet for their printing needs.

5.3 DISCUSSION OF THE QUANTITATIVE FINDINGS

5.3.1 Understanding the usage of the printed material

The study found that usage of the printed material in Saudi Arabia that Fiction/Non-Fiction printed material is most sold with a mean rank of 4.12. Next to it is the sales of printed magazines with a mean rank of 4.08. Academic journals show an average rate of selling with a mean rank of 3.44. Newspaper sales volumes are amongst the lowest with a mean rank of 1.19. Other printed paper products also scored lowly with a mean rank of 1.56. These findings are consistent with the literary discourse which highlights the diminishing sales of the print product within the Middle East in the previous decade. The slow down in the sales of the printed products have been attributed to the rising use of the internet-based media, with an estimated rise of over ninety per cent during 2012 – 2017 (Media Use in the Middle East, 2018). The slowdown in the usage of the printed products, particularly the printed newspapers have been consistent across the Middle East. Most notably, reports have found consumption of newspapers has drastically dropped in Saudi Arabia (Media Use in the Middle East, 2018). Print magazine readership has also dropped from 21 per cent to 16 per cent. Overall, in Arab countries, from 2013-2017, people who looked for news online relatively remained unchanged from 46 per cent to 47 per cent.

The dropping rates of the usage of the printed products could directly be attributed to the rise of the internet. In the new digital age fuelled by the internet, printers have found it increasingly difficult to drive sales and maintain profitability. The aberration towards digital media platforms has been well documented across the world (Simsim, 2011). The findings of this study lend support to the evidence presented by prior empirical studies on the impact of the internet on the printing/publishing industries across the world.

5.3.2 Understanding Substitution by the Internet

The study indicates internet is most likely to replace traditional print media for acquiring information, with a mean rank of 4.69. It is also found that internet offers higher efficiency to its users in comparison to print media, with a mean rank of 4.24. Factors which ranked low included the suitability of the online platforms for the customer needs, with a mean rank of 2.71. It was also found that online subscriptions to various forms of print products are on the rise, with a mean rank of 3.94. The participants also appear to favour online platforms versus offline platform of print-based products, with a mean rank of 4.02. The findings are found to be consistent with the study of Qasem (2015) and Alkhaldi (2016), asserting the disruptive nature of the internet for printing industries across the world. This study points out to the mismatch between the efficiency of the print media in comparison with digital media. The printing industries face a major threat of being replaced by the internet-based media platforms. This threat of replacement is fuelled by the increasing adoptability of the internet into the lives of its users. In the literature review it was pointed that internet use is swiftly increasing across multiple domains ranging from education, entertainment, business and so on (Alasem, 2013; AlSaadi 2012; Curwen & Whalley 2010). The internet-based platforms have effectively managed to gain popularity owing to its speed and ease of use for its users (Sigmund, 2016). Therefore, the findings of this study lend support to the prior empirical evidence relating to the substitution of the printed material with digital content.

5.3.3 Current product mix at Saudi Printing Firms

The study found that the quality of the advertising services offered at the firm is not deemed satisfactory by the participants, with a mean rank of 1.89. Furthermore, the quality of the marketing-based product is also deemed unsatisfactory, with a mean rank of 1.06. The results further indicate that participants do not feel Saudi printing firms offer a wide range of products of services, with a mean rank of 4.56. The results also showed that stationary based product lines are the most popular amongst participants, with a mean rank of 4.34. Business adequacy in meeting the customer needs is ranked as average with a mean rank of 2.79. These results are consistent with the literature review, in indicating a need for the current product mix at printing firms to be upgraded. There is a need for printing businesses to diversify their product offering to meet changing customer needs.

Internet as a disruptive force has greatly altered customer need (Qasem, 2015). This is particularly true in the case of Saudi printing industry. The changing landscape of the printing/publishing industry globally has called on for a need for printers to rethink customer needs. It could be asserted that the traditional products and services offered by the printing firms no longer is adept at meeting changing customer needs. These customer needs have evolved with the rise of technology. Now, customers are likely to respond well to added services and products which add value to the personal or business needs of the customers. Product mix is an essential component within the printing business. Saudi printing firms offer various products lines to its customers ranging from marketing and advertising services, printed material such as brochures, pamphlet, business cards and personal invitations, magazines, and journals. In the literature review it is noted that printing industries will need to diversify their product mix by adding in innovative products and services. Printing businesses will also have

to restructure their current product mix to respond to the changing landscape of the industry in the age of the internet.

5.3.4 Proposed Product Mix for Saudi printing firms

The study found overarching results in relation to the proposed product mix for Saudi printing firms. The results clearly show that scope of introducing new products and services will be well received by the customers. In particular, the scope for digital marketing product is the highest, with a mean rank of 4.83. In second place there is the scope adding state of the art 3-D printing technology in the pre-press process, with a mean rank of 4.79. Participants also indicated they would welcome add on value via cross sectional product deals, with a mean rank of 4.38. Scope for adding digital advertising services is also amongst preferred services, with a mean rank of 4.11. Lastly, it appears scope for diversifying stationary based products isn't much preferred by the participants, with a mean score of 1.03. These findings are mainly consistent with the literary discourse which asserts the need for diversifying product mix through technology and innovation.

The findings are largely consistent with the literature review which essentially highlights that printing firms will need to remodel their businesses and aspire to offer better product and services to its clients. This will require the printing firms in Saudi Arabia to expand their business scope by creating new products and services for its customers. These new products could be designed to meet the advertising, marketing, and networking needs of the customers. Furthermore, the printing businesses should investigate creating value for their customer through the product mix. This will require offering a range of cross-sectional discounts and add on services.

One of the finding contrasts with the empirical evidence. This finding relates to the scope for diversification of stationary based products. It was revealed the customers are indeed satisfied

with the quality of the stationary based products offered at Saudi printing firms. This rise of the internet has fuelled competition between retailers with large retailers competing fiercely on price and quality (Beck & Jacobson, 2017). This should lead to a significant disadvantage for small-mid-sized retailers such as printing firms to keep their stationary based product offering profitable.

5.3.5 Marketing mix and significance for printing firms

The study poor examines performance of the current marketing mix in place at Saudi printing firms. The results show that the weakest feature of the marketing mix relate to lack of regular discounts and consistent advertising of its products and services, with a mean rank of 1.06. Furthermore, participants revealed that they do not feel engaged by the firms across multiple platforms, with a mean rank of 1.74. The quality of the product lines shows an average result, with a mean rank of 2.28. The only overarching result relates to quality of the products and services being in line to their price, with a mean rank of 3.99. This finding is stark as it reveals potential for innovation. Finally, participants reveal an average consensus with the robustness of the distribution channel, with a mean rank of 2.14.

Marketing is a crucial component for the printing industry globally as a tool for responding to the competition from internet (Gilaninia, 2011). Empirical studies have shown that traditional revenue streams have declined globally in the printing industry (Gilaninia, 2011). Therefore, marketing mix becomes crucial in driving sales and growth for the printing companies. The marketing mix is contingent on factors such as quality of the product lines; cost effectiveness of products and services; robustness of the distribution channels; product pricing; and effective engagement of customers across multiple marketing platforms. The findings of this study reveal a gap in the market for Saudi printing firms. This gap relates to the poor consistency of offering discounts and deals on product lines. The findings also reveal Saudi printing

companies are poor at engaging its customers across multiple marketing platforms. These findings could perhaps help in explaining the inability to Saudi printing firms to maintain profitability in congestion with the rising threat of substitution from the internet.

5.3.6 Scope for adoption of latest technology in printing

The study reveals striking findings in favour of adopting new technology within printing. The scope for adopting 3-D printing is the highest, with a mean rank of 4.89. Adoption of water-resistant technology in printing is also favoured by participants, with a mean rank of 4.67. Participants also revealed they would prefer online platforms for their advertising and marketing needs, with a mean rank of 4.52. It was also shown that participants would like to have mobile based application to streamline their printing-based needs, with a mean rank of 4.15. Finally, the participants indicated they would like use of digital platforms for purchasing printing-based products, with a mean rank of 4.07.

In the literature review it has been shown that latest technology is supplementing the potential of printing businesses in new and innovative ways. There has been a rise in integrating latest technology such as 3-dimensional printing techniques and use of technology to make print products water resistant. In this way, technology has disrupted the printing industry and paved way for growth. However, in the case of the Saudi Arabia there is still low adoption rates for new technology (Arab News, 2014). These findings are consistent with the literary discourse. There is evidence to show that technology in printing could enhance customer experience and drive growth for printing companies (Naik et al, 2015). However, the current state of printing industry in Saudi Arabia shows low rates of technology adoption.

5.3.7 Response to transformational change in printing

The findings relating to the response to transformational changes in printing reveal are consistent with the literature. The findings also revealed customers would like to see online store versions of the printing businesses, with a mean rank of 3.96. The finding indicates customers feel the quality of the printed reading material has not remained the same in the age of the internet, with a mean rank of 1.68. It is also shown that customers would like to have printing services to be well aligned with their own schedule, with a mean rank of 2.51. Lastly, it was shown that customers feel a need for inclusion of marketing and networking services by printing companies, with a mean rank of 4.63. These findings are consistent with the current literary discourse. Prior empirical studies have proposed that internet has put pressure on print industry for structural transformation (Brokaw and Reed 2010). It shows a different type of transformation, which is directly linked with structural transformation. In addition to this, Stokes, and Wilson (2010) stated that changers in trends and customers' hectic schedule also become the reason of customer's movement from print magazines or books to online books and magazines. It affected printing industry in terms of posing pressure to provide quick and accurate and reliable information to customers.

5.3.8 Challenges of the internet for Saudi printing firms

The findings of the study are consistent with the themes discussed above in the literature review. The results show that the most prevalent challenge for printing firms is to be replaced by open access online printing portals such as wix.com, with a mean rank of 4.98. The next major challenge relates to the efficiency of the online printing portals, with a mean rank of 4.87. It is also observed that customers regard online printing-based portal as more customizable than traditional printers, with a mean rank of 4.38. Next challenge is linked with the prices for printing being lowered in the age of the internet, with a mean rank of 3.46. Lastly,

internet has also shown to have altered the reading habits of the users, with a mean rank of 4.02.

Notably the most prevalent challenge for Saudi printing firms come from the price competitiveness which is fuelled by the rise of the internet. The problem is exacerbated given the huge mismatch between the efficiency and accessibility of traditional print product products in comparison to the internet. The internet has altered by market forces in the Saudi printing industry by offering quick and easy to access products digitally at fraction of the cost of printed products. With the technology boom, open access web-based portals are now providing free content to the user which used to previously be catered by the printing firms. Furthermore, the internet is changing the reading habits of the user. It can be argued that readers now are more inclined towards prescribing to blog styled posts and articles. Prior to the rise of the internet the propensity towards reading favoured editorialized content. However, this is seen to be changing swiftly since the previous decade. These are some of the most potent challenges presented by the internet for Saudi printing businesses. In this regard, above findings confirm the major challenges faced by the printing firms in Saudi Arabia are consistent with the literary discourse.

5.3.9 Industry competitiveness in Saudi Arabia

The study show that customers have not switched vendors in the last one year, with a mean rank of 1.02. However, there is a propensity for switching vendors for increased quality, with a mean rank of 3.67. The customers are seen to agree that large scale printing vendors are more efficient than small scale vendors, with a mean rank of 4.86. There is a high extent of using the internet for printing cards/pamphlets/invitations, with a mean rank of 4.36. The customers are also not likely to look overseas for their printing needs, with a mean rank of 1.04.

The Saudi Arabian printing industry in the global context falls under the category of an evolving market (Alasem 2013). This perhaps could explain the relatively low levels of competition within the industry. It can be argued that the printing industry in Saudi Arabia as explained by the lifecycle of industry model is at the stage of innovation, where there is scope for significant improvement within the industry.

5.3.10 External factors – Economical, Social, and Technological impacting printing industry

The study show that awareness of carbon footprint is not an influential factor impacting the printing industry, with a mean rank of 1.18. It is also been revealed that technology in printing has increasingly accessible, with a mean rank of 4.81. The customers also agree that digital products are cheaper than printed products, with a mean rank of 4.35. It is interesting to note that environmental friendliness of printed products does not influence the purchasing behaviour of the participants, with a mean rank of 2.31. This finding contrasts with the literature review. Lastly, participants give preference to digital products over printed products as they save on physical space, with a mean rank of 4.84.

External factors related with technology, social behaviour and environment also impacts the performance the printing industry. With the end user becoming more aware of the cost of printing to the environment, preferences have shifted in the favour of digital printing than paper printing. These shifts have to some extent altered how printing firms operate globally. There also have been social shifts such as increased accessibility to technology in the age of the internet which have impacted the printing industry.

It is interesting to note that finding of this study relating to the cost of environmental factor as an influencing factor in the buying behaviour is contrasting to the wider empirical evidence from prior studies. This study shows the Saudi consumer of print media do not exhibit a

significant regard for their carbon footprint. There is a large body of compelling empirical evidence which contrast this finding (Ali 2009; Iqbal 2011). Consumers in developed economies are increasingly become more conscious about their consumption behaviours impacting the environment. This has led to a significant corporate social responsibility drive by many multinational printing firms towards moving digital mediums.

5.3.11 Strategies to minimize Risk and Challenges of internet for printing firms

The study show that consumers are likely to agree with adoption of latest technology in printing, with a mean rank of 4.96. Additionally, the participants also strongly agreed that printers should reinvent themselves and they would better respond to improved print designs, with mean ranks of 4.35 and 4.73 respectively.

In the literature review it is asserted that printing firm should be looking to re-invent and realign themselves to adapt to the threat of the internet. Some of the key strategies suggested revolving around the capacity of the printing companies to be able to hire new talent; introducing innovative products; adapting new technology in printing; improving the design of printing. In addition, the companies can develop a new product introduction team that has responsibility to design better printing products to ensure success.

5.4 DISCUSSION OF QUALITATIVE FINDINGS

5.4.1 Impact of the internet on the Saudi printing industry

This study found that disruption fuelled by the internet has had a major impact on the Saudi printing industry. Majority of the respondents pointed to disruption by technology such as television and broadcasting at different timelines in the history of the printing industry. However, the printing industry has been able to technological disruption with the notable

exception of the internet. The internet has strongly impacted the printing industry around the world. In the specific context of publishing, the move has been towards online mediums which were traditionally print media (Vines, 2017). In this regard, the technological advancements and particularly the internet has led businesses and perception of the masses to alter.

The impact from the internet has left the Saudi printing businesses vulnerable to either being replaced or becoming obsolete if they remained unchanged. The crisis of responding to the adverse impact of the internet is worsened in the presence of the gap between the managerial and customer's perception of the same publishing business (Ronte, 2001). This gap was majorly exacerbated due to the technological advancements fuelled by the internet.

On the other hand of the spectrum the impact of the internet within the printing industry is also shown to be driver of innovation. Since the rise of the internet, an increasing number of printers globally have adopted new technological advancements and aligned their businesses digitally (Zawya Thompson Reuters, 2015). However, it should also be noted that examples of such technological innovations are shown to be limited to large and well-established printing houses such as Huffington Post (Zawya Thompson Reuters, 2015). The findings of this study also inferred presence of a drive amongst Saudi printing firms towards digital media platforms and products. The shift is shown to be consistent with the current literary discourse. Kippahan (2001) has noted that masses in the age of the internet are more inclined towards the digital media to meet their reading needs, such as newspapers, books, and magazines. The internet is unmatched to the traditional printing industry due to its speed and ease of its accessibility. This has had a corrosive impact on the printing industry.

5.4.2 Internet Fuelled First Mover Advantage

The study found there to be a potential for taking advantage of earlier adoption of the internet as a driver for growth. This finding is supported by the fact that Saudi printing industry is relatively young and evolving in comparison to the printing industries in the developed world. In this way, it was revealed that a first mover advantage relating to the early adoption of the internet exists in the Saudi printing industry. The finding also revealed poor levels of integration of the internet into the business model of printing businesses in Saudi Arabia at present. This places the Saudi printing businesses at a unique advantage to become early adopters of the internet and reap the potential benefits of being a first mover advantage.

The study found that adopting the internet early into their business model will provide the Saudi printing firms with the flexibility of developing skills and capacity within the work force. One of the potential benefits of being an early adopter of technology into an industry relates to the stronger brand image (Al Rehamani, 2015). By being the first to adopt new technology strengthen the brand image and helps in differentiating the business from its rivals. One of the respondents inferred adopting internet into a printing business would harness improved relation with customers; increased and stronger brand presence; and offer better opportunities to businesses to align their model to customer needs.

Furthermore, later adoption of the internet could not only result in a lost advantage opportunity but exacerbate business competition. Late adoption of the internet into the printing industry could also have significant disadvantages associated with it. These disadvantages relate to increased levels of competition and high marketing related costs.

5.4.3 Technology Driven Growth and Development

The findings have revealed adoption of technology within the printing industry has vast potential for driving growth. This study highlights the key advantage of the internet is its vast reach and the speed of its accessibility. This could possibly enable the printing businesses to reach out to a wider audience and increase its readership base. Increased readership could significantly increase the growth of printing businesses in Saudi Arabia. In the literature review, it was noted that growth within the printing industry has stagnated in the recent years. This is directly linked with the increasing use of the internet (Printing processes, 2017). Given this apparent stagnancy it becomes imperative for the printing businesses in Saudi Arabia to start moving towards developing strategies to use internet as a tool for growth and development. Internet could offer greater speed and access to the Saudi printing businesses in reaching their customers. This could possibly enable the printing/publishing businesses to reach out to a wider audience and increase its readership base. Increased readership could significantly increase the growth of printing businesses in Saudi Arabia.

Investment into the current infrastructure and integrating online media platforms could be an effective strategy to use the potential of internet for driving growth. Printing firms in Saudi Arabia face the challenge of transitioning into the digital media space from traditional print. This will require effort in terms of creating capacity and skills within the work force. The internet could be used to better market the products and services of the printing businesses in Saudi Arabia. This will require developing specific strategies around hiring talent with skills in the digital marketing domain. Furthermore, as a strategy – restructuring the hiring practices within printing businesses could lead greater potential for businesses in a better position to leverage the advantage of the internet.

5.4.4 Enhancing Customer Experience through Technology

This study found that Saudi printing firms have the potential for enhancing the customer through technology experience. This potential is reflected in the accounts of the respondents. It was revealed that specific measures include hosting innovative services and products; quickly respond to changing customer needs by analytics; improving operational efficiency and speed of product delivery; and greater accessibility of products and services.

Findings of Curwen & Whalley (2010) highlight the potential of technology in the transforming the way businesses interact and engage with their customers. In the literature review, it is noted that internet is now widely accepted by the people in various aspects of their lives ranging from education to business. An increasing number of businesses are innovating via internet to offer added value to their customers. Furthermore, it is noted that customer experience could be enhanced through the internet by investing in the creation of services and products which add value for the customer. Internet could be used to harness vast amounts of data in order to predict customer preferences and future needs. In this way, the printing businesses could enhance customer experience by anticipating and responding to their needs ahead of time.

The internet could also be used to improve operational efficiency and expedite the speed of product/service delivery to the customer (Carr, 2010). In this way, customers can enjoy greater accessibility and at low cost of distribution. To do so, printing firms in Saudi Arabia will need to invest in web-based applications. One of the responded points out to the lack of potential for Saudi Arabian printing firms to be able to do so.

5.4.5 Innovation in the Product Mix

The study found a consistent theme amongst the responses which reinforced the notion of restructuring of the product mix to drive the sales and growth for the Saudi printing businesses. Overall, the respondents agreed that the product mix should be better aligned to the evolving needs of the customers. Specific measures included greater product offering upon digital platforms; optimization of the product and services pricing; creation of new innovative services which better align with the customer's needs; and finally cutting of costs linked with printing and distribution mediums. These findings are largely consistent with the literary discourse. Empirical studies have shown that adoption of the internet has led to lowered costs of products and services for the customers (Alfarraj, Drew and AlGhamdi, 2011). In addition, the speed of delivery has increased whilst reducing the cost of distribution with the adoption of internet (Alfarraj, Drew and AlGhamdi, 2011). This impact has placed pressure upon printing businesses to remain profitable and grow as a business. On the other hand, internet has also provided the printing businesses with the opportunity to innovate and rethink their product mix to drive sales.

The findings of this study indicate that the product mix could also be innovated by the addition of specific marketing-based services for the customers. These services would offer consumer insights reports and lead generation. Addition of such services will increase product length for printing firms which could be a driver of growth. The product mix can be restructured via internet by introducing custom content delivery services for the customer. Additionally, the pricing of the current print-based products could be cut down with the adoption of the internet.

5.4.6 Marketing Strategy in The New Era of Digital Media

This study found that marketing via digital platforms will lead to collecting vast amounts of customer data which can then be used for optimizing the customer segmentation process. Optimized customer segmentation will help in driving up sales through better product offering. The industrial scenario has been completely changed because of the presence of the internet. Not only has the technology transformed the promotion more non-traditional, but more attractive, aggressive, and directive also. According to Baltes (2016) each sphere of promotion: public relation, advertising, direct marketing, personalization, interactivity, and others are causing the fundamental changes to the marketing of last generation. The new age promotion ideas are more consumer focused, practical, affordable, and put big impact over the mindset of the customers. Social media is a great platform to make the audiences aware of a company's offerings and all the other concerned information to all the parties and potential clients as well. It can be asserted that marketing via digital platforms will enable printing business to better segment their customers. This will lead to opportunity for better and enhanced product offering for each segmented group. Furthermore, digital marketing will also enable the printing businesses to develop a closer relationship to their customers and boost brand loyalty.

5.4.7 Challenges and Benefits of adopting the internet

This study found the main challenges associated with the internet in the Saudi printing industry is linked with the diminishing sales of the print products and services. On the other hand, the study also found that main benefit for adopting the internet include potential for creation of new products and services to drive up sales. The findings also point out to the apparent shortage of skilled technology workers within the Saudi printing industry. Consistent with the theme of loss of revenue by printing firms in Saudi Arabia, there is a need for creating more technology-based products and applications in the printing industry. It is noted that creation of new

products and services will lead to better customer relationships. These findings are consistent with the literary discourse relating to disruption in the printing industry globally. Alotaibi (2013) in his study has notes consistent digitization and availability of various options in the printing segment presented by the multinational companies has created a threat of loss of customers in front of the average to medium scale companies. The large-scale multinationals further offer the comparatively better products at a lesser price. The traditional customers of the companies also move towards the providers of innovative ideas and efficient costs. Alotaibi (2013) motioned that the influence of brand images, marketing campaigns and impressive customer relationship management practices also cannot be denied in the success of firm. Ultimately, the companies must work hard to get the new customers and retain the existing clientele.

Internet has led to the commoditization of the printing products. This has had a huge impact on the sales for the printing firms. Furthermore, in the digital age there is an apparent scarcity of talented people with digital skills in the printing industry within Saudi Arabia. These sentiments are resonated in the findings of this study.

5.5 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this chapter present forth a detailed discussion about the critical benefits, challenges and opportunities presented by the internet in the Saudi printing industry. This chapter has endeavoured to present the key findings of this study from both a quantitative and qualitative perspective. This chapter has attempted to either corroborate or differentiate the key findings from the current literary discourse. In doing so, the findings have either lent support or contradicted the existing empirical evidence. The literature review is invoked in this chapter as a medium of doing so.

6 CONCLUSION, IMPLICATIONS, CONTRIBUTION, RECOMMENDATION AND LIMITATIONS

6.1 INTRODUCTION

This brief chapter aims at clearly summarizing the key findings of this research, offering key recommendations for small-mid-sized Saudi printing firms in line with the findings of this study. Finally, the chapter concludes this research project by acknowledging key limitations of the study. More importantly, this chapter plays a pivotal role in demonstrating how the research question and key objectives of this were met through quantitative and qualitative findings.

6.2 CONCLUDING REMARKS

The primary aim of this research was to analyse the current market scenario in the printing industry of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia and the risks and challenges posed by internet on the current product mix of printing organizations, mainly because of substitution. Furthermore, the study strived to provide recommendation to the current product mix strategy and substitution by the internet there by creating a sustainable product mix. To sufficiently address the research aim, the study employed quantitative and qualitative research methods. The qualitative research method allowed the researcher to better understand the impact of the internet on Saudi printing industry through the insights offered by industry experts. Specifically the qualitative approach helped the researcher to address objective two (To assess the current market situation and challenges faced by mid-size printing industry in Saudi Arabia), Objective three (To identify the current product mix used by organizations and the impact of internet substitution on the product mix), Objective four (To recommend a product marketing mix strategy for the midsize organizations so as to minimize the risks caused by the internet substitution.).

On the other hand, the literature review aided in addressing research objective one which was to evaluate the risks and challenge caused in Saudi mid-size printing firms. In addition to the qualitative analysis, the quantitative analysis enabled the researcher to further address research objective two (To assess the current market situation and challenges faced by mid-size printing industry in Saudi Arabia), Objective three (To identify the current product mix used by organizations and the impact of internet substitution on the product mix), Objective four (To recommend a product marketing mix strategy for the midsize organizations so as to minimize the risks caused by the internet substitution.)

Research Objective 1 – To evaluate the level of risk and challenge for Saudi Arabian mid-sized printing firms.

This research objective is effectively addressed in three folds. Firstly, the literature review for this research project has enabled to identify the key themes relating to the challenges posed by the internet for printing firms in Saudi Arabia. Secondly, the quantitative findings of questions such as – Challenges posed by the internet enabled the researcher to reach key quantitative findings. Lastly, the qualitative findings on the theme of – Challenges and benefits of the internet, as well as theme of – Impact of the internet on the product mix enables the researcher to gain critical insight about the specific risks and challenges faced by mid-sized Saudi Arabian printing firms. Therefore, this research objective was effectively met.

Research Objective 2 – To assess the current market situation and challenges faced by the Saudi mid-sized printing firms.

Research objective two is addressed in two folds. First, the quantitative findings and discussion relating to several questions in the cross sectional questionnaire such as “*response to transformational change*”, “*Industry competitiveness*”, “*External Factors – Economical, Social, and Technological impacting printing industry*”, “*Adoption of latest technology in*

printing”, etc have effectively enabled the researcher to gauge at the current market situation within Saudi printing industry. Secondly, the qualitative findings and discussion relating have further enabled the research to gain subjective insights about the current market situation and challenges faced by Saudi mid-sized printing firms. Therefore, this research objective was effectively met.

Research Objective 3 – To identify the current product mix used by the organisations and the impact of internet substitution upon the product mix.

This research objective is met in two folds with the help of quantitative and qualitative findings and resulting discussion. Researcher was able to quantify the robustness of current product mix used by Saudi mid-sized printing firms by considering the product mix at Al-Fakhoor. Then, the robustness of the current and proposed product mix was appraised by the 250 research participants who are also users of the printing products. In addition to the customer’s perspective, the perspective of the printing industry experts was also gathered through qualitative findings and discussion of those findings. Therefore, this research objective was effectively met.

Research Objective 4 – To recommend a product marketing mix strategy for the midsize printing firms to minimize the risks caused by internet substitution.

This research objective was met in two folds. Firstly, the researcher was able to effectively analyse the impact of the product mix, performance of the internet, and overall impact of the impact of the internet on the Saudi printing firms through quantitative and qualitative findings. Secondly, based on these findings the research has presented specific recommendations for mid-sized Saudi Arabian printing firms to minimize the risks caused by internet substitution. Therefore, this research objective was effectively met.

6.3 CONTRIBUTION OF THE STUDY

6.3.1 Contribution to the knowledge

Theories of disruption are not new; they have found a pivotal place in business literature as sectors and industries transform due to disruptive forces. The scope and impact of disruption is well documented in the works of Christensen et al amongst others. Christensen et al (2012) note that response to disruption is not a case of one size fits all. In fact, even within the same industry to respond to disruption will vary depending on several factors. These factors include size of the firm, cause of disruption, affected aspects of business, and end goal objectives. In the context of the global printing industry, rise of internet has presented technological disruption for the industry. In the short run, this has created challenges for printers globally. Printers globally are looking for ways to respond to disruption through internet by innovating and adopting the internet to drive future capabilities. Whilst in Saudi Arabia majority of the small and mid-sized printers have been caught up in the perpetual struggles of making ends meet in an industry which is at risk of becoming replaced/obsolete. This study highlights that struggle. The findings of this study add knowledge to the already existing literature on response of printers to technological disruptions.

More specifically, this study sheds light on the issue of “Saudization” and its corresponding impact on the printing industry. Saudi Arabia is distinct in its own right when compared to the rest of the Arab world owing to ultra-protectionist approach towards its work force. This study adds knowledge on how growth can be driven within protectionist macro environments. Therefore, this study is also of significance to anybody investigating the impact of protectionism within an industry, whilst dealing with disruptive forces.

This study has critically reviewed prior research and literature which offers theories, conceptual frameworks of disruption caused by technology within the printing industry. By conducting a

holistic review of the literature, the study can derive its own conceptual framework which is a contribution to the existing body of literature.

6.3.2 Contribution to Practice

The study offers robust practical contribution to small and mid-sized printing firms in Saudi Arabia. Since the rise of the internet, the printing industry in Saudi Arabia has come under threat of replacement. Rise of online printing platforms has caused a significant decline for traditional print methods. Furthermore, online platforms are rapidly replacing print-based products which used to be a core product offering. The findings of this study indicate there is a vast adoptability of online print platforms within Saudi Arabia. Online print platforms in lieu of traditional print is swiftly becoming the norm. This research aimed to suggest ways in which Saudi printing firms could diversify their product offerings to compete in the “new age” of printing.

Innovation and building new products and services is at the heart of responsiveness to the technological disruption caused by the rise of internet. The findings point out to the inefficacy of the product mix as lacking in length, unsatisfactorily meeting the customer needs; poor suitability of add on services such as marketing and advertising. Findings also show a high potential of the proposed product mix which includes scope for digital advertising & marketing; customized 3-dimensional printing; and deals on cross sectional product lines.

The study also reveals there is a significant scope for the printing firms in Saudi Arabia to adopt latest technology to compliment the quality of their product. Specific measures include development of mobile based application for customers to use; introducing digitalized version of the printed product; adopting 3-dimensional printing; development of new technology driven products such as water-resistant print. The main challenges posed by the internet for Saudi printing firms relates to lowering prices of the print products due to the competition from the

internet; changing content consuming habits of the customers; ease of customizing print online; inability of printed material to match the speed and accessibility of the internet.

From within the industry, experts are gearing towards transformational change with a vision of moving towards a digital model of the print. The digital model will leverage capabilities of the internet and help drive future growth and revenues. This study in this regard lays out a roadmap for small to mid-sized Saudi printing houses with practical steps towards transitioning from print to digital. The practical contributions of this research extend beyond the Saudi context. The recommendations of this research are also relevant for businesses who are currently in the process adopting technological change.

6.3.3 Methodological Contribution

This study is an independent scholarly endeavour which is carried out on scientific methodological principles to meet its objective and address its aim. Numerous methodological challenges relating to the collection and analysis of the data were successfully overcome owing to the logically robust methodological framework. In the specific context of the Saudi printing industry, the use of a mixed method approach is relatively rare as compared to other industries like oil or natural resources. In this regard, this study will become a motivating factor for future researchers to deploy a mixed methodology approach in the specific context of Saudi printing industry or related industries affected by technological disruption.

The methodology is discussed meticulously in the Methodology chapter with an aim to provide a rich and deeper understanding of the research methods. To illustrate; the research lays down the different alternatives available to the researcher when choosing a research philosophy. Following that, justification is provided for choosing a pragmatic research approach. Clear rationale for deploying both qualitative and quantitative methods were provided. These rationales were intimately linked with research objectives set out in previous chapters. This

structured approach to research methodology could provide guidance to future researchers on how to rationalize methodology related choices and make decisions. The methodological framework of this study will be useful to researchers from different domains both within academia, industry, or business. Future studies investigating the scope and impact of technological related disruptions could treat this research as a template to guide their own methodological framework.

Lastly, the rigorous explanation and justification provided on research paradigms like sampling, data collection instruments, analysis techniques and ethical considerations would continue to add value for researcher, companies, consultants, and other stakeholders methodologically.

6.4 RECOMMENDATIONS

Considering the research findings, the following recommendations may prove to be beneficial for Saudi mid-sized printing businesses.

- **Skills Acquisition** – Saudi mid-sized printers are hindered by leveraging the potential benefits of the new media-based platforms owing to the lack of technological skills within the printing industry. Mid-sized printing businesses should restructure their hiring and training policies to yield specific technological skill sets. This will enable mid-sized firms to transition into the digital age as printing companies in the developed world have done.

Shifting Customer Needs – The customer needs are altering owing to the disruption from technology. Mid-sized printing businesses will have to rethink their business model with a focus on innovation. Specific addition of new products and services could digitally advertise and marketing; digital platform for networking; offering lead generation and analytics-based applications.

- **Explore Page Growth Opportunities:** The study has shown the customers are more inclined towards digital media than print media. This offers an opportunity for mid-sized printing firms to cut down on operational costs by developing online applications where traditional print could be migrated to digital print.
- **Digital Packaging:** packaging production using the digital printing is a latest industry trend. Globally printing firms are already using it due to its speed to market (efficiency) and provision for personalization advantages. Adding digital packaging to the product mix will help mid-sized printing firms to differentiate themselves.
- **Greater Level of Personalization:** The findings revealed that customers of the printing firms would very much like options to customize or personalize their products. Additionally, the digital media platforms are preferred by the customers as they offer a higher degree of personalization. Therefore, mid-sized printing companies could greatly benefit from forming strategies which enable a higher level of personalization of their products and services.

- **Utilizing All Media Channels:** One of the stark findings of this research related to the poor levels of customer engagements by the mid-sized Saudi printing firms. Ideally, to effectively advertise and market their products and services, the printing firms in Saudi Arabia should be looking to engage their customers on all available marketing channels such as digital and physical channels. This study also found that respondents favoured digital marketing channels.
- **Print Drives Digital:** Most importantly, the mid-sized printing firms should refrain from viewing the digital print as a competitor, but rather an ally. The findings of this study clearly direct to the message that there is great potential for Saudi printing firms to integrate digital print into their business model.

6.5 LIMITATIONS AND FURTHER RESEARCH

There are two major drawbacks of this study. The first drawback relates to the fact that the results of this study could not be generalized to other Saudi Arabian industries or sectors. This is mainly due to the study being focused only on the printing industry within the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. This is to say that the results would be deemed inappropriate for other prominent Saudi Arabian industries such as tourism, or finance or energy. The second major drawback relates to the small sample size of the respondents (n=5) for collecting qualitative insight. This drawback results from the severe constraint on resources such as time and budget.

It should also be noted that the small sample for collecting qualitative data is balanced by the relatively larger sample size for collecting quantitative data. The quantitative analysis benefited

from a sample size of 250, which could be deemed appropriately large. This leads to the results of the quantitative analysis being generalizable in the context of the Saudi printing industry. The study adopted a mixed methodology approach which is often critiqued on grounds of reliability and validity. Proponents of the mixed methodology approach argue about its suitability for contemporary business research (Bryman et al, 2015). It should be noted that this study has employed suitable statistical methods and presented sound justification for the choice of statistical methods. It can be argued that appropriate statistical methods are enough for proving the reliability and validity of this research project.

The researcher's lack of experience is to some extent compensated for with adopting a mixed methodology approach. The sampling of the participants for qualitative data is not representative of the industry professionals within the Saudi printing industry. However, the extensive years of experience chosen sample is conducive to the overall aim and purpose of this research.

The researcher would urge the further study into the domain by keeping into account the following limitations:

- Resource constraints such as cost, and time could limit interview process and result in bias.
- The sample size should be statistically representative of the underlying population. This would greatly limit the scope for erroneous results.
- Sample for qualitative data should be collected from different businesses across Saudi Arabia for better generalizability of the results.

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APPENDIX

APPENDIX 1 CUSTOMER CROSS SECTIONAL SURVEY

Age:

Sex:

Instructions – Kindly read and answer each of the survey questions to the best of your ability. The survey is totally anonymous, and your identity will not be revealed at any point. Your responses will be strictly and solely used for the purposes of this research. Kindly place ☑ tick sign next to your responses, leaving the other boxes blank.

Likert Scale for responses

Response	Scale Value
Strongly Agree	5
Agree	4
Neutral	3
Disagree	2
Strongly Disagree	1

1. Understanding the Usage of Printed Material.

	Strongly Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
I purchase paper products weekly/monthly	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I purchase newspaper at least weekly/monthly	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I purchase Magazines at least weekly/monthly	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I purchase Academic Journal at least weekly/monthly	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I purchase fiction/nonfiction at least weekly/monthly	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

2. Internet Substitution

	Strongly Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1. Internet is my primary medium for acquiring information	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Internet is more efficient than print media	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. I prefer online mediums over printed mediums	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

to access information

4. I have the same or more online subscriptions than
printed prescriptions

5. Online platforms align better to my individual
Or business needs

3. Current product mix at Al-Fakhoor

Strongly Agree Agree Neutral
Disagree Strongly disagree

1. Al-Fakhoor fully meets my print related
Needs.

2. Advertising products at Al-Fakhoor align
to my personal/business needs.

3. Marketing services at Al-Fakhoor is at par
with industry standards.

4. I prefer to purchase my stationary items at
AL-Fakhoor.

5. I do not think AL-Fakhoor offers a wide range
Of products.

Proposed Product Mix at AL-Fakhoor.

Strongly Agree Agree Neutral
Disagree Strongly disagree

1. I would be open to enhanced digital
advertising products at Al Fakhoor.

2. I would be open to enhanced digital
Marketing products at Al Fakhoor.

3. I think custom printing material offers
Good value for money.

4. Stationary products at AL-Fakhoor offer
Quality & value for money.

5. I feel Al Fakhoor offers various cross-
Sectional deals on its products.

Marketing Mix & Significance for printing industry.

	Strongly Agree Disagree	Agree Strongly disagree	Neutral	
1. Product lines at AL-Fakhoor are good quality. <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. I feel quality of services is in line to its price & offers good value. <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Distribution of products is efficient & cost Effective for the customers. <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. AL-Fakhoor regularly advertises promotions & discounts on its products/services. <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. I feel engaged on multiple platforms to interact With the business (Al-Fakhoor). <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Adaptation of latest technology in printing.

	Strongly Agree Disagree	Agree Strongly disagree	Neutral	
1. I would use a mobile based app for my Printing needs. <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Products and services should be more Focused on digital than actual print. <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

3. 3-d printing is better than traditional printing.

4. I like new technology-based products such as Water resistant print.

5. I would welcome online platforms for Advertising and marketing needs.

Response to transformational change.

Strongly Agree Agree Neutral
 Disagree Strongly disagree

1. I prefer shopping online than in-store for For my print-related needs.

2. I think that data services offered by printing Companies is outdated.

3. Services & products offered by print companies Fit well around my needs.

4. I feel the quality of reading material has remained

Consistent in the age of the internet.

5. I feel printing companies should include more tailored Services for marketing & networking.

Challenges of internet for printing business.

Strongly Agree Agree Neutral
 Disagree Strongly disagree

1. My local vendor should offer internet enabled Services.

2. I prefer customizing my printing products Online than offline.

3. Pricing of printed products has lowered Because of the internet.

4. Performance of Open source online print websites Vs. Traditional printing press.

5. Online printing portals are quicker than Traditional printing press.

Industry Competencies

	Strongly Agree Strongly disagree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree
1. I have switched my printing vendor in the last One year.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
2. Switching my current vendor For increased quality of services/products is easy.		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
3. I feel large scale printers are more efficient Then medium scale printers.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
4. I feel printing my cards/pamphlets online is Much easier for me than traditional print.		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
5. I have considered Qatari printers over Saudi Printers.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	<input type="checkbox"/>			

External Factors – *Economical, Social, and Technological impacting printing industry.*

	Strongly Agree Disagree	Agree Strongly disagree	Neutral	
<p>1. I am aware of my carbon footprint caused Due to paper consumption.</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<p>2. Technology in printing has become accessible Then it was before internet.</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<p>3. I feel digital products are cheaper than print Products.</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<p>4. Environmental friendliness of printing products Influences my purchasing decision.</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<p>5. I prefer digital printing products as they save Physical space for me.</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Strategies to minimize risk and challenges of the internet for printing companies.

	Strongly Agree Disagree	Agree Strongly disagree	Neutral	
<p>1. Printers should re-invent themselves by Having new and innovative services.</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></p>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

**2. Printing businesses should add latest
Latest technology in their operations.**

**3. Offering low prices will
Make me use printers over internet for my
Printing needs.**

APPENDIX 2: INTERVIEW QUESTIONNAIRE

1. How do you foresee the impact of the internet on your business?
2. Do you think adopting the capabilities of the internet will give you FMA?
3. What steps have you taken to develop strategies to use the internet's advantages as a growth and development opportunity?
4. How do you plan to use the internet to improve customer experience?
5. What will be the impact on the product mix and how do you plan to innovate?
6. What sort of changes in the marketing strategy will you have to make?
7. What, according to you, are the challenges and benefits of adopting the internet?

APPENDIX 3: ETHICS APPROVAL APPLICATION FORM (UEC1.1)

Pre-screening questions:

(Please read the UWS and your School Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship before answering these questions, which will help you decide whether you need to make a full ethics approval application for your work).

Does your work involve human participants? YES Choose an item.

Does your work involve the use of personal data? NO Choose an item.

Does your work involve the use of animals? NO Choose an item.

(For this purpose, animals are defined as captive or temporarily captive living vertebrates or cephalopods. If such work is already licensed under the terms of the Animals Scientific procedures act (ASPA) then no further ethics approval is required)

Does your work involve risk to the investigator that is not adequately mitigated by proper application of the University's health and safety policies and procedures? NO Choose an item.

If you have answered **YES** to **any** of the above questions you should complete the remainder of this form and submit it to your school ethics committee for approval **PRIOR** to commencing any work on your project.

If you have answered **NO** to **all** of the above questions your research/scholarship would be Class 1 as defined in the UWS Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship and so you do not need the approval of a School Ethics Committee for your work.

1. Name of Principal Investigator: Danish Mohammad Ashraf

2. School: Business and Enterprise

2b. If you answered "other" above please provide details below:

3. Position of Principal Investigator: Postgraduate student

4. Name and contact details of collaborators: Al- Fakhour Printing Press

5. Name of Supervisor/Director of Studies: Dr.Uma Mohan
(for student applications only)

5a. Position of Supervisor/Director of Studies: DBA Supervisor Lecturer
(for student applications only)

5b. School of Supervisor/Director of Studies: Business and Enterprise
(for student applications only)

6. Title of the study: Impact of Internet substitution on Printing Industry in Saudi Arabia. Recommending a Product Mix to Minimise the impact of Internet Substitution in Saudi Arabia

7. Primary purpose of the study: Postgraduate dissertation

If you answered "other" to this question please provide details below:

8. Has the proposed study been considered by any other ethics committee? NO Choose an item.

If the study has been considered by another ethics committee please provide details below:

9. Please give a full summary of the purpose, justification, design and methodology of the planned study:

(word limit 10 words. A full study protocol should be attached to your application)

For getting effective outcome from the research work, the researchers must use suitable research methods. This research work is based on the printing company of Saudi Arabia named as Al-Fakhor Printing Co. As the researcher wants to find out the impact of internet on the business of printing media, so the researcher used various research approaches for getting effective outcome from the research process. In this context, the researcher also considered the research findings of previous researchers to effectively analysis the factors that directly influence the business of the print media companies in the modern context (D'Arma, 2011). The researcher also compares the financial data of the organization to effectively understand the effects of internet on their business process. The findings of this research work help the organization Al-Fakhor Printing Co. to identify the effective strategies for improving their business process in the era of internet.

Method

This study will be based on the use of pragmatist research philosophy because it will support the researcher in aligning the principles of both interpretive and positivism research philosophies to effectively answer the research questions. It is believed under this philosophy that research questions play an important role in selecting a philosophy (Ahmed, Opoku, and Aziz, 2016). In addition, the use of this philosophy also shows that both quantitative and qualitative methods will be used to complete this research successfully. The use of mix methods will be supportive for the researcher to understand various perspectives as well as study the subject in several ways (Ostrom and Wilhelmsen, 2012). Similarly, for this research, the researcher believes that to evaluate the impact of internet on printing industries in Saudi Arabia, the use of mixed methods would be effective.

Although the author will use two data collection and analysis procedures under qualitative and quantitative methods, but at the same time, these methods will not be combined. In other words, it can be stated that as a part of the mixed method research, the researcher will apply quantitative analysis methods for quantitative data while qualitative analysis methods will be used for evaluating qualitative data (Lodico, Spaulding, and Voegtle, 2010). In addition, the researcher also aims to gather both kind of data simultaneously.

In this research, the researcher will also adopt an exploratory qualitative approach as it helps in developing understanding about the influence of internet on customer decisions. This is the primarily theoretical outlook of opinions, perceptions and cannot be statistically measured and analysed. Qualitative approaches such as interviews and focus groups can be techniques for conducting the exploratory research, and it provides an insight into the phenomenon and research approach.

Aims and Objectives of the research Approach

The major goal of this research is to analyse the impact of internet on the printing business of the Saudi Arabian printing organization Al-Fakhor Printing Co. In addition, the researcher also emphasizes to find out effective strategies the organization should implement in order to expand its business as well as improve its performance. The major objectives of the research work are:

- To evaluate the impact of the use of internet substitution on the printing industry of Saudi Arabia.
- To examine the current product mix and identify those which could be substituted by the internet.
- To recommend a product mix strategy to minimise the risk of internet substitution particularly on Al-Fakhor and printing industry of Saudi Arabia

Secondary Research

The theoretical and conceptual framework discussed in Literature review will be the basis for secondary research. The secondary research also includes journals, information from search engines and online database. These sources are important and play a pivotal role in the collection of primary data for identifying the key variables relative to primary research.

The researcher will also gather the data by using the website and annual report of the company, financial and non-financial publications providing information about the printing firms, and the government records (Benz and Newman, 2008). Moreover, for completing this research successfully, the research from well-known organizations including Deloitte, Accenture, etc. will also be incorporated. The use of these sources would be helpful to gather data in numerical form that mainly reflect on the impact of internet on the performance of printing firms.

10. How has the scientific quality of the proposed research project been assessed?

- | | |
|--|-------------------------------------|
| Independent external review | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Review within a company | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Review within a multi-centre research group | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Review within the principal investigator's institution | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Review within the research team | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Review by supervisor/director of studies | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> |
| Other | <input type="checkbox"/> |

If you answered "other" above please provide details below:

11. Please explain/justify your intended sample size:

Regardless of the age and gender, the participants will be selected for this study. Moreover, the researcher will approach approximately 250 customers of printing industry in Saudi Arabia directly and asked them to involve in the online survey. The main purpose is to examine the impact of internet on printing industry. In-depth interviews with the owners and top managers of the company will be organized to understand the situation in a fully manner. 5 managers will be selected from Al-Fakhoor Printing Company for the purpose of interview.

12. Please explain how you will analyse, present/disseminate the data you intend to collect:

Both qualitative and quantitative methods will be used to effectively analysis all the gathered data. For quantitative analysis, the use of SPSS software would be appropriate and concurrently, for qualitative interviews, the use of thematic framework analysis would be beneficial. In addition, table, graphs, and charts will also be used to present the analysis of data effectively.

13. Does the proposed research involve the use of individual/group interviews or questionnaires?
YES

13a. Will proposed interviews or questionnaires discuss topics that might be sensitive, embarrassing or upsetting for participants or is it possible that criminal or other disclosures requiring action could occur during the study?
NO

If you have answered **YES** to the question above please provide details below and how you propose to deal with such issues:

14. Is the study likely to cause any discomfort or distress, either physical or psychological (see UWS Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship)?
No

If you have answered **Yes** to the question above please provide details below and how you propose to deal with this:

15. Does the proposed research involve any physically invasive procedures?NO

If physically invasive procedures are to be used what hazards are associated with them?

16. Please identify any other ethical considerations with the proposed study.

None identified at this stage

17. Does the proposed research involve deception regarding aims, objectives or the identity of the investigator?
NO

If you have answered **YES** to the above question please provide an explanation/justification of this deception:

18. Will research participants be debriefed after their participation?NO

If you have answered **YES** to the above question please provide details of when this debriefing will take place, who will do it and how it will be done:

19. What is the expected duration of participation in the study for each participant?

Surveys: 15 - 20 Minutes

Interviews: 20-45 Minutes

20. Please provide details of how you will recruit participants to your study:

To complete the survey, online sites such as Survey Monkey.com will be used. For the survey, the target participants include 250 people. The researcher will recruit survey participants online with the use of social media sites mainly facebook. In addition, the interview will be organized by the researcher by following a face-to-face process in Saudi Arabia. Moreover, 5 senior managers from different departments of the company will be targeted for the interview.

21. What measures will you put in place to ensure the confidentiality of personal data gathered during your study?

Standard procedure and anonymity of accumulated data can only be accessed by supervisor and the researcher

22. Who will have access to the data collected during the study and how will you keep it confidential?

Any hard copies of notes maintain during the interview will be kept secure and shredded at a later date. Moreover, at all time, the respondents' privacy and confidentiality will be maintained by keeping data in password secured computers and other locations.

23. Will informed consent be obtained from study participants?YES

If you have answered **YES** to the above question please provide details of how you will obtain this consent and the information you will provide to potential participants to allow them to make an informed choice about whether or not to participate in your research.

It will be provided and attached in the interview and analysis part of the research after it has been conducted. Additionally, verbal permission will be asked from the participants to contribute. In terms of interviews, the participants will be asked to participate and given time

about 2 weeks to make their decisions to interview or not. A consent will be ask prior to the interview, whether they like to participate or not.

(Note: See attached participant consent form).

If you have answered **NO** to the above question please justify your decision not to obtain consent from your participants.

24. How long will potential participants have to decide whether or not to take part in the study?

8 Days

25. Will participants be informed that they can withdraw from the study at any time?YES

26. Will participants be from any of the following groups?

- Children under 16
- Adults with learning disabilities
- Adults who are unconscious or severely ill
- Adults with a terminal illness
- Adults in emergency situations
- Adults with mental illness
(particularly if detained under the mental health act)
- Adults with dementia
- Adults in Scotland who are unable to consent for themselves
- Those who could be considered to have a particularly
dependent relationship with the investigator

- Other
- None of the above

If you answered “**other**” above please provide details:

If you intend to include participants from any of the above groups please outline how you will mitigate the risks involved:

27. Are there any special pressures which would make it difficult for potential participants to refuse to take part in your study?

(e.g., relationship to the investigator?)

NO

28. Will study participants be paid to take part?NO

If you have answered **YES** to the above question please provide details of the payments involved:

29. Where will the proposed research take place?

In Saudi Arabia at Al-Fakhoor head office

30. How will the costs of the study be met?

Self-funded

31. Please indicate which supporting documents you are submitting with this application:

- Participant information sheet (PIS)
- Consent form
- Copy of the protocol

- Letters to participants
- Letters to parent/guardians/gatekeepers etc
- Letter or ethical committee approval or other approvals
- Risk assessments
- Other relevant materials (please specify below)

The information supplied above is, to the best of my knowledge and belief, accurate. I have read the university ethics guidelines and clearly understand my obligations and the rights of study participants, particularly in relation to obtaining valid consent.

Signature of the principal investigator(s): **Danish Ashraf**

Date: 15/06/2017

Signature of the supervisor/director of studies:

Uma Mohan

Date: 15/06/2017

APPENDIX 4: PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM

Name of the Participant

Name of the Researcher

Title of the Project : Evaluation of the Impact of the Internet on Printing Industry in Saudi Arabia

Dear Participant,

Thanks for your participation in this research, and your time and cooperation. The aim of this research is to evaluate the impact of internet on printing industry in Middle East Countries specially in Saudi Arabia on the basis of the case of Al-Fakhoor Printing Company. A close ended questionnaire by using Likert scale will be used for this research to attain the aim and objective of this study. The participants responses will be held anonymous and personal data will keep secret.

To complete this section, please fill each box.

I agree to the interview being audio recorded.

I agree to take part in the above study.

I have knowledge that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to draw back at any time, without giving any reason.

I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet effectively for this research.

The researcher provides the opportunity to ask questions and answered in an appropriate manner.

Kindly sign below if you agree to participate in this study.

By signing below I consent to participate in the current research. I also recognize the purpose, aim, and objectives of this research and its implications.

Signature of the participant:

Date:

Signature of the person taking consent

Date:

Email address to receive copy of this research

APPENDIX 5: PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

For Interview and Survey Process Type Data Collection

Evaluation of the Impact of Internet on Printing Industry in Saudi Arabia

Summary of the Project

The main purpose of this research is to analysis the impact of internet on small and medium sized printing firms in Saudi Arabia. Your participation will enable in the data collection process which will form part of a research undertaken at the university.

The reason to ask to participate in the research

You have been asked to take part in this research because you fit the profile of the population being studied. It is because you are between the ages of 18 and 40 and belong to printing industry.

The main criteria include

- Age more than 18
- The participants include employees, managers, and customers.

At the same time, you are suggested not to drive to or from the interview and survey process.

During the survey process you will be asked about the use of printing media sources and how the evaluation of internet affected their choice about printing media.

You will only be required to provide their opinion about the impact of internet on printing industry.

In addition, your participation is totally voluntary and at any time, you may withdraw.

Project Risks

The completion of the survey through questionnaire process and participation in an interview process are part of this research and these will be recorded for further analysis. This study does not involve the collection of sensitive data from the participants; this research is only related with moderate impact of internet on printing industry in Saudi Arabia and will not discuss the impact of other factors such as interest rate, inflation, etc. It shows that this study does not contain any significant risks that can affect any participant, or other people. Concurrently, if you feel that any of the question is inadequate, you can stop at any time. In addition, at any time, you can change your mind to draw back from the research-your decision will be respected completely.

The Way to Protect your Privacy

All the information and data provided by you will be kept in confidential. The researcher will take care and ensure that no participant cannot be identified from the questionnaire form in a direct way; there is no information in the questionnaire that will identify you. Additionally, your personal details such as name, income, age, and occupational level in the questionnaire and on the consent form will be preserved in secure locations by the research team. After the completion of this study and analysis of the information from the documentation used to collect the data will be destroyed. Additionally, during this research, the recordings of the interview will also be kept in a secure and confidential environment and it will be destroyed after the completion of this research.

A Copy of this Information Sheet will also be offered to You

APPENDIX 6: TRANSCRIPTS

Transcript 1

Date – 28/6/2019

Time & Venue – Al- Fakhour Head office

Name of interviewee – XXXXXXXXXX

1. How do you foresee the impact of the internet on your business?

The internet has greatly altered how the printing industry used to operate and how it will likely operate in the future. You have to understand that printing press based business have the key objective of reaching to the masses with their message. This message could be news, discussions, forums, reporting on key socio-economic statistics. If we speak historically, the newspaper and public forum news boards were the key messengers that used to reach out to the masses. The people relied on the printed press to be informed about the affairs of their environment.

Now, however we have the internet which has given stiff competition to the printing press based industry. You see, as internet has grown into multiple domains of daily life from entertainment to business people's reading habits have largely altered. A good example of this would be that back in the day people would solve the Sudoku over tea as a source of entertainment, or look at cartoons. This was all in congestion with news about more serious affairs in the newspaper. Times now have changed. Now, we have the internet which offer too many choices to people to seek entertainment and information. It is available round the clock and anywhere the reader would like it.

So, the internet has disrupted the printing media industry in a major way. Internet also poses threat to the way we have operated historically. We will have to adapt to the internet as it provides us with opportunities to expand our readership; better engage our readers; increase our market presence and popularity and so forth.

2. Do you think adopting the capabilities of the internet will give you FMA?

I do believe there is a first mover advantage for us if we are to fully adopt the capabilities of the internet. There is evidence of early mover advantage online. Early movers online enjoy a lenient competitive environment in the early stage of industry development that permits firms to experiment, develop skills specific to online selling and to build customer base at a lower cost. On the other hand, late Internet entrants have to face the hyper-competition and the resulting marketing resource depletion.

For example, the online advertisements and customer attraction expenses become unaffordable for some new entrants. The design features of the Internet platforms also favor early movers. Some information which is important for online customer decision making, such as prior sales information, store reputation or word of mouth, are endogenous in nature. Because early movers have a longer time to build and disseminate such information through the use of design features of the platform, they can enjoy an early mover advantage.

3. What steps have you taken to develop strategies to use the internet's advantages as a growth and development opportunity?

Well, you see we essentially would like to transition from a printing media platform to an online media platform. The heart and soul of the printing press industry is good journalism. I believe the internet offers opportunity to enhance journalistic capabilities. Therefore, in order to for us to make this transition we are now developing policies around hiring and training process which is essentially aimed at training our workforce to be more tech savvy. We have created few new roles within the organization which will specifically handle to the digital media and social media functions. This new roles will enable us to better market our brand via the internet.

We are also in the process of developing “new media” portals which will act an electronic version of our printed media products. Again, this is vertical integration within the organization so it will require hiring online media developers and testers. We really hope to leverage the opportunities offered by the internet into growing and developing our brand. This will require us to both have an engaging internet based platform as well as train the new generation of journalists on how to use internet channels effectively when reporting. I believe, this will enable us to step into the future of the printing media. A future where internet will play the role which the printing press did in the 16th century in the times of Marin Luther King.

4. How do you plan to use the internet to improve customer experience?

Oh well, the possibilities are quite exciting. Essentially, we want to enhance the consumer experience by offering new services and products, new applications and overall give the customer an opportunity to align their business model with our offerings.

For printing companies the focus must lie on two key areas. These are, firstly the operational side of the business. Secondly, the need to deliver new innovative ideas which enables them to differentiate themselves whilst adding value to their customers.

The current landscape is such that print companies which are inefficient and not making any real money are solely focused on fighting the everyday battles of operation and pushing out the content somehow. These companies are likely to become redundant in the future. Some printing companies are focused on cost reduction as a response to financial constraints. They lack the resources or appetite for investing in new range of services for their customers. They tend rely on status quo and don't really anticipate customer's future needs.

A growing fraction of the printing companies have now introduced customer centric application via web and data management. Unfortunately, it is not done to the extent where it's effective in meeting the customer's needs. The printers who are striving to grow and adapt their business realize that they must be focused and driven as much by innovation as operational improvement.

The printers who are really thriving have grown and increased their profitability even through the last few years of economic recession. The reason for this is that they have a customer centric approach to everything they do and provide solutions to a customer's business problems, rather than selling them a printed product. By using this approach they have avoided the commodity trap and now have conversations about added value and return on investment instead of unit price of the printed product.

5. What will be the impact on the product mix and how do you plan to innovate?

The product mix will be diversified by expanding in to the realm of digital print. We plan to innovate by developing deeper relationships with our reader base by targeting specific interest areas. Well known printing brands all have one thing in common, i.e – they all enjoy a trusted relationship with their reader base. This is due to the fact they provide quality content in targeted areas. Digital print media offers us opportunities to effectively establish such a kind of relationship with our reader base.

Product mix needs to be diversified beyond just traditional streams of revenue which have been advertising and circulation. New products and services will need to be created via innovation. These products and services could include custom content, consumer insights, and lead generation, and new offerings for customers such as premium content and data-based applications.

Another strategy to innovate is to rethink our content delivery model. Thus far, content delivery model has been heavily preoccupied with cost cutting. I believe this needs to change. The focus must now shift to delivering a "profitable core" of unique and brand-defining material. The costs associated with the content delivery system should be better align with the cost of content versus the revenues generated.

Another strategy to innovate could involve innovating through better and more optimized pricing models. We really have to rethink the ways in which we price our products and services. This is due to the digital age we now are a part of. Paper based print is rapidly being replaced by new online platforms for consuming content. Every few months a new app is launched which makes the paper based print more obsolete.

6. What sort of changes in the marketing strategy will you have to make?

In growing numbers printers have looked for fresh revenue opportunities to supplement the decreasing historical core revenue streams. It is very striking to see how printers are diversifying and the wide range of services they are now offering.

Digital communications now represents 57% of daily media time, so a marketer seeking to get the best from their limited marketing budget would want to maximize the chance of getting the consumer's attention. There is repeated evidence that shows the necessity of using multiple marketing 'touch points' to prompt a consumer and get a response to a call to action. Marketers will now consider all the different channels available and choose those that fit with the budget and are most likely to generate an effective response.

Printers are starting to realise that with digital communications there is a growing opportunity for consumer segmentation i.e. collecting data and insights to more closely define the audience or individual, thereby increasing the relevance of the messaging and the likelihood of a positive response. We can see that the top 20% of print companies are exploiting these new opportunities and are having much closer relationships with their customers. However the vast majority are not responding and adapting their business to this new landscape and are finding it increasingly difficult to achieve any profitable growth.

7. What, according to you, are the challenges and benefits of adopting the internet?

Strong competition and a lack of sales are key challenges. Strong competition and commoditization are key challenges to growth for around 50- 60% of print providers. Lack of sales is the next biggest issue followed by a lack of skills in sales and marketing and being able to recruit the right staff.

The key to growing sales is finding new customers and this is the biggest challenge because printers are not focused on adapting their sales and marketing approach to include conversations around new digital services and how they can integrate them with print. Printers include lack of demand as a constraint to sales but they are confusing lack of demand with their inability to effectively sell the value of digital print and multi-channel services to the customer.

The major internal challenge for print providers is being able to transform their business and redefine what it means to be a printer and understand how they can deliver new services that will be relevant to their customers and add value to their relationship. Recent Print Future research has demonstrated that very few printers are ready for this journey. Around 35% of print providers do not believe they can make this transition and are going to stick to what they have always done, concentrating purely on print and they are prepared to take their chances as the market evolves. A further 25% have indicated that they are aware that they need to make this transition and add new services but they haven't started the process yet. 30% of companies have started transforming their business but are only part way through and still have a lot of ground to which create new revenue streams as well as supporting and complimenting their print activities.

The great news for ambitious print providers looking to grow their business is, that if they start the process now they can instantly become one of the top 40% of print companies. With some planning and investment they could quickly get into the top 20% of the market greatly enhancing the profitability and relevance of their business in the future.

Transcript 2

Date – 22/06/2019

Time & Venue – Al-fakhoor head office

Name of interviewee – [REDACTED]

1. How do you foresee the impact of the internet on your business?

The internet is likely to disrupt the printing press industry in a major way. In some subset within the industry it is already happening. In the future, the internet will likely become what the newspaper used to be 30 or 50 years ago. The newspaper was the primary source of news on immediate and global affairs. It would even be printed multiple times a day and circulated to keep up with the speed of news affairs. The newspaper would be a source of entertainment, communication, advertising and of course reporting of the news. Now, all of that is getting swiftly replaced by the internet.

The internet has what the newspaper never did – i.e. – speed and wide reach. In the printing industry, we are now faced with a huge .. huge.. challenge of responding to the rising threat of substitution from the internet. The internet has overtaken the newspaper in the sense that it now caters to a wider audience as well as have higher product offering that traditional printed press. These offerings mainly relate to higher mobility and accessibility.

The internet is surely disrupting the traditional status quo in the print industry. We will have to adapt to the new way of things... this would mean finding ways to leverage the potential of the internet within the print industry. For instance, the internet is already disrupting areas such as readership capturing, retention and marketing function within the print industry. Social media platforms are giving stiff competition to print journalism but that is again not

without its flaws. I feel there will need to be a synergy between the adoption of internet within operations and print journalism.

2. Do you think adopting the capabilities of the internet will give you FMA?

To talk specifically about the Saudi Arabian context, there is a very strong first mover advantage for any printing business looking to fully integrate the potential of the internet into their business model. If we look outside the Saudi Arabian context, then we see that top printing businesses such as the Huffington post, Wall Street Journal or the Harvard Business review have found ways to incorporate the potential for internet much earlier on. So, in this sense I strongly believe the same advantage could be replicated in the Saudi context.

Moreover, in any industry the first mover advantage is there. However, you should not take that for granted as it could be short lived. By that I mean you really have to focus on sustaining your first mover advantage as much as you can. This requires a strong brand image and presence. Internet should be seen as an enabler of doing that. So, in this regard a first mover advantage could help small and mid-size printing businesses in Saudi to really establish a strong market presence and drive growth through it.

3. What steps have you taken to develop strategies to use the internet's advantages as a growth and development opportunity?

That's a good question, I think we are still in the process of leveraging the potential of the internet within our business. You have to understand that internet is an excellent platform which means it can reach masses very quickly and effectively. It goes without saying that core of print industry will always be producing good and relevant content which the reader would like to engage in. So, we see internet as this framework which can add value to our core strategy. In terms of specific steps which we have taken to advance our business through internet, I would say we are now looking at training our workforce to enable them to better use the internet for capturing audiences. In addition to training our people, we have also created several new positions within the business that work specifically on internet based products that we offer. These new additions to our existing framework is aimed at capturing more audience and better engaging the existing readership.

We have launched internet based channels which essentially will act as an extension of our print model. All of this requires strong capacity building within the organization first. For that we have decided to create a new cell division within the business dedicated to developing these internet based channels. The idea is to optimally leverage the opportunities provided by the internet to better market and channel our products as well as improving our current product offerings.

4. How do you plan to use the internet to improve customer experience?

Let me begin by saying that the internet have huge potential for improving the overall customer experience. We plan to improve the customer experience by creating product mix and web based applications which the customers can then utilize to add value to their own businesses.

In today's market the printing firms will need to seek ways to use the internet to improve operational efficiencies as well as creating new products which can set them apart from the competition in terms of adding value to customers.

To give you a brief idea about what is happening currently in this markets is that we have firms which struggle to maintain their existing readership because they are operationally inefficient. These are the printing firms which are cash strapped as a result of limited audience. Money as a resource is a huge constraint in this business, you have to keep that in mind. So now, these firms will likely try to resort to cost cutting in order to keep afloat. Essentially, what is wrong with these printing businesses is that they lack any real capacity for developing new products for the consumer and innovate. These are the firms which are at risk of becoming obsolete because they couldn't capture and respond to customer needs.

On the other end of the spectrum we have firms which printing firms which have anticipated the changing customer needs by developing a consumer centric web based platforms and data collected through these platforms. These firms are continuously trying to predict customer behavior through data analytics and developing products and services which cater to these specific needs of the customers. These firms have a strong operational base. They innovate new services and products instead of treating the print as just a commodity for the customer which they can get anywhere. They seek to use the internet to develop solutions to customer problems, add value and return on investment.

A growing fraction of the printing companies have now introduced customer centric application via web and data management. Unfortunately, it is not done to the extent where it's effective in meeting the customer's needs. The printers who are striving to grow and adapt their business realize that they must be focused and driven as much by innovation as operational improvement.

The printers who are really thriving have grown and increased their profitability even through the last few years of economic recession. The reason for this is that they have a customer centric approach to everything they do and provide solutions to a customer's business problems, rather than selling them a printed product. By using this approach they have avoided the commodity trap and now have conversations about added value and return on investment instead of unit price of the printed product.

5. What will be the impact on the product mix and how do you plan to innovate?

We are excited about the product mix because now a lot of new products and services could be added to our existing mix. These new products and services will be digital in nature and will be tightly aligned with the future needs of our customers. By revamping the product mix

we anticipate to develop a much closer relationship with our customers. Our vision behind restructuring our product mix is to be able to gain greater trust from our customers.

We intend to launch specific products such as consumer insights for our readers, lead generation for their businesses, and premium content and data based applications. Additionally, the pricing for these new products and services will need to be optimized in a way which complements our existing product mix. This is one key strategy which will prove to be pivotal in driving growth.

6. What sort of changes in the marketing strategy will you have to make?

Marketing is an important aspect in the printing business. With changing times the industry has really focused on new opportunities to replenish the diminishing revenue streams since the rise of the internet. Printing businesses are now in the process of diversification and creating new ranges of products and services.

Historically, media exposure used to be over 70% on the printed material. This has swiftly changed because of the internet and digital broadcasting channels. It is estimated that over half of media exposure is now through digital channels and majorly over the internet. Marketers have realized the importance of developing strategies which involve use to all digital channels in creating touch points to reach the consumer.

Marketing strategies greatly benefit with the use of digital platforms as they enable optimal customer segmentation. This is done through gathering vast amounts of data on consumer behavior and eliciting valuable insights which helps in segmenting the customers. Optimal segmentation enables the marketers to develop targeted content to different segments and hence, likely increasing customer engagement. So essentially, internet and data analytics have enabled to printing firms to develop robust marketing strategies through optimal segmentation. This is done by the thriving printing businesses and as a result they have a much more active and engaged readership than their competition. This directly leads to profitable business growth.

7. What, according to you, are the challenges and benefits of adopting the internet?

I'd like to begin to answer this question by telling a bit about the main challenges which are faced in the print industry today. These mainly relate to saturation and diminishing sales. You see, the print industry is plagued by lack of competency in being able to market your product. With the rise of technology and digitalization the printing industry has fallen behind in terms of developing competencies which the workforce to harness the benefits of technology.

There is a feeling of scarcity that is there aren't enough consumers for the digital print products in the market. I think this is where majority of the printing firms are going wrong. Increasing sales is challenge because that involves acquiring new customers. Majority of the

printers are still caught up in a rut that markets are drying up when what they should actually be focusing is on effectively marketing their products via digital platforms.

The internet is a tool which can enable the printers to effectively redefine their business model by rethinking their existing relationship with their consumers. Printing firms will need to use the accessibility provided by the internet to create new services which are relevant to their consumers and increase value in their entire supply chain process.

The problem however lies in that fact majority of the printers are yet to recognize this within the Arabian world. For those, who have realized this but lack the resources to invest in the infrastructure for this transition. Very few firms have indeed taken this leap into digitalization of their platforms. They are mostly in the early phases of this transition and yet to see any real growth in terms of sales. Nevertheless, it's a step in the right direction. I think these are the firm which will become more responsive and adaptable to the speed at which the market is changing.

Transcript 3

Date –15/6/2019

Time & Venue – Al Fakhoor Head office

Name of interviewee – XXXXXXXXXX

Title: Operation Manager

1. How do you foresee the impact of the internet on your business?

The printing business is one of those businesses which haven't evolved much since its early days. This is not to say that printing as a business is exactly the same that it used to be. We have come a long way in terms of mediums and channels that we engage in to reach our consumers. In the old days, the printing business was mainly confined to the spreading of news on current affairs. As time progressed, the printing firms started to think of ways to keep their readership more engaged. This led to the evolution within journalism and expanding of business for the printing businesses.

The internet since its early days have come a long way in transforming people's lives. It has disrupted almost every single industry and printing industry is one of those industries which is majorly affected with the rise of the internet. The internet has the potential to transform the printing industry in a major way. For instance, the internet is already the platform of choice in which people consume a lot of their content in the field of education, entertainment, and politics and so on. In this way, the internet has really been able to become an indispensable part of people's lives. So I do see the internet really impacting the printing business because before the internet, the print media was the major platform for the masses to consume information.

The internet offers a lot of potential for transforming the printing business. These opportunities lie in creation of new digital media products and changing the way in which the consumers interact with our business.

2. Do you think adopting the capabilities of the internet will give you FMA?

The first mover advantage is there in many industries. In that sense, the printing industry is perhaps no exception. The question now arises what sort of specific first mover advantage could be reaped from adopting the capabilities of the internet. To answer this we can look at the way things have been done from around the world. We have successful printing businesses with a strong market presence which have successfully integrated the internet into their business model and are now reaping the benefits of it.

These specific first mover advantage in the printing industry mainly has related to the business being able to establish itself and gain the confidence of its readers much earlier on. This has been done by reaping a stronger brand image, launching services via internet which are unique and well aligned with customer's needs and so on. If you ask me if there is potential for this to be repeated in the Saudi market, I would say definitely so! Ours is a relatively younger market and there is room for a lot of innovation. So I can say that adopting the capabilities of the internet will reap some sort of first mover benefit in the Saudi market.

3. What steps have you taken to develop strategies to use the internet's advantages as a growth and development opportunity?

Well, we see tremendous opportunity in the digital print which is essentially powered by the internet. What we would like to do is create new digital products and find new and more creative ways to engaging the customer. Doing so will be main driver of sales and expanding the business. We have done a SWOT analysis and our key strength is good journalism and the overall quality of the content which we provide. The main challenge/threat for us lies in the fact we have not yet been able to transition into the digital media space as much as we would like to. So to address this threat we have decided to make the necessary investment into helping us transform into the digital media space. These investments relate to restructuring the work force and creating capacity within our work force so they are able to perform better on digital platforms.

Presently, we have digital platforms but they don't offer a lot in terms of products and services to our existing readership. We would like to hire more professionals who have been trained well digital media platforms. The idea is to make our present readership transition onto the digital media platforms. We also would like to set up a specific digital media marketing function within the organization. These will be the people which will really help to propagate our brand through the internet. So, all in all these are some of the strategies which

we have in mind that we would like to execute. I really believe that these strategies will vastly help us to take complete advantage of the internet in enabling us to grow.

4. How do you plan to use the internet to improve customer experience?

Well, we are very excited about improving the customer experience through the internet. We have a lot in mind that we would like to offer our customers in terms of newer services and increased product offerings. The great thing about digital platforms is that there is scope for collecting so much data about consumer preferences and then using the insights from the data to improve what we offer. Our vision is such that we would to integrate ourselves with what our consumer's business model. So our services will have to be created with this vision in mind.

See, I'll talk about the Saudi context. At present not a lot of firms have realised the potential of the internet in enhancing customer experience. Most of the printing firms in this market are not making a lot of money, as they struggle with the challenges posed by the internet. The future for these firms seems bleak. Then, we have printing businesses which do realise that internet offers a lot of opportunities in addition to the challenges it poses. Unfortunately, these business are too small in scale and lack the resources for transitioning to start using internet to enhance user experience.

A very small number of printing businesses in Saudi Arabia are introducing newer web based applications for its users. They have introduced specific services which enable their users to network better using their platforms. Again, this is all very new and most of these firms are still in the process of testing the waters. Innovation has to lead the way.

If you talk about the few players who have effectively enhanced customer experience through the internet have done so through advance data analytics techniques. These firms have seen increased growth in their reader base. They offer services to their readers which can be custom tailored to each customer's specific needs.

5. What will be the impact on the product mix and how do you plan to innovate?

The product mix will have to be restructured through innovation. This innovation will be directly led via digital platforms. We aim to deepen our existing product mix with digital based services that complement our existing product mix. Our vision behind being able to innovate is to provide specialised services to our customers which are focused on their needs. This vision will allow us to develop a deeper relationship with our reader base and promote loyalty for our brand.

Innovation could be driven by multiple strategies. One of these strategies could be to add services which go beyond the traditional scope of printing businesses. For example, we could include marketing services like providing lead generation, consumer analytics and insights to our customers.

We also plan to innovate by cutting down the costs and reinventing the content delivery system. This will be done with a particular focus upon minimizing the costs associated with

our content delivery system. This cost reduction will enable more optimized resource allocation to content creation related tasks. In this way, the costs will reflect the quality of the content and drive revenues.

Pricing of the new products and services could also pave the way for innovation. We have new devices and digital media platforms emerging into the market each day. These will require new opportunities for the printing businesses to re-price their products and become more cost efficient and competitive.

6. What sort of changes in the marketing strategy will you have to make?

Marketing is a crucial area within the printing business. We are heavily dependent of maintaining our reader base as acquiring new readers. The marketing in this particular business is under a lot of strain as traditional revenue streams have started to decline. Now marketers are required to look to fresh streams of generating revenues via diverse channels.

In one word we really see the future of marketing strategies to be heavily centered on the digital marketing. There is good reason for this. If we talk about how marketing strategies used to operate before the rise of the internet, it would be through offline channels. This worked well in those days. Now digital marketing is seen as the prime form of marketing for reaching the customers. Specific strategies which we have are all based on the principle of establishing multiple digital contact points with the customers. This has worked well for us.

Digital marketing also has an advantage that it enables us to collect and collate vast amounts of meta-data which would not be possible via other channels of marketing. Meta data analysis has been very helpful for us to better target our customer via segmentation. It enables us to better understand the needs of our customers and respond most effectively. Marketing this way has led us to become more profitable and also increased our market presence.

7. What, according to you, are the challenges and benefits of adopting the internet?

If you ask me there are more benefits to adopting the internet than there are challenges involved. You might ask, what exactly I mean by this statement. Well, the printing industry is already facing a lot of challenges. These challenges are exacerbated by the prevalence of the internet. For example, the tried and tested way of doing things no longer works as internet has rose to prominence. We are losing readership. This has a direct result on our revenues. This leads to stagnation and practically no growth for prolonged periods of time. In the meantime, the internet is continuously grabbing greater hold of our existing “print media” customers. Furthermore, there are issues relating to competition within the industry and a lack of skilled sales and marketing professionals. So these are the main challenges posed by the internet in a nutshell.

In order for us to grow we need to more customers for our product, which can only be done by creating a demand for our product. There is a common misconception that there are no new customers within the market. I think there is a gap in the market where marketers are failing to create a demand. Internet can be a valuable aid in this process. For example, by

engaging the customers through new media platforms and informing them of the online based services which we now provide, I think we should be able to acquire new customers. This can drive our growth and solve financial worries.

I mentioned about creating new online based services. This is the need of the hour. It's a shame that most printing firms are not taking this seriously. You cannot compete with the internet as a print based company alone. You will have to evolve as markets and customer needs are changing. The best way to benefit from the internet is to use to your advantage. This can be done by creating specialized online services and special online products for the clients which will add value to their lives. This will help in transforming the customer's relationship with us in a positive way. The main challenge to this is level of investment into the infrastructure and creating a market for our products.

Transcript 4

Date – 28/6/2019

Time & Venue – Al- Fakhour Head office

Name of interviewee – XXXXXXXXXX

1. How do you foresee the impact of the internet on your business?

The internet has disrupted the printing industry in a major way. I see internet becoming an indispensable part of the printing industry in the future. In the recent past internet has posed challenges for our industry, this is to say that traditional way how the print industry operates came under threat. You have to understand that as an industry, we have relied mainly on the printed products. These are newspapers, magazines, books, which were our primary products. Ever since the printing industry came into existence we experienced little disruptions from mass media technology like the radio or the television. This is however, nowhere near in comparison to the disruption we are facing from the internet.

I will explain my point in detail, the radio or even the television lacked something, it was the lack of accessibility. Not everyone had access to the radio or the television, while the printed products were readily available to the masses at significantly lowered prices. This is what limited the impact of the radio and television on the printing industry. In the case of the internet, this has now changed. The internet is readily available at low prices. In terms of product offering, the internet has managed to evolve as a single platform for all customer's needs. Whether it's entertainment, news, education or commerce. This is the reason why internet has proved itself to be such a disruptive force for the printing industry.

The internet also has the potential of having a positive impact within the printing industry. I mentioned this earlier. We will have to find ways to incorporate the internet within our business model. This is to say we have to find ways to turn the threat from the internet into opportunity for us to grow and benefit from.

2. Do you think adopting the capabilities of the internet will give you FMA?

First mover advantage by adopting the capabilities of the internet will relate to being able to establish a brand before the competition. There is some truth to the idea that moving in first with the potential of the internet will enable us to get ahead of the competition. Off course, only time can tell if first movers advantage through the capabilities of the internet really applies in this industry as it has to some other manufacturing based industries. Internet has proved itself as a disrupting force within the print industry. So, I'd like to think that moving in early with the advantages of the internet will enable us to gain a pre-emptive advantage and also allow us greater flexibility in experimenting, developing skills specific to online selling to build an active online customer base at low costs.

Entering into the market as a late entrant has a few significant disadvantages associated to it. These relate with hyper competition and huge costs associated with marketing to gain a footing in the market.

3. What steps have you taken to develop strategies to use the internet's advantages as a growth and development opportunity?

We are essentially aiming towards modifying our business model which will be a hybrid of the traditional printing press model and new online based products and services. We have to develop our brand which appeals to the changing needs of our customers. I see, the internet as an enabler of things new within our existing model. The core competency in our industry is providing good content to our readers. I believe the internet can act as a catalyst in propagating our content and increase our readership. To talk about specific strategies which we have in place to harness the power of the internet we now have restructured our hiring policies aimed at hiring people with the right skill sets in the online mass media domain. We are also rethinking our marketing e

We also plan on launching new innovative services and products which will be online. These will help us to better respond to the changing needs of our customer base. To make this happen we have to invest in the infrastructure. By infrastructure, I mean creating these online platforms and servers to run these online services and host our product to our customers.

With the right strategies in place we really believe we can use the internet to our advantage and reap its benefits. This is what is needed to drive us forward with the changing times.

4. How do you plan to use the internet to improve customer experience?

Customer service is an important part of our business. What we are striving to do is provide a holistic service to our customers. We want to create products and services which our customers need and will complement their business at the same time.

How this can be achieved from a business point of view you may ask. Well we would like to restructure our operational side of the business. At present, we are in the process of developing newer products and operations would need to be customised accordingly.

It's quite a challenging task for a firm of our size to be able to innovate and invest our resources into developing new products for our customers. But then again, this is the need of the hour and we must evolve with the changing conditions of the market. At present, the old way of doing things is under threat. In our sector, printing companies are struggling to remain financially profitable because they lack a vision for the future. The customer experience plays a key role in this vision.

We have planned on setting aside a significant part of our annual budget towards building capacity which will enable us to deliver customized customer experience. This will mainly include building data base platforms via internet. The data harnessed on these platforms will enable us to analyze customer behavior and anticipate customer's needs ahead of time. Online platforms have a distinct advantage with regard to the vast amount of customer data it can collect. We aim to use this data in delivering customized services and products to our customers.

The key to growth in this market by adopting a customer centric approach. Printing businesses in Saudi and globally who have done this have remained resilient to the fast changing landscape of the industry. Internet will play a pivotal role for us towards building this resilience within our own business.

5. What will be the impact on the product mix and how do you plan to innovate?

The first strategy is to develop deeper relationships with readers around targeted interest areas. This builds on a strength that has always been at the heart of publishing: Strong print brands enjoy a trusted relationship with their audience; readers are loyal to print publications because they provide high-quality content about specific interest areas. Digital media afford opportunities to deepen and extend those relationships.

The second strategy is to tap into revenue streams beyond advertising and circulation. New publishing models will include marketing services such as custom content, consumer insights, and lead generation, and new offerings for customers such as premium content and data-based applications.

The third strategy is to reinvent the content delivery model (with a particular focus on lowering costs) and to emphasize a “profitable core” of unique and brand-defining material. Print media companies need to avoid the formula-driven approaches to cost cutting that have been prevalent so far, and instead adopt approaches that better align their cost of content with the revenues generated.

The fourth success strategy for the media company of the future is to innovate with new products and pricing models. As the pace of change continues to quicken in the digital world, as new devices for accessing printed content continue to emerge, and as new applications are developed to exploit online content, this will lead to as-yet-untapped opportunities for media companies.

6. What sort of changes in the marketing strategy will you have to make?

Marketing strategy will need to change as we develop and innovate. You see, with new products and services which will largely be internet based we will need put heavier focus on digital marketing for us to promote these. Historically, the marketing within our industry has evolved a lot in the last 20 years.

Digital marketing approach which we seek to develop will be heavily reliant on ensuring customer engagement and interaction with our brand. Ideally, we would like to engage our customers by having multiple touch points for the customer. This will ensure greater exposure of our brand. Off course, we will be considering other marketing strategies to compliment digital marketing. This will be done across all available channels to us. We would like to retain marketing strategies that have worked well for us. With that being said, we have to find out ways in which our product mix will change by addition of new products and services.

Marketing via digital platforms will also enhance our segmentation capabilities. Segmentation is important in our line of work as we cater to a very diverse and wide range of audience. So it become essential for us to be able to segment them correctly. Again, internet and digital platforms will pave the way for this. Optimal segmentation will enable us to deliver the right message and increase our likelihood of customer engagement. In the mid to long term with increased customer engagement we can develop a closer and personal relationship with our customers. This will ensure longevity and sustainability of our market share. All of this is what will drive our future growth.

7. What, according to you, are the challenges and benefits of adopting the internet?

We are faced with a lot of challenges which are actually a direct threat from the internet. The sales are not what the used to be and now we have greater competition within the market. Growth has been stifled in the face of diminishing sales. Furthermore, the industry is changing quick and moving towards digitalization. So that poses a challenge for us to acquire the right talent for the changing times.

Sales has become increasingly challenging for us because we have not been able to acquire new customers at a steady pace. This is partially due to the fact that we did not think about restructuring our marketing strategy. The key challenge for us is to be sell our products and services to new customers across the most effective channels. As discussed earlier, we have identified digital marketing with multiple touch points to be an effective strategy. This is actually one of the key benefits for us to adopt the internet.

In order for printing businesses to really be able to unlock the benefits offered by the internet, they will have rethink their entire business model. They will have to reconsider what is it that their customers want and how best to service these needs. This can be done through the internet most easily and effectively. Unfortunately, a lot of the printing businesses are not ready for making this transition. They lack a vision for the future and do not see the potential for the benefits offered by the internet. These printing businesses are at a major risk of becoming obsolete with changing times. There are printing businesses which understand that it is essential for them to create new services and products for their customers in order to compete in the market. What is challenging for such firms is the lack of resources. While some have realized the potential for the internet and started investing into developing new products, they still have a long journey ahead of them to see any real benefits.

Key is to have a vision for the future. A printing businesses can start with small steps towards this transition and eventually will find itself making leaps ahead. If they do so now, they are automatically ahead of the pack and it will not be long before they see a rise in their profitability. As I said, in the end it all comes down to whether or not you have that vision for the future.

Transcript 5

Date – 02/7/2019

Time & Venue – Al- Fakhour Head office

Name of interviewee – XXXXXXXXXX

1. How do you foresee the impact of the internet on your business?

The way I see it, the internet is both a good thing and bad for our business. On one hand it allows us to connect to our users and it's cheaper of course than sending out business cards in the mail or distribute paper pamphlets (we still do that but not as much). Also, it allows us to reach out to customers in regions outside of Riyadh... we have customers from all over Saudi kingdom now. We plan to reach as far as possible. That's the good news...

The bad is that internet has made everything so cheap Literally everything is cheap now I feel because of the internet. So our price margins have definitely shrunk...because on the internet you could get the same printing job done from some other vendor for less. So you see it's great for the customer... they get to dominate. I can think back to the 1990s when

printing used to be a seller's market. There were only a few printers and printing used to be expensive because of it. People also didn't have personal computers like they do now, so that also meant the printers could charge prices with higher margins. You see, internet and technology in general has changed all of that. Printing has become really cheap and the competition in the markets have risen because of the internet.

In the future, I can see more and more interactive printing services being offered to the customers online. Customization in printing has become quite popular, earlier there used to be bulk printing of the same format...now you can use software to customize your print and print in on all sorts of things like mugs, clothes, frames, etc. This is how I see the internet impacting printing in the future.

2. Do you think adopting the capabilities of the internet will give you FMA?

I personally feel there can be a first mover advantage in the industry if you know exactly what you are targeting. The greatest capability of the internet is its wide reach; ease of use; and greater services which it could host. In a nutshell you can reach more people, more easily than more, and offer them more services than you ever could. I have some loyal clients whom I have met in person and yet we share such as fruitful business relationship.

I will specifically talk about the Saudi printing industry, I feel if you can figure out how to integrate new services using technology (internet) that can compete with what bigger players are offering, and then there is certainly a first mover advantage to be had. Off course, this only holds true for a certain segment of the industry. You can't compete with bigger players with just technology alone, you need more resources like capital, much larger operation and so on. But I think, the first mover advantage for SME providers like us lies in being able to differentiate themselves from the herd, i.e – rest of the players in your league. So regionally, yes I do see there being a first mover advantage.

3. What steps have you taken to develop strategies to use the internet's advantages as a growth and development opportunity?

See, we understand that the Saudi printing industry for the smaller players like us is in the decline. Profit margins have significantly shrunk from what they used to be and internet is the main driving force behind this decline. But the internet also provides us with the opportunity to reshape our business model and become a hybrid version of physical print and online printing company. For this we have decided to invest in the infrastructure needed and upgrade our human resources capability. We are looking to hire people with prior experience in digital print. I feel it's much easier to hire people with the right skills than train them, although we will focus on training some of our existing staff. We have created few new roles within the organization which will specifically handle to the digital media and social media functions. In terms of developing the infrastructure, we are planning to invest in print based technologies such as web-to-print and customization software and machinery.

We are also in the process of developing "new media" portals which will act an electronic version of our printed media products. Again, this is vertical integration within the organization so it will require hiring online media developers and testers. We really hope to

leverage the opportunities offered by the internet into growing and developing our brand. I believe, this will enable us to step into the future of the printing media.

4. How do you plan to use the internet to improve customer experience?

I think the internet could be used in many ways for improving the customer experience. For example we can use the internet to better engage and interact with our customers. We can also use it launch some new products and services which will increase the value proposition for the customer. All in all, we plan to enhance customer service, plan on offering our customers more platforms to interact with us. We also plan to introduce new online based applications where our customers can directly place orders with us using those applications. This will make help the customers because it will be quick and convenient for them to place orders and customise them anywhere they want.

We can also streamline our internal operations using technology. Although this is not directly linked to customer experience but we feel it will help in generating capacity needed to provide the customer with better product delivery and support. Advanced and bigger players are already offering data management services using the internet to their customers. This greatly enhances the value proposition because you are thinking beyond just being a printer. I feel, maybe at some point down the line we could also think about integrating similar services which adds value and enhances customer experience. I feel it pays off in the long run to become a customer centric firm. Printers that are just solely focussed on providing their customer with print as the only service will soon find it difficult to remain relevant in the future. Having a vision for expanding product offering and improving customer experience will what we feel will help us remain competitive into the future.

5. What will be the impact on the product mix and how do you plan to innovate?

The product mix is one key area which will be restructured as we plan to build and execute a hybrid business model of print and digital. The product mix will need to be re thought and re designed by looking at what are the main trends in the market. So far we have seen a rise in customization which has emerged as consistent theme in printing all over the world. Printers are now also becoming interactive and focus on establishing a deeper connection with their customers.

Product mix needs to be diversified beyond just traditional streams of revenue which have been advertising and circulation. New products and services will need to be created via innovation. These products and services could include custom content, consumer insights, and lead generation, and new offerings for customers such as premium content and data-based applications.

How we deliver the content to the customer can improve by innovation. So far, content delivery model has been heavily preoccupied with cost cutting. I believe this needs to change. The focus must now shift to delivering a “profitable core” of unique and brand-defining material. The costs associated with the content delivery system should be better align with the cost of content versus the revenues generated.

Pricing is also an important aspect of the product mix. We need to optimize the pricing of our services and products. This will need to be done by taking into account several factors such as consumer demand, scalability and so on.

6. What sort of changes in the marketing strategy will you have to make?

Marketing is a crucial area within the printing business. We are heavily dependent of maintaining our reader base as acquiring new readers. The marketing in this particular business is under a lot of strain as traditional revenue streams have started to decline. Now marketers are required to look to fresh streams of generating revenues via diverse channels.

Marketing strategies greatly benefit with the use of digital platforms as they enable optimal customer segmentation. This is done through gathering vast amounts of data on consumer behavior and eliciting valuable insights which helps in segmenting the customers. Optimal segmentation enables the marketers to develop targeted content to different segments and hence, likely increasing customer engagement. So essentially, internet and data analytics have enabled to printing firms to develop robust marketing strategies through optimal segmentation. This is done by the thriving printing businesses and as a result they have a much more active and engaged readership than their competition. This directly leads to profitable business growth.

Marketing via digital platforms will also enhance our segmentation capabilities. Segmentation is important in our line of work as we cater to a very diverse and wide range of audience. So it become essential for us to be able to segment them correctly. Again, internet and digital platforms will pave the way for this. Optimal segmentation will enable us to deliver the right message and increase our likelihood of customer engagement. In the mid to long term with increased customer engagement we can develop a closer and personal relationship with our customers. This will ensure longevity and sustainability of our market share. All of this is what will drive our future growth.

7. What, according to you, are the challenges and benefits of adopting the internet?

These mainly relate to saturation and diminishing sales. You see, the print industry is plagued by lack of competency in being able to market your product. With the rise of technology and digitalization the printing industry has fallen behind in terms of developing competencies which the workforce to harness the benefits of technology.

In order for us to grow we need to more customers for our product, which can only be done by creating a demand for our product. There is a common misconception that there are no new customers within the market. I think there is a gap in the market where marketers are failing to create a demand. Internet can be a valuable aid in this process. For example, by engaging the customers through new media platforms and informing them of the online based services which we now provide, I think we should be able to acquire new customers. This can drive our growth and solve financial worries.

In order for printing businesses to really be able to unlock the benefits offered by the internet, they will have to rethink their entire business model. They will have to reconsider what is it that their customers want and how best to service these needs. This can be done through the internet most easily and effectively. Unfortunately, a lot of the printing businesses are not ready for making this transition. They lack a vision for the future and do not see the potential for the benefits offered by the internet. These printing businesses are at a major risk of becoming obsolete with changing times. There are printing businesses which understand that it is essential for them to create new services and products for their customers in order to compete in the market. What is challenging for such firms is the lack of resources. While some have realized the potential for the internet and started investing into developing new products, they still have a long journey ahead of them to see any real benefits.

Key is to have a vision for the future. A printing businesses can start with small steps towards this transition and eventually will find itself making leaps ahead. If they do so now, they are automatically ahead of the pack and it will not be long before they see a rise in their profitability. As I said, in the end it all comes down to whether or not you have that vision for the future.